

Sonification of Health and Environmental Data

SoniHED

Conference 2025

WHEN: 29/01/2025

AT: 08:30-17:30

WHERE:
Digital Futures
and Online

digital futures

Sound for Energy Swedish Energy Agency

SoniHED 2025

Proceedings
of the
3rd Conference on Sonification
of Health and Environmental Data

29 January 2025

Stockholm, Sweden

Edited by Sandra Pauletto

ISBN: 978-91-8106-119-2

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15032831>

Table of Contents

Introduction.....	3
Conference Programme.....	4
Guest Talks Abstracts and Biographies.....	6
SoniHED 2025 Organisation and Articles.....	13
Rosana Sanz, et al. <i>Sleep Quality and Sound: Insights from Hospitalized Patients</i>	14
Abhishek Choubey, et al. <i>Sleeping Soundly: an Interdisciplinary Approach to Communicating Individual Sleep Experiences Through a Shared Sonic Domain</i>	20
Permagnus Lindborg, et al. <i>SleepSound: Charting the Nighttime Soundscape and Sleep Quality in Hong Kong through Machine Listening and AI-supported Information Design</i>	30
Daniel Gea and Gilberto Bernardes. <i>Semantic and Spatial Sound-Object Recognition for Assistive Navigation</i>	38
Georgios Marentakis and Victoria Grace. <i>Guided breathing performance with and without supervision</i>	46
Kajol Rafi and Kjetil Falkenberg. <i>Situationally-Induced Impairments and Child Care: The Case of Browsing an Audio Streaming Platform While Kangarooing</i>	53
Natália Santos and Gilberto Bernardes. <i>A Scoping Review of Emerging AI Technologies in Mental Health Care: Towards Personalized Music Therapy</i>	61
Simon Hallak, Abhishek Choubey and Sandra Pauletto. <i>Sound Asleep: A study on the relationship between emotional state and sound preferences as sleep aid</i>	69
Prithvi Ravi Kantan. <i>Probabilistic Generative Music as a Data Sonification Medium</i>	77

Introduction

The Conference on Sonification of Health and Environmental Data (SoniHED) brings together experts in the fields of sonification, sound design, health and environmental science to propose and discuss novel sonic ways to engage with data from these often interconnected fields.

Sonification, and more generally sound design, sonic interaction design and sound-driven design, are concerned with using data and information in sonic form so that listeners (experts and/or non-experts) can perceive and engage with data structures, complex information and their meaning.

The first SoniHED Conference was organized and chaired in 2014 by Dr Sandra Pauletto and colleagues from the Stockholm Environment Institute at the University of York (<https://www.york.ac.uk/c2d2/seminars/sonihed/>; proceedings: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15032756>). The second edition took place in 2022 at KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Sweden (see <https://soundforenergy.net/sonihed2022>; proceedings: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7243532>).

SoniHED 2025, the third edition of the conference, was organised thanks to a collaboration between the Sound for Energy Project (<https://soundforenergy.net>), the EU MSCA Lullabyte Doctoral Network (<https://lullabyte.eu>) and the DRS Special Interest Group in Sound-Driven Design (<https://www.designresearchsociety.org/cpages/sdd-sig>), and with the support of Digital Futures Centre (<https://www.digitalfutures.kth.se>). The conference was hybrid and took place in Stockholm at KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Sweden, on Wednesday 29 January 2025.

This year we especially welcomed research addressing the theme: sound and sleep. Sleep and relaxation play crucial roles in maintaining physical, mental, and emotional health. Many people use sound and music to aid their sleep. In this context, there is growing interest in interactive sonic designs and applications informed by sleep data that can embed in our lives and sleeping habits in a more sustainable and personal way.

In addition to peer-reviewed papers, the conference included three panels of experts on sound and sleep, sound and environmental sustainability, and sound and movement.

The SoniHED 2025 Team

Sandra Pauletto (KTH, Sweden), Stefano Delle Monache (IRCAM, France), Nicolas Misdariis (IRCAM, France), Elif Özcan (TU Delft), Abhishek Choubey (KTH, Sweden), David Holmgren (KTH, Sweden)

Conference Programme

08:30-08:45 Welcome by SoniHED Chair Sandra Pauletto

08:45-10:15 GUEST PANEL 1: SOUND AND SLEEP - Chair: Elif Özcan

- *Lullabies. Evidences of an exciting relationship* - Miriam Akkermann (FU Berlin, Germany)
- *The use of music as a sleep strategy: Who, when, why and what?* - Kira Vibe Jespersen (Aarhus University, Denmark)
- *Are you sleeping? Auditory processing during sleep* - Thomas Andrillon (Institute du Cerveau, ICM, France)

10:15-10:30 BREAK

10:30-11:15 PAPER SESSION 1: SLEEP - Chair: Georgios Marentakis

- Rosana Sanz, et al., *Sleep Quality and Sound: Insights from Hospitalized Patients*
- Abhishek Choubey, et al., *Sleeping Soundly: an Interdisciplinary Approach to Communicating Individual Sleep Experiences Through a Shared Sonic Domain*
- Permagmus Lindborg, et al., *SleepSound: Charting the Nighttime Soundscape and Sleep Quality in Hong Kong through Machine Listening and AI-supported Information Design*

11:15-12:00 PAPER SESSION 2: CARE - Chair: Rosana Sanz

- Daniel Gea and Gilberto Bernardes, *Semantic and Spatial Sound-Object Recognition for Assistive Navigation*
- Georgios Marentakis and Victoria Grace. *Guided breathing performance with and without supervision*
- Kajol Rafi and Kjetil Falkenberg, *Situationally-Induced Impairments and Child Care: The Case of Browsing an Audio Streaming Platform While Kangarooing*

12:00-13:00 LUNCH

13:00-14:30 GUEST PANEL: SOUND AND SUSTAINABILITY - Chair: Sandra Pauletto

- *The home: an arena for transforming the energy system* - Cecilia Katzeff (KTH, Sweden)
- *Peripheral & persuasive sounds* - Katharina Groß-Vogt (IEM, Austria)
- *Reflections and transformation. On sustainable transport futures* - Mattias Höjer (KTH, Sweden)

14:30-14:45 BREAK

14:45-16:15 GUEST PANEL 3: SOUND AND MOVEMENT- Chair: Stefano Delle Monache

- *Movement in music performance: lessons for movement sonification?* - Sofia Dahl (Aalborg University, Denmark)
- *Decoding, measuring and enhancing human movement* - Lanie Gutierrez-Farewik (KTH, Sweden)
- *Movement Sonification: from creative applications to rehabilitation* - Frédéric Bevilacqua (IRCAM, France)

16:15-17:00 PAPER SESSION 3: EXPRESSION - Chair: Nicolas Misdariis

- Natália Santos and Gilberto Bernardes. *A Scoping Review of Emerging AI Technologies in Mental Health Care: Towards Personalized Music Therapy*
- Simon Hallak, Abhishek Choubey and Sandra Pauletto. *Sound Asleep: A study on the relationship between emotional state and sound preferences as sleep aid*
- Prithvi Ravi Kantan. *Probabilistic Generative Music as a Data Sonification Medium*

17:00-17:30 Final Discussion and Conclusion

Guest Talks Abstracts and Biographies

GUEST PANEL 1 : SOUND AND SLEEP

Kira Vibe Jespersen, Aarhus University, Denmark

The use of music as a sleep strategy: Who, when, why and what?

Music is often mentioned as a self-help tool for facilitating sleep. This leads to questions about how common this practice is, why people use music as a sleep aid, and which music they use? In a recent survey study among the Danish population, we shed light on the prevalence and frequency of using music for sleep as well as the characteristics of people using music compared to other sleep strategies. When looking at the type of music used for sleep, slow, soothing music is typically recommended. However, when analysing music tracks from Spotify sleep playlists, we find that people use a broad range of music genres. Even though sleep music is generally less energetic, more instrumental and acoustic than general music, we also see a large variation in the music characteristics. This variation may be explained by individual preferences and different motivations for using music as a sleep aid.

Biography

Kira Vibe Jespersen, PhD, is MSc in psychology with an additional BA in Music Therapy. She holds a PhD in health sciences from Aarhus University, where she is currently Associate Professor at the Danish National Research Foundation's Center of Excellence for Music in the Brain. Her research focuses on clinical applications of music with a particular interest in the effect of music on sleep and the use of music for insomnia. Using both behavioral and neuroimaging methods, she evaluates the effects of music for improving sleep as well as the potential neurophysiological mechanisms underlying these effects. In a related line of research, she is mapping the use of music as a sleep aid in the general population and use surveys and big data from Spotify and YouTube to investigate the universal and subgroup characteristics of sleep music.

Miriam Akkermann, FU Berlin, Germany

Lullabies. Evidences of an exciting relationship

Lullabies seem to have existed throughout all centuries and have been traced in many different cultures. However, not every song that is considered a Lullaby was written to sing children to sleep. The term subsumes – from a western music perspective – many love songs, Abendlieder and Christmas carols. In a broader sense, “sleep music” also includes sound scape compositions, ambient music, and drone or noise-based audio tracks including nature sounds. In contrary, not all music tracks used for going to sleep would be considered a Lullaby. From a musicological perspective, Lullabies are hence hard to define. At the same time, this very heterogeneous collection can provide some insights into how people have thought about the relationship between music and sleep.

Biography

Miriam Akkermann is musicologist and sound artist. She received a PhD in musicology from the Berlin University of the Arts, and completed her habilitation at Bayreuth University. Her research areas include music of the 20th and 21st century, computer music and music technology, digital musicology, musical performance practices and archiving music. A special emphasis lies on examining the intersection of music research and artistic practice. Within the framework of "Lullabyte," the researches focus is set on the effect of music on sleep. Since April 2024, she holds the Ernst-von-Siemens endowed professorship for new music at FU Berlin.

Thomas Andrillon, Institute du Cerveau (ICM), France

Are you sleeping? Auditory processing during sleep

When we sleep, we are generally unable to respond to external stimuli, such as sounds. However, this state of unresponsiveness is not absolute. Even when sleepers do not visibly react to external sounds, it does not mean that these auditory inputs are not processed by the brain. In this presentation, I will discuss a series of studies demonstrating that our brain continues to monitor the environment during sleep and is capable of performing complex cognitive processes. For instance, salient stimuli, such as hearing one's own name or the cry of one's baby, are more likely to trigger an awakening. Even when we remain asleep, the auditory cortex can faithfully encode auditory information. Brain activity recordings during sleep reveal that the brain can process more complex auditory information, such as extracting the meaning of a word or allocating attention. However, certain processes, particularly predictive ones, seem to be significantly impaired during sleep. Additionally, sleep appears to inhibit the formation of new memories, rendering most of these processes implicit and ultimately forgotten. In conclusion, the sleeping brain is far from inactive. Instead, it flexibly monitors its surroundings while maintaining the unique constraints and limitations of the sleep state.

Biography

I am a neuroscientist based in France, at the Pitié-Salpêtrière Hospital. I am part of the Mov'it research group and the "Sleep, Dreams and Consciousness" team (DreamTeam). I hold a Bachelor in Life Sciences and did my Cognitive Neuroscience Master thesis in the laboratory of Prof Giulio Tononi and Prof Chiara Cirelli (University of Wisconsin at Madison), under the supervision of Prof Yuval Nir. I graduated from a PhD in Cognitive Sciences at the École Normale Supérieure in Paris, under the supervision of Sid Kouider. I then moved to Australia to do a post-doc with Prof Nao Tsuchiya (Monash University) and Prof Joel Pearson (University of New South Wales). I moved back in Paris in February 2021.

GUEST PANEL 2: SOUND AND ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY

Cecilia Katzeff, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Sweden

The home - an arena for transforming the energy system

My presentation focuses on the role of households in the transition to a sustainable energy system and the transformation of the electricity system into a smart grid. It will address people's relationship to energy and how this is intertwined with technology development and the home environment. As private households are often referred to an "untapped source of flexibility" I will speak a bit about how this is supposed to happen. What type of expectations are formulated? What type of technology is supposed to support the change of practices in the home and what is expected from households themselves? I will bring up the concept of the home and how it is affected by the digital change society is going through. In regarding the home as an intersection of streams such as policies, infrastructure, technologies, norms and everyday life it becomes an arena for research questions studying people's participation in the energy system. The home forms a central part of people's lives. It is not just a residence or building, but also a social place. Does the implementation of smart grids in society lead to a digital revolution in the home? This is something we will probably be able to tell in the future. Right now, we may speculate and learn from history. How has the home been affected by past technological changes? During the Industrial Revolution, it wasn't just industry that was transformed by new technology. The transformation also occurred in the homes. Finally, I will talk about a returning type of organization of the energy system in Sweden – the energy community. At the end of 2024 the Swedish Energy Agency delivered a governmental inquiry specifying what type of actions need to be taken to speed up the development of energy communities in Sweden. I will talk about some preliminary findings from our research in two ongoing projects on the role of households in this emerging type of actor in the energy system.

Biography

Cecilia Katzeff is an associate professor in human-computer interaction at the Dep. of Sustainable development, Environmental Science and Engineering, SEED, KTH and a faculty member of Digital Futures. Katzeff holds a PhD in psychology and her research focuses citizens' role in the energy transition. It includes questions around how people relate to energy in their everyday life and how digital technology and policy development plays a role in this relationship. As the electricity system becomes more and more automated, Katzeff's research also raises questions on how this affects our homes and the dynamics of households. Linked to this, the research explores the emerging phenomenon of energy communities as an engine in the energy transition, in urban as well as in rural areas of Sweden. Katzeff is on the board for the organization Sveriges Energigemenskaper and is the KTH project partner and part of the management group of Resistance and Power – Smart Grids for The Many People (Family Kamprad Foundation) – a research program collaboratively run by KTH, Chalmers, Lund University, Linköping University and Uppsala University.

Peripheral & persuasive sounds

In sonification, the objective representation of sound has long been sought, but no standards have yet been achieved. One reason for this is that sound is perceived very subjectively, based on our listening and music experiences. The most effective examples of sonification are based on its evocative, unconventional and affective character. In a world that relies ever less on objective truths, we can use this emotional nature of sound to move people towards preferred behavior, i.e. for persuasive design.

In our SIDlab, we have a focus on sustainability, so that even when teaching and researching sound, the content should work towards the UN SDGs. The projects presented at <https://sidlab.iem.sh/> range from small seminar papers to Master's theses in sound engineering and sound design. We want to sensitize students to the climate crisis, for example, and challenge their skills and creativity to try out small solutions. While we adhere to a broad definition of sustainability that includes also social dimensions, in this talk I will focus on examples that are intended to support a more ecological lifestyle. On the one hand, sonifying data sets can leave a different impression than reading numbers or looking at a dry graph - as we can try out by listening to the "heartbeat of the Earth". The effect of engagement is difficult to research, but is evident in the proliferation of sonification in the media. On the other hand, we have gained experience in augmenting interactions in the real world with informed sounds. In this case, the sounds need to be subtle and acceptable, which is a major design challenge. Ideally, additions to the soundscape are only peripheral to our attention, so do not interfere, but can come into our focus if we want them to. We conducted basic research to find out how much information can be conveyed at this periphery, and set up prototypes of peripheral and persuasive sound. In an earlier experiment, our colleagues were given feedback on the power consumption in the kitchen of our institute by changing the reverberation of the room in real time, making the abstract entity of energy perceptible. And recently, a Master thesis explored the effect of different interactive sounds for driving electric cars, with the aim of achieving a more relaxed and therefore more ecological driving style.

Biography

Katharina Groß-Vogt researches and teaches sonification and sonic interaction design, i.e. two interdisciplinary combining her backgrounds in music and science. She is senior scientist at the Institute of Electronic Music and Acoustics (IEM), University of Music and Performing Arts Graz, Austria. Sonification research projects covered, e.g., physics, climate science, or physiotherapy. For her thesis Sonification of Simulations in Computational Physics she received the Award of Excellence of the Austrian Ministry for Science and Research 2010. Groß-Vogt served as a board member at the International Community of Auditory Display (ICAD) 2012-16 and is part of the Steering Board of the Audio Mostly Conference (since 2020). She runs the SIDlab at IEM with a focus both on sound and sustainability, see <https://sidlab.iem.sh.>

Mattias Höjer, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Sweden

Reflections and transformation. On sustainable transport futures

I have no knowledge from before about sonification, so this is an exciting and unaccustomed context to me. I have been considering what parts of my work would be closest to what I would guess is relevant for sonification researchers, and I then thought about some work I have been doing with the artist Jens Evaldsson. We have made two movies where we explore ways of interacting with a receiver in a very different way than I do when communicating as a researcher. During the conference, I hope to show our latest 5 min movie “Reflections and transformations”, but we are cutting the movie only now. In case that is not ready in time, I will instead show the 6 min movie “Art of Rules” from 2021. Before the movie, I will present work on car travel and greenhouse gas emissions. It will be based on a project with colleagues Jonas Åkerman and Hampus Berg Mårtensson. We have investigated how far electrification of the car fleet, biofuel and sharing of cars can take us towards a sustainable car transport system. We have also explored what would be required by the whole transport system to be in aligned with climate targets. In short, the results indicate that reduced car travel will be required and that electrification does bring down emissions from driving, but that there are large challenges with emissions from production of cars and from what to do with the fossil cars that should no longer be on the roads.

Biography

Mattias Höjer is professor in Environmental Strategic Analysis and Futures Studies at KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Stockholm, Sweden, since 2012. During 2008-2017 he was Director for a Vinnova Center of excellence, CESC, focusing on digitalization for sustainable development. He has been Program director for a doctoral program (Planning and decision analysis) the last ten years. Since beginning of his carrier he has been working on topics related to mitigation of greenhouse gas emissions. His main areas have been buildings and transport, coming from a planning department. The use of digitalization for supporting mitigation of greenhouse gas emissions through a more efficient use of buildings and transport, thus supporting lower total volumes of both buildings and transport, has been a thread that can be traced in his research back to by PhD thesis, called “What is the point of IT?”. Mattias was co-author of “Digital Reset” and member of the expert panel of D4S, Digitalization for Sustainability 2021-2022, who authored that report <https://digitalization-for-sustainability.com>. Ha has also been involved in various groups for supporting policies striving for using digitalization for reduced greenhouse gas emissions.

GUEST PANEL 3: SOUND AND MOVEMENT

Sofia Dahl, Aalborg University, Denmark

Movement in music performance: lessons for movement sonification?

A beginner learning to play the violin can be demanding to listen to. A professional violinist, practicing a difficult passage over and over, can also test our patience despite producing a different quality of sound. In both cases, the novice and expert player engage in motor learning with real time sound feedback. A rough estimate is that 10 000 hours of deliberate

practice is needed to achieve mastery, and sound feedback is an integral part of this process for musicians. Depending on the instrument and type of playing, the feedback may be continuous, such as the sustained sounds produced by bowing or singing, or discretely separated in time, such as the impulse like sounds for keyboards and percussion. In either case, sound feedback helps to develop highly specialized movement patterns resulting in differences in both sound and movement quality between novice and expert, easily distinguishable also for non-experts. During the past century, researchers have studied movement and sound production in music performance, documenting clear differences between skills and novices but also individual differences. These individual differences as well as other, random, variability make it challenging to quantify and describe the movements. When sonifying movements we may face a similar problem: what part of the movement is essential to reinforce and how to deal with individual differences? Should feedback be given continuously or discretely? I will present examples from the study of movement in music performance as well as sounds designed by our team during five years of developing real-time sound feedback to support motor learning for patients re-learning daily activities such as sit-to-stand transfers and gait.

Biography

Sofia Dahl holds a PhD in Speech and Music communication from KTH, Royal Institute of Technology and currently affiliated with Aalborg University, where she is associate professor in music cognition. Originally with a background from electrical engineering and musicology, Dahl's field of research has become increasingly transdisciplinary over time, spanning disciplines such as music psychology, music performance, movement and neuroscience, interaction design, and music acoustics. For the past five years she has collaborated with experts in neurorehabilitation to design sonification for motor learning.

Lanie Gutierrez-Farewik, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Sweden

Decoding, measuring and enhancing human movement

The ability to move is fundamental for humans. The quality and performance of one's movement and walking reflect to a large amount their motor function and ability to synthesize it with perception, cognition and goals. It is important that this relationship is incorporated into techniques aimed to predict movement performance and into interventions and assistive devices aimed to improve movement performance. The KTH MoveAbility research group studies human movement over a range of scales and modalities, in order to decode the complex relationships that govern human movement, to predict the potential for improved mobility in individuals with motor impairment, and to develop active assistive devices. All with the aim to help people move beyond their current capabilities. Our various projects involve patient populations with a range of movement disorders, including stroke, spinal cord injury, cerebral palsy, Parkinsons, and even a normally aging population. Our goals include analyzing neuromuscular function, predicting movement performance, studying added value of various interventions on movement improvement, developing assistive devices that interact with the user to achieve improved walking function, predicting risk of developing shoulder injuries from wheelchair activities, understanding how

sensorimotor interactions affect movement performance, and developing mobile systems to measure and monitor movement in everyday settings.

Biography

Lanie Gutierrez-Farewik is Professor of Biomechanics at KTH Engineering Mechanics, the director of the Promobilia MoveAbility Lab, and the president of Swedish Society of Biomechanics. She has a background in engineering and medical science and nearly a decade of clinical experience with children and adults with motion disorders. She and her research group aim to revolutionize how we understand and assist human movement.

Frédéric Bevilacqua, IRCAM, Paris, FRANCE

Movement Sonification: from creative applications to rehabilitation

My research concerns the design and development of movement-sound interactive systems. Using various motion sensing, these systems allow for controlling or interacting with digital sounds. These systems can be either performed as musical instruments, with a focus on the sound produced (sound-oriented tasks), or be used as movement sonification devices (movement-oriented tasks). Precisely, in the latter case, the primary role for the sound is to act as auditory feedback for a given movement. Through different collaborations, we have been investigated movement sonification to facilitate sensori-motor learning or adaptation, to increase body awareness or to modify body schema in different applications, from walking to various sport exercises. We have also been working on movement sonification for rehabilitation for stroke patients and for people with acquired visual deficiency. In all cases, the sound design is primordial as the sound must be both informative as well as motivational. In a study we compared different movement sonification types (direct sound modulation, musical interaction, and soundscape) in upper-limb movement in hemiparetic and healthy participants. I will also present the system called como-rehabilitation which is a portable movement sonification device using a Raspberry Pi and wireless inertial motion units. This system has been designed to be easily duplicable and adaptable to various rehabilitation exercises with a palette of choices for sounds and music. Targeted first toward supervised self-rehabilitation for stroke patients (an evaluation is currently carried on with therapists), we are currently modifying this device in support to visual impaired patients' rehabilitation.

Biography

Frédéric Bevilacqua is the head of the Sound Music Movement Interaction team at IRCAM in Paris, in the joint research lab on Science & Technology of Music and Sound between IRCAM – CNRS – Sorbonne Université. His research concerns the modelling and the design of interaction between human movement and sound, and the development of gesture-based digital musical systems. The applications range from artistic creation, education to health. Recent projects concerned learning processes, movement sonification and rehabilitation, and collective musical interactions.

SoniHED 2025 Organisation and Articles

Conference Chair

Sandra Pauletto (KTH, Sweden)

Papers Chair

Stefano Delle Monache (IRCAM, France)

Organising Committee

Nicolas Misdariis (IRCAM, France)

Elif Özcan (TU Delft)

Abhishek Choubey (KTH, Sweden)

David Holmgren (KTH, Sweden)

Conference Scientific Committee

Davide Rocchesso, University of Milan, Italy

Simone Spagnol, Iuav University of Venice, Italy

Daniel Hug, Zurich University of the Arts, Switzerland

Niklas Rönnerberg, Linköping University, Sweden

Rod Selfridge, Edinburgh Napier University, UK

Sara Lenzi, University of Deusto, Spain

Georgios Marentakis, Østfold University College, Norway

Davide Andrea Mauro, KreativInstitut.OWL, Paderborn University, Germany

Rosana Sanz, Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain

Sofia Vallejo, IEM, Graz, Austria

Sandra Pauletto, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Sweden

Stefano Delle Monache, IRCAM, Paris

Nicolas Misdariis, IRCAM, Paris

Elif Özcan, TU Delft, The Netherlands

Sleep Quality and Sound: Insights from Hospitalized Patients

Rosana Sanz-Segura
School of Engineering and
Architecture. University of
Zaragoza. Spain.
rsanz@unizar.es

Iris Espallargas
School of Engineering and Architecture.
University of Zaragoza. Spain.
799473@unizar.es

Eduardo Manchado-Pérez
School of Engineering and
Architecture. University of
Zaragoza. Spain.
manchado@unizar.es

ABSTRACT

Advancements in technology and the resulting dehumanization of medical environments, combined with a focus on organizational efficiency, have created significant challenges for the quality of care and the well-being of healthcare professionals. Sleep quality is critical in hospitalised patients' physical and mental recovery, with the hospital soundscape being a major factor affecting rest. This contribution adopts a holistic perspective on the well-being of both patients and caregivers, utilizing user-centred design and open innovation methodologies to establish a shared understanding of the relationship between sleep quality and sound. To get this, the study integrates knowledge from hospitalized patients by collecting valuable insights into how sound impacts sleep quality. The gathered data is analyzed to uncover opportunities for improvement and define design specifications. The initiative aims to identify needs and solutions related to sound while fostering a user-centred approach with a unified language across stakeholders. The findings of this study will serve as the first step of a roadmap, providing design specifications and guidelines for improving sleep quality through sound. These contributions will not only guide future research and development but also redefine the medical care concept, ultimately enhancing patient well-being.

1. INTRODUCTION

The significance of rest for patient recovery is an increasingly explored topic in medicine and healthcare. Proper rest, particularly quality sleep, is essential for physiological recovery, enabling the body to repair tissues, consolidate memory, and regenerate the immune system. Numerous studies have shown that sleep deprivation can negatively impact the immune system, increasing susceptibility to infections and complicating recovery from acute and chronic illnesses (NIH, 2021; Helvig et al., 2016).

*Copyright: ©2025 Rosana Sanz-Segura et al. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15032388>*

Moreover, rest plays a critical role in the mental and emotional recovery of patients. Insufficient or poor-quality sleep can exacerbate stress and anxiety symptoms, affecting mental health and pain perception—factors that interfere with recovery. For instance, studies have documented that patients who receive adequate rest report lower pain levels and improved overall well-being, optimizing their recovery and quality of life (Cambridge University Press, 2020).

Rest also contributes to stabilizing vital functions such as glucose regulation and blood pressure, which are key factors for patients with chronic conditions like diabetes and cardiovascular diseases. In general, prioritizing rest, including both sleep and wakeful relaxation, allows for better organization of physiological resources to combat illness and promote healing (American River Healthcare, 2022).

The impact of sound on rest quality is a widely studied topic, particularly in hospital and urban environments. Exposure to environmental noise, such as traffic, or socio-technological noise, such as medical alarms or healthcare staff activity in intensive care units (ICUs), disrupts the deep sleep phases necessary for patients' physical and mental recovery. Studies indicate that these noises can prolong the time needed to fall asleep and reduce the amount of slow-wave sleep, which is crucial for physiological recovery and immune function (NIH, 2021; Sleep Foundation, 2021).

Some interventions have shown positive effects in mitigating the impact of noise on sleep. For example, exposure to white noise (continuous low-frequency sounds) appears to help reduce the time required to fall asleep, although the benefits vary depending on the characteristics of the noise and the environment. In hospital settings, the use of headphones or earplugs has been shown to improve rest quality by decreasing the number of nighttime awakenings and enhancing patients' subjective perception of sleep (Sleep Foundation, 2021; Basner et al., 2011).

Music has also proven to be an effective intervention for improving sleep quality. Studies have shown that listening to music before bedtime reduces anxiety and promotes deeper rest, even in patients with mild sleep

disorders. However, this intervention is more effective in cases of mild or subclinical insomnia, with benefits increasing over prolonged exposure (Frontiers, 2019). These findings emphasize the importance of managing soundscapes in healthcare settings to optimize patient rest and, consequently, their recovery.

The phenomenon of complex soundscapes, such as those in hospitals, has been extensively studied. In such settings, sounds play a crucial role in directing actions and facilitating staff coordination, where alarms, surgical tools, and conversations contribute to an "acoustic biotope" guiding attention and immediate responses (Özcan et al., 2022). Ecological approaches to operating room acoustics suggest that studying and improving these environments can lead to effective acoustic interventions that enhance surgical team precision, staff well-being, and patient rest (Johannesma & Aertsen, 1979; Aletta et al., 2020).

This project serves as a preliminary phase for replicating research conducted in the Netherlands on the impact of sound sources on hospitalized patients' rest in a neurology ward. Lenzi et al. (2023) in *Disturbed Sleep: Estimating Night-Time Sound Annoyance at a Hospital Ward* analyzed nocturnal sound events and their perceived annoyance levels among patients. The aim was to develop a model informing healthcare staff about the impact of specific sounds on patient sleep quality, providing a design tool to mitigate the negative effects of hospital acoustic environments. The study involved identifying and classifying sound events, analyzing over 9,000 nocturnal sound events across 429 recordings, categorized into nine types (e.g., snoring, speech, alarms, mechanical sounds). Patients' perceived annoyance was measured using a scale of 1 to 3 for each event. Proposed solutions included staff training in noise reduction, redesigning equipment and spaces, and integrating the data into an algorithm for real-time detection of disruptive sound events. This would enable staff to manage noise sources more effectively, improving the nighttime patient experience.

This new research serves as a precursor to replicating the *Disturbed Sleep* study, aiming to investigate how sound sources affect hospitalized patients in specific wards. The objective is to develop a qualitative study of the environment and its users, guiding the next phase of quantitative research involving sleep monitoring in patients. Key actions include defining sleep quality parameters and descriptors concerning sound. This contribution focuses exclusively on the research conducted with patients, analyzing how sound sources impact their rest and recovery in hospital settings. In subsequent phases, the study will be expanded to include investigating other key stakeholders, such as clinical staff and experts from fields like sound-driven design, machine learning, and user-centered interface design. These future stages will aim to integrate diverse perspectives, fostering a comprehensive understanding of the acoustic environment and its effects, and enabling the

co-creation of solutions that address the needs of all involved parties. Additionally, creating a shared vocabulary among all stakeholders will guide specifications for the next phase and provide a roadmap for implementing actions that will contribute to evolving medical care concepts and enhancing patient well-being.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study 1 - Environment

The first study in the research focused on an objective analysis of the hospital environment during a night shift, from the patient's perspective. The procedure involved collecting and examining all sound events occurring during a single night in a patient's room.

A female patient hospitalized in the neurology ward, in a private room, participated in this phase. The research team was allowed to accompany her throughout the night. The patient was selected based on the following criteria recommended by the ward supervisor: sufficient space in the room to accommodate the researcher, the patient's and her family's consent and willingness to participate, and her location in the neurology ward.

Ideally, this environmental investigation would have been conducted in a double room, as it would have provided a richer sound environment. However, the patients who approved our presence were either in individual rooms or did not have roommates.

The procedure was as follows: the researcher entered the patient's room after dinner and visiting hours, at 9:00 PM, and remained there until the nurses' first morning round at 6:00 AM the next day. During this period, the room was occupied by the hospitalized patient in bed, a caregiver in a chair, and the researcher in another chair.

Sound events were documented using pen and paper, noting their type, frequency, and duration (categorized as momentary, prolonged, or constant). The subjective disturbance level experienced by the researcher was assessed using a Likert scale from 1 to 7, with 1 being "not disturbing at all" and 7 being "very disturbing."

The materials used included writing tools and a timer. Electronic devices were avoided to prevent interference with the patient's rest. The data analysis involved manually transcribing the handwritten notes into a computer, and organizing, and classifying the information into tables and diagrams. The results were directly derived from this analysis.

The study was conducted using pen and paper because the technical resources to record sound and video in a non-intrusive manner were not available. It was the first approach focused on immersing in the context and was

considered a less intrusive option than a video camera recording the entire session.

2.2 Study 2 - Patients

The second phase aimed to explore hospitalized patients' sleep experiences in the neurology ward compared to their experiences at home, and to gauge their willingness to participate in the next phase of the Sleep Study replication.

A total of 7 patients participated, of whom 6 were men and 1 was a woman. Patients were recruited based on the ward supervisor's recommendation, selecting those physically and mentally capable of responding to the questions independently and rationally, and who had spent at least three nights hospitalized in the ward.

The experiment consisted of semi-structured, face-to-face interviews where patients answered open-ended questions or rated their responses on a Likert scale. These questions focused on comparing their sleep experiences in the hospital to those at home, identifying sound events, assessing their level of disturbance, and determining their willingness to participate in a second phase of the study involving sound recordings.

All interviews were recorded using a mobile phone and transcribed using the Transkriptor app, producing a PDF of the conversation. The transcripts were then manually cleaned and corrected to remove unnecessary data, off-topic comments, and transcription errors. No additional materials were required for this phase.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Study 1 - Environment

The aim of the study on the nocturnal sound environment at Miguel Servet Hospital in Zaragoza was to identify and analyze the sound sources present during the night and to document the physical layout of the rooms.

As previously mentioned, the study was conducted in a single-patient room occupied by the patient, a caregiver, and the researcher. The room was located midway down the corridor, between the central staff area (with the call button) and the end of the neurology ward. Adjacent rooms were also occupied by other patients. The layout and elements of the room are shown in the following diagram.

Figure 1. Diagram of a single-patient room

The patient's rest began at 9:00 PM when the lights were turned off, blinds lowered, and silence was maintained in the room. At this time, external noises were comparable to those during the daytime.

At 11:00 PM, the nurses conducted their first round of administering medication, followed shortly after by the nursing assistants, who checked on patients, changed diapers, and ensured everything was in order. From this point until 6:00 AM, when the first morning nursing round began, staff did not enter the rooms unless called.

The following tables summarize the sound events recorded during this period, as well as the previously mentioned interruptions, detailing their duration, frequency, and perceived disturbance level.

EVENTOS SONOROS	HORARIO	DURACIÓN	REPETICIÓN	NIVEL DE PERTURBACIÓN
Aire acondicionado	De 23:30 a 6:00	Constante	Constante	Bajo
Ruidos silla acompañantes	De 23:30 a 6:00	Momentáneo	11	Bajo
Ruido movimiento paciente	De 23:30 a 6:00	Momentáneo	6	Bajo
Timbre central	De 01:00 a 6:00	Segundos	2	Alto
Puertas	De 23:30 a 6:00	Momentáneo	4	Alto
Golpes	De 23:30 a 6:00	Momentáneos	3	Medio
Voces de externas a la habitación	De 23:30 a 6:00	Minutos	5	Alto
Pasos	De 23:30 a 6:00	Unos segundos	4	Bajo
Carrito de medicinas	23:00 y 6:00	Unos segundos	3	Alto
Voz paciente	De 23:30 a 6:00	Unos segundos	3	Alto
Ronquidos y suspiros	De 23:30 a 6:00	Constante	Constante	Medio
Tos	De 23:30 a 6:00	Momentáneo	5	Medio

Table 1. Sound events during a night shift

INTERRUPCIONES	HORARIO	DURACIÓN	REPETICIÓN	NIVEL DE PERTURBACIÓN
Enfermería medicamentos	23:06	45"	1	Muy alta
TCAE mirar pañal	23:21	1'30"	1	Muy alta
Vuelta para otros pacientes	00:06	10'	1	Muy alta
Ruido movimiento paciente	06:10	5'	1	Muy alta

Table 2. Interruptions during the patient's rest period

As observed, some events were more frequent throughout the night but were not necessarily the most disturbing or disruptive for the patient. Disturbance depended not only on the occurrence of these events but also on their intensity and duration.

3.2 Study 2 - Patients

The second study focused on assessing the sleep quality of patients and the sound events they perceived, as well as their willingness to participate in subsequent research phases.

Regarding sleep quality, most patients reported that their sleep in the hospital was inferior to their sleep at home. Key findings included:

- 6 out of 7 of patients reported more frequent sleep interruptions during their hospital stay.
- At home, patients averaged more hours of sleep, compared to the hours in the hospital.
- Only 2 out of 7 felt they achieved a quality of rest comparable to their home. One patient attributed this improvement to pain relief provided by medication.

The primary differences lay in involuntary interruptions, with patients describing greater difficulty maintaining continuous sleep in the hospital. Noise and medical interruptions were significant contributors to this discrepancy.

Patients identified several sources of noise or sleep disruptions during hospitalization. The most frequently mentioned were:

- Medical procedures: Activities by staff, such as entering rooms or handling devices, affected rest for 4 out of 7 of patients.
- Snoring: Mentioned as a nuisance by 2 out of 7 of patients in shared rooms.
- Caregivers or visitors: Reported as a moderate disturbance by 3 out of 7 of patients.
- Cart wheels: Noted as bothersome by 2 out of 7 of patients, though less frequently.

Specific noises, such as infusion pumps and air conditioning, were highlighted for their detectability even during quieter periods at night. However, 3 out of 7 stated that the general sound environment did not significantly disturb them, or they were able to adapt to it.

Regarding participation in studies related to hospital sound monitoring, responses varied:

- 4 out of 7 were willing to collaborate, provided the objectives were clear and recordings ensured confidentiality.
- 2 out of 7 expressed reluctance or refusal, citing privacy concerns or potential inconvenience.
- One patient was indifferent, remarking that "there's no need to record room sounds."

Patients who viewed such studies as beneficial emphasized the potential to improve the hospital environment and the rest experience for future patients. Clear and ongoing communication played a pivotal role

in achieving a "shared language" between researchers and participants. This was especially evident when addressing privacy concerns and explaining study objectives. For instance, one participant expressed initial hesitation about sound recordings but later agreed to participate after a detailed explanation of data confidentiality measures. Another patient emphasized the need for explicit communication about the purpose of the study, which researchers addressed by providing examples of how sound data could improve hospital practices. These efforts not only built trust but also helped align the understanding of both parties regarding the study's goals.

Challenges in communication arose primarily from the diversity of patients' backgrounds and health conditions, which required researchers to tailor their approach. For example, one participant, unfamiliar with digital recording methods, required additional clarification on how recordings would be managed and used. Similarly, patients in shared rooms sometimes had differing opinions on the intrusiveness of noise, requiring the team to mediate and establish a mutual understanding of acceptable study conditions. These examples demonstrate the iterative and collaborative process of creating a shared understanding, ultimately enabling meaningful engagement with the research.

4. DISCUSSION

The findings of this study highlight the profound impact of sound sources on the quality of sleep of hospitalized patients and reveal a multifaceted problem. Firstly, nocturnal sound events, such as medical alarms, healthcare staff activities, and environmental noises (carts, slamming doors, conversations), were identified as significant factors disrupting rest. The characterization of the hospital acoustic environment showed that not only sound intensity but also the regularity and psychoacoustic characteristics of the sounds affect subjective perception and patients' ability to rest. These results align with previous studies emphasizing the importance of designing acoustic environments to promote hospital well-being (NIH, 2021; Özcan et al., 2022).

As a contribution of this research, a series of actions are proposed to improve a sound ecosystem focused on the comprehensive well-being of patients and caregivers:

- Awareness and training. Develop educational programs not only for staff but also at the hospital level on the impact of noise and its management, integrating practical acoustic reduction guides. Awareness-raising sessions could be held on the individual and collective impact of each hospital agent's sound sources and noise and their effect on the patient's recovery and the optimal development of clinical activities.
- Technological interventions. One option could be to implement silent notification systems, such as visual alarms and alerts on mobile devices,

which do not necessarily need to be hospital equipment but could be an app installed on individual mobile devices. Additionally, tying in with the previous point on awareness, a visual sound meter could be implemented to indicate the state of the environment and encourage those present to be mindful of the noise they produce. An option might also be to integrate a device that could emit relaxing background sounds, such as white noise, adjustable to the patient's personal preferences.

- Redesign and maintenance of medical equipment. As much as possible, maintain equipment in good condition to avoid unnecessary noises such as squeaky cart wheels and low-noise operating medical equipment.
- Operational management focused on prioritizing patients' rest, coordinating medical rounds to minimize interruptions, and establish "quiet zones" during key rest hours.
- And having clear policies. Communicate to patients and staff the strategies and benefits of noise reduction measures to encourage their adoption.

Lastly, design specifications are written for the development of future quantitative research where sound events are recorded and correlated with patient sleep quality.

Patients' interests and needs lie in their own comfort. Evidently, they are the ones who are ill, and what they need is to achieve adequate rest to promote a quick recovery. As for the system for collecting and gathering sound information, accessible interfaces will be essential to allow customization of acceptable noise levels. An important aspect to consider is that the equipment should not interfere with the patient's activities, meaning it should neither obstruct nor inconvenience, trying to respect personal space. The device must be understandable to them or at least provide basic instructions or guidelines to allow them to stop recordings if they do not want the sound to be recorded at any time.

The findings of this study highlight the significant influence of sound events on the sleep quality of hospitalized patients. However, a noteworthy aspect is an observation that some participants do not perceive certain sounds as disruptive, raising questions about the inherent subjectivity of acoustic experiences and their impact on patients' well-being. This phenomenon underscores the importance of avoiding hasty generalizations unsupported by data, as noise perception varies significantly among individuals.

Personal context plays a key role in the interpretation of sound stimuli. Factors such as health status, prior experiences, expectations of the hospital environment,

and familiarity with ambient noise levels can modulate patients' responses to sound. For instance, a patient living in an urban environment may be more accustomed to high noise levels and therefore perceive hospital noise as less disruptive than someone from a quiet rural setting. Additionally, the emotional and physical state of patients, such as anxiety, pain, or the use of sedatives, can also influence their sensitivity to noise.

This finding has significant implications for designing interventions to improve the hospital's acoustic environment. Instead of adopting a uniform approach, it is necessary to consider the diversity of individual perceptions and adapt strategies to address the specific needs of different patient profiles. For example, providing customizable options, such as devices emitting white noise or relaxing sounds adjusted to the patient's preferences, could be a more effective and respectful measure of individual variations.

On the other hand, the variability in noise perception also presents methodological challenges for research. Future studies should be designed to capture this subjectivity, possibly using qualitative tools such as in-depth interviews or self-report scales that explore how personal context and patient experiences influence their perceptions. Additionally, it is suggested to complement these data with objective measurements, such as electronically recorded noise levels, to contrast and enrich the understanding of the acoustic environment's impact.

Regarding the study's limitations, we highlight a limited sample size; the small sample restricts the generalization of the findings. We must also address data collection bias; the absence of electronic devices in the first study may have influenced the accuracy of sound event recording. Additionally, the complexity of the acoustic environment presents challenges, as the multiple sources and characteristics of hospital sounds make isolating key variables difficult. Another critical limitation is the study's focus on individual patient rooms. Conducting the research in shared rooms would likely introduce additional noise sources, such as interactions between roommates, visitors, and overlapping medical procedures, which were not considered in this study. Lastly, the subjectivity and perspective of the patient must be noted, as some results reflect individual adaptations to noise, potentially underestimating the broader impact of certain sound sources. These factors underscore the need for further research with larger, more diverse samples and methodological approaches that address the complexities of shared hospital environments.

In conclusion, we can affirm that this study provides a valuable initial framework for addressing the impact of the sound environment in hospitals, although future quantitative research will be essential to validate the proposed interventions and extend their applicability. It also emphasizes the need to critically address individual

perceptions. Recognizing and respecting differences in how patients experience sound will not only strengthen the validity of future research but also enable the design of more inclusive and effective interventions that promote the overall well-being of patients in hospital settings.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study provides significant insights into the relationship between the hospital soundscape and the sleep quality of hospitalized patients, contributing to a growing body of research on optimizing rest in medical settings. The findings confirm that nocturnal sound events adversely affect sleep quality, with implications for both physical and mental recovery. The study emphasizes that sound intensity, frequency, and psychoacoustic characteristics are key determinants of patients' subjective perception and their ability to rest.

The research also highlights the multifaceted nature of the problem, requiring a holistic approach to address the needs of diverse stakeholders, including patients, healthcare professionals, and design teams. Proposed solutions include fostering awareness and training programs for hospital staff, implementing adaptive technologies such as silent alarms and personalized soundscapes, and redesigning medical equipment and hospital environments to minimize noise disruptions. Furthermore, operational strategies, such as optimizing medical rounds and creating "quiet zones," are essential for supporting uninterrupted rest.

Importantly, this research underscores the value of user-centered methodologies and interdisciplinary collaboration in developing effective and practical interventions. While the study was limited by its small sample size and the subjective nature of certain findings, it establishes a robust framework for future quantitative investigations, particularly in correlating sound events with objective measures of sleep quality.

By prioritizing a shared language among stakeholders and fostering the co-creation of innovative solutions, this research paves the way for redefining hospital acoustic environments. Ultimately, these efforts aim to enhance patient well-being, optimize recovery outcomes, and establish new standards for patient-centered care in healthcare facilities.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] National Institutes of Health (NIH) News in Health, "Good Sleep for Good Health," 2021.
- [2] A. Helvig, S. Wade, and L. Hunter-Eades, "Good Sleep for Good Health," in *J. Advanced Nursing*, 2016.
- [3] Cambridge University Press, *The Handbook of Wellness Medicine*, 2020.
- [4] American River Healthcare, "The Science of Rest: Why Resting is So Important for Recovery," 2022.
- [5] M. Basner, et al., "Single and combined effects of air, road, and rail traffic noise on sleep and recuperation," in *Sleep*, vol. 34, no. 1, pp. 11–23, 2011.
- [6] National Institutes of Health (NIH) News in Health, "Good Sleep for Good Health," 2021.
- [7] Sleep Foundation, "How Noise Can Affect Your Sleep Satisfaction," 2021.
- [8] *Frontiers in Psychology*, "Music on Prescription to Aid Sleep Quality: A Literature Review," 2019.
- [9] E. Özcan, C.L.H. Broekmeulen, Z.A. Luck, M. van Velzen, P.J. Stappers, and J.R. Edworthy, "Acoustic Biotopes, Listeners and Sound-Induced Action: A Case Study of Operating Rooms," in *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health*, vol. 19, no. 24, 16674, 2022.
- [10] P.I.M. Johannesma and A.M.H.J. Aertsen, "Categorization of Acoustic Patterns and Behavioural Responses in Natural Habitats: An Ecological Approach," in *Ecological Acoustics Studies*, vol. 34, no. 1, pp. 67–83, 1979.
- [11] F. Aletta, J. Kang, and Ö. Axelsson, "Soundscape Approach Integrations and the Human Health Implications," in *Handbook of Soundscape and Wellbeing Research*, Springer, 2020.
- [12] S. Lenzi, P. Lindborg, N. Han, S. Spagnol, D. Kamphuis, and E. Özcan, "Disturbed sleep: Estimating night-time sound annoyance at a hospital ward," in *Proc. Forum Acusticum*, pp. 2607–2614, European Acoustics Association, 2023.

Sleeping Soundly: an Interdisciplinary Approach to Communicating Individual Sleep Experiences Through a Shared Sonic Domain

Abhishek Choubey

KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Sweden
achoubey@kth.se

Samuel Morgan

University of Stuttgart, Germany
samuel.morgan@ipvs.uni-stuttgart.de

Silvia Genovese

Aarhus University, Denmark
silviagenovese@clin.au.dk

Tinke van Buijtene

Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Spain
tinke.vanbuijtene@upf.edu

Ali Saberi

Radboud University, The Netherlands
ali.saberi@radboudumc.nl

Annika Partmann

University of Fribourg, Switzerland
annika.partmann@unifr.ch

Bagmish Sabhapondit

Endel Sound GmbH, Germany
bagmish@endel.io

Michelle George

ICM - Paris Brain Institute, France
michelle.george@icm-institute.org

Tristan O'Leary

Freie Universität Berlin, Germany
tristan.o.learny@fu-berlin.de

Zhenxing Hu

Université Marie et Louis Pasteur, France
zhenxing.hu@femto-st.fr

ABSTRACT

Sleep is a universal behaviour, being essential to physical and mental wellbeing, yet it remains an individual and largely incommunicable experience. During sleep, our consciousness is altered, involving diminished perceptions of the external world. The auditory system, however, remains responsive, opening possibilities for using sound as a two-way method of communication during sleep. This paper explores the use of objective measurements to relate two individuals' subjective sleep experiences via a shared sonic domain, and in doing so details an ongoing interdisciplinary project which integrates knowledge from neuroscience, psychology, data science, sound and music computing, and musicology.

The project, once implemented, will transform real-time physiological data from two sleeping participants into abstract soundscapes through sonification, thereby facilitating a reciprocal interaction within a closed-loop system. This forms the basis for a planned immersive public installation, through which synchronised soundscapes, visualisations, and educational content invite audiences to engage with sleep science and reflect on their own experiences.

This paper details an iterative design process, guided by the Double Diamond framework. It addresses conceptual challenges of the project, such as integrating knowledge from multiple disciplines, relating subjective experience to sonic representations, and applying analytical techniques within an artistic framework. Practical and ethical issues regarding the implementation of the system are also discussed. This paper highlights collaborative efforts from ten doctoral candidates, whose expertise shaped the project.

Copyright: © 2025 Choubey et al. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15032422>

1. INTRODUCTION

Sleep presents a paradox: it is universal, yet deeply personal, and cannot easily be shared. This unique, altered state of consciousness has long captivated scientists and artists alike, who strive to express its intangible nature in more concrete forms. Across cultures and eras, sleep has been a recurrent theme, appearing in mythological and religious works [1]. For example, the Vedic and Upanishadic literature of the Indus Valley civilisation (11th–16th century BC), as well as ancient Chinese and Greek writings, offer reflections on sleep and dreams [2, 3]. Similarly in visual art, Piero della Francesca's *Dream of Constantine* (1452) and Sandro Botticelli's *Mars and Venus* (1483) offer mythological representations of sleep. In later centuries, attention shifted to the exploration of the subconscious through dreams. Surrealist artworks, such as those of Salvador Dalí (see Fig. 1), depict the sleep experience using the particular characteristics of 'hypnagogic hallucinations'—vivid sensory experiences that can emerge during the transition between wakefulness and light stages of sleep [4].

Figure 1: Salvador Dalí's *Le Sommeil* (*Sleep*) (1937).

Sleep has also served as inspiration within classical mu-

sic. Johannes Brahms’s *Wiegenlied (Lullaby)*, Op. 49 No. 4 (1868) remains one of the most iconic cradle lullabies, and Johann Sebastian Bach purportedly composed the *Goldberg Variations* (1741) as a remedy for insomnia [5]. In addition to aiding sleep, orchestral works have also depicted it, as heard in Hector Berlioz’s *Symphonie Fantastique* (1830), where a drug-induced slumber carries the protagonist into uncanny visions. More recently, Max Richter created *Sleep* (2015) [6] based on input from neuroscientist David Eagleman. This 8-hour piece, structured to echo Bach’s *Goldberg Variations*, is designed to be ‘slept through’, blending music and neuroscience into an immersive experience which is often performed overnight to explore the interplay between sound and sleep.

In recent years, the exploration of sleep in art has taken on new dimensions, with contemporary artists incorporating multisensory experiences and cutting-edge technology. Works such as Matthew Bird’s *Dormitorium* (2017) (see Fig. 2), [7] and Sally Anderson’s *Sleep Sounds* (2018) [8] exemplify this interdisciplinary approach. Bird’s installation blends clinical aesthetics with familiar comforts, creating an environment featuring pulsing lights that mimic natural sleep cycles, while Anderson transforms auditory sleep aids into visual art, examining how modern technology influences our perceptions of sleep. These efforts build upon historical traditions while integrating neuroscience, music, and visual art, offering fresh perspectives that bridge scientific understanding and artistic expression.

While most art depicts an individual notion of sleep, few have explored what it might mean to interactively ‘share’ such an experience. Here, we present a project that is novel in its approach, as it intends to address this gap by using modern technology to facilitate such an interaction, transforming the subjective and isolated nature of sleep into a form that can be collectively experienced.

Figure 2: Matthew Bird’s *Dormitorium* (2017). [7]

1.1 Sound as a Medium for Shared Sleep Experience

The act of sleeping represents an altered state in which external perceptions fade, yet certain sensory systems, such as hearing, remain active [9, 10]. This characteristic opens the door to using sound as a medium not only for sleep aid [11], but also to express and connect with the otherwise-elusive experience of sleep.

In an era which explores the use of scientific knowledge for media experiences, the potential for sound to commu-

nicate subjective phenomena such as sleep offers new avenues for interaction and understanding. In this context, many interdisciplinary collaborations have embraced sonification—the process of translating data into sound—as a powerful tool for making abstract or subjective phenomena more tangible [12–14]. By converting objective data into auditory formats, sonification offers an intuitive and engaging way to discover otherwise-hidden patterns and dynamics, serving both functional and artistic purposes. For example, it has been employed to transform seismic activity into musical compositions [15], represent astronomical data [16, 17], and raise awareness about climate change [18].

Similarly, technologies for measuring brain activity, such as electroencephalography (EEG), have been embraced in the creation of musical compositions. Alvin Lucier’s *Music for Solo Performer* (1965) (see Fig. 3) pioneered the use of brain waves to generate sound, transforming neural activity into an auditory performance [19, 20]. Similarly, David Rosenboom’s *On Being Invisible* (1977) [21] explored auditory-evoked responses, using changes in brain signals to shape musical output. More recently, brain wave sonification has expanded into interactive installations such as *MoodMixer* (2011) [22], in which participants navigate a musical latent space by altering their cognitive states via wearable EEG technology. Projects such as *Music for Brain Waves* (2018) [23] further demonstrate the creative potential of EEG-based compositions using neurofeedback, bridging neuroscience and art in innovative ways.

Figure 3: Alvin Lucier performs *Music for Solo Performer*. Photograph: PR handout (sourced from The Guardian).

EEG is also the primary tool for objective sleep measurement, and its sonic representation has been explored as an alternative medium to both understand the sleep process and express it creatively [24–26]. Sonification can provide novel sonic representations of EEG and other physiological features, thereby offering a more intuitive understanding of sleep patterns. The project described in this paper builds on these developments, employing sonification to explore the ambiguity of the individual sleep experience.

1.2 Project Overview: Designing a Shared Sleep Installation

This project involves real-time sleep measurements from two participants, transforming their physiological data into

evolving soundscapes. Each participant listens to the sonified data of the other, creating a shared and reciprocal experience within a closed-loop system. This bi-directional interaction forms the foundation of an upcoming immersive public installation, which serves as the project's final output. Within the installation space, synchronised soundscapes from both participants, along with accompanying visualisations and educational content, will also be presented to an external audience, encouraging them to engage with sleep science and reflect on how this relates to their own experiences.

This project is an ongoing collaborative effort from a network of ten doctoral candidates, working together remotely to integrate diverse disciplines including neuroscience, psychology, human-computer interaction, data science, sound and music computing, and musicology. Neuroscience provides insights into the physiological processes of sleep, while psychology examines emotional responses to sonified data. Sonic interaction design and human-computer interaction play key roles in shaping the immersive installation, being facilitated by the principles of data science. Sound and music computing, meanwhile, provides the tools to create soundscapes, informed by knowledge from musicology.

1.3 Core Challenges

The integration of these fields presents three core challenges in creating a cohesive and meaningful work of art. These challenges are:

- **Artistic Engagement with Sleep:** Working within an artistic framework to represent the altered state of sleep through music and sound.
- **Interdisciplinary Integration:** Drawing upon expertise from fields related to the three principal components (PCs) of the research network—music, sleep and data science—to create a coherent and meaningful work of art.
- **Communicating Subjective Experience Through Objective Means:** Sonifying objective sleep data to reflect the personal, often intangible, experience of sleep.

The following sections detail the stages of the project's development, starting with the methodology used. We then outline the exercises that helped to identify and tackle the core conceptual challenges, followed by a review of the design and ideation process, including ethical considerations. Towards the end, the planned implementation for the final installation is described.

2. METHODOLOGY: THE DOUBLE DIAMOND FRAMEWORK

To address the complexities of this project, we utilised the Double Diamond (DD) framework¹, which offers a struc-

¹Link to Double Diamond design framework: <https://www.designcouncil.org.uk/our-resources/the-double-diamond/>

tured approach to iterative design [27]. The DD framework (see Fig. 4) visualises a design process that alternates between divergent thinking—broadly exploring an issue—and convergent thinking—narrowing focus towards actionable solutions. It is divided into four distinct stages:

- **Discover:** This phase assists in understanding, rather than assuming, what the problem is. It entails engaging in discussions to understand existing perspectives within the context of the challenge.
- **Define:** This phase uses insight gained during the Discovery phase to define and re-frame the original challenge, as a clearly-stated problem.
- **Develop:** This phase encourages the team to provide diverse solutions to the problem from the Define phase, seeking inspiration from other sources and through various collaborations.
- **Deliver:** This phase entails trialling various ideas on a small scale, dismissing those that do not work and enhancing those that do, thereby reaching a final solution to the initial challenge.

3. THE INITIAL CHALLENGE

The team was initially presented with an open task: to work together in completing an artistic project, with no specific restrictions on the medium or format of the final output. This project was, however, expected to involve the aforementioned three PCs of the network and to draw from the expertise of all ten involved researchers, each of whom has a background in one or more of these components. Observing the DD framework, the first goal therefore became to define an initial challenge which incorporates all of the PCs. The team could then use this challenge as a point of divergence, gathering new knowledge to better understand the context and framework in which the work would be developed.

The first PC, music, was selected as the principal medium of artistic output. This was a straightforward choice, being itself a common form of creative expression which could draw from related domains present within the network, such as musicology and sound and music computing. While this decision was taken unanimously early on in the project, the mechanisms through which the music should be both produced and presented remained unclear. Initial discussions were therefore focused on exploring conceptual issues relating to the second PC, sleep, with the idea of tackling these through some form of musical representation. This was particularly approached through the lens of the third PC, data science; all members of the team are from analytical and/or descriptive research backgrounds, providing a motivation to incorporate data-driven science communication into the work. These discussions thereby produced a core question, which served as the initial challenge for the team: *How can we use music to express scientific knowledge regarding sleep, in a way which encourages audience reflection on the topic?*

Figure 4: An illustration of the Double Diamond framework.

4. DESIGN PROCESS

4.1 Discover: Understanding the Context of the Work

To begin addressing this question, the team was encouraged to share existing works of art (music, visual art, literature, film, ...) which relate to sleep, and to explain what the work communicates about sleep that is captivating to them. Resultant themes ranged from the individual to the collective, including the impact of sleep deprivation in modern society, representation of dream experiences, and the diversity of sleeping environments across different cultures. These ideas were compiled through open discussion, including brainstorming sessions and virtual ‘idea boards’ (e.g., Miro²) onto which researchers could contribute their thoughts collaboratively. One criterion applied when evaluating these different ideas was novelty. For example, many of the surveyed works, particularly those of the surrealists, were focused on the contents of dreams, and there was therefore a desire to avoid replicating these depictions. A decision was ultimately reached to focus the project on sleep experience at an individual level, as this would allow members of the audience to directly relate the piece to their own personal experience of sleep.

Having reached this consensus and conducted a general review of existing works on the topic, the team also explored their own instinctive notions of how different qualities of sleep could be represented. One exercise involved separately expressing verbal accounts of the sleep experience through metaphor (e.g., ‘the feeling of melting’, ‘floating on a calm river’, ‘a thick, misty atmosphere’), before reviewing the different descriptions to identify points of congruity. Fig. 5 shows a word cloud, produced from these written accounts to visualise the common themes. The use of shared online documents was a key component within such exercises, due to the remote nature of the collaboration.

The team also began relating sleep experiences specifically to music. This involved separately selecting pieces of

Figure 5: A word cloud produced from various written descriptions of sleep metaphors, using an online tool³. The size of each word is determined by the frequency of its occurrence across all descriptions.

music which represented their own sleep experience, and justifying these choices to the other researchers by delineating the musical qualities which held sleep-like connotations. Further exercises included collectively analysing existing works by contemporary composers, noting the perceived meanings and associations presented within these works. This included works such as the aforementioned Richter’s *Sleep*, which exemplified the integration of neuroscientific knowledge within a musical composition. A key takeaway from these exercises was the inherent ambiguity in representing subjective experiences of sleep – both when described verbally and when conveyed through an abstract musical domain. Rather than fighting this attribute, the team chose to embrace sleep’s lack of clear definition, using sound to express the different subjective states of consciousness that can be inferred from sleep measurements rather than explicitly communicating the objective measurements themselves to the listener.

Nevertheless, meaningful communication remained a core concern of the development process, as a purely aesthetic approach would neglect the fundamental research-

² Link to Miro: <https://miro.com/>

³ Link to word cloud tool: <https://www.jasondavies.com/wordcloud/>

based character of the project. Alongside exercises involving listening to music, the team engaged creatively with sound as a medium of expression; this was particularly motivated by the diversity of background within the network, which meant that not all researchers were familiar with musical concepts or sound production tools. The team experimented by developing ‘sound collages’, produced by digitally arranging and layering audio samples using simple software such as Audacity⁴. These were developed both individually and collaboratively within small groups. Once produced, ‘games’ were played in which other members of the team speculated on the intended meaning of the sound collages. This encouraged self-evaluation on the part of the researchers regarding the assumptions made when producing a piece of music, and led to introspection over the associated meanings that were communicated through their pieces. These reflections were furthered by exploring psychological accounts of the subjective listening experience, such as Auditory Scene Analysis [28]. This helped to decompose the approached creative works into separate perceptual streams, thereby clarifying and formalising analogies between the different layers of the respective piece and the individual concepts they represent.

4.2 Define: Establishing the Project Concept

Over the course of these exercises, two contrasting goals emerged within the project: the artistic expressivity gained through a non-explicit approach to sleep representation, combined with a desire for communicating knowledge on sleep with a basis in scientific clarity. A natural tension therefore lay between the inherently objective approach of the researchers’ own disciplines, paired with the subjective nature of the artistic task. This conflict was addressed by adopting sonification at the core of the project’s musical output. By converting objectively-measured sleep data to a musical domain, sonification serves as a natural link between all three PCs of the network (music, sleep, and data science), and allows the project to employ objective domain knowledge within an artistic framework.

While the project had now converged on sonification as a general method for producing the artistic output, the format of the presentation still had yet to be determined. Building on the chosen technique, the team now began engaging with existing sonification-based art, sharing works together and meeting with artists who had worked directly with the sonification of EEG data. EEG (and accompanying physiological measurements) was soon chosen as the data to be sonified within this project too, due to its widespread adoption within sleep science. These measurements could now be approached within the context of specific frameworks such as the Data Sonification Canvas [29], which introduced new ways of thinking about the framing and presentation of sonified data. The team was now searching for a format in which sonified EEG data could be used to address the core aim of the project: inducing a reflection of individual sleep experience within the audience.

⁴ Link to Audacity: <https://www.audacityteam.org/>

Producing a sonified output which could be related directly to the audience’s own sleep behaviour brought with it a suggestion of personalisation, something which could be achieved computationally using skills present within the network. Such an approach necessitates some form of interactivity within the system, and led the team to decide upon a live installation as the format of the work, taking inspiration from contemporary multisensory experiences such as the aforementioned *Dormitorium*. While the details of this implementation had yet to be determined, a notion emerged of having individuals’ own sleep data be measured and sonified in real-time. Thus, those participating in the work cease to be passive, impartial observers, and instead form critical components of the piece itself, forming a continuation of Lucier’s *Music for Solo Performer* which applies the expressiveness of EEG sonification to communicating subconscious mental states. The three core challenges of the project (listed in Section 1.3) now followed from this stage, becoming critical points of discussion within the team, and acted as starting points for further ideation, towards an explicit design for the installation.

By this point in the project, the team had developed a collective understanding of the context in which the piece would be implemented, and had used this knowledge to define a re-framing of the initial challenge. A new question now arose: *How can the experience of sleep be communicated from one individual to another, through real-time sonification of sleep measurements?*

4.3 Develop: Shaping the Project Through Ideation

The transition into the development stage of the DD framework marked a return to divergence. This is the current phase of the project, in which ideation sessions have up to now focused on exploring varied approaches to sonification and user interaction, specifically aiming to transform sleep into a shared experience through sound.

To ensure a comprehensive exploration process, contributors were free to focus on aspects of the project aligned with their skills and interests. All individuals could therefore participate freely across the ideation tasks, encouraging collaboration and communication within the project. A combination of tools and techniques were used to facilitate creative thinking, including further brainstorming sessions and idea boards, as well as individually producing mock-ups of the envisioned sonic and visual final outputs, which were then reviewed jointly as points of discussion. This approach was instrumental for integrating perspectives across the team’s different backgrounds, ensuring that everyone was involved in contributing to the evolving vision.

These ideation sessions have been critical in synthesising individual ideas towards a cohesive design concept. A significant outcome was the establishment of the project’s central system design: two sleepers in separate spaces, each hearing the sonification of the other’s physiological signals, while an external audience experiences a combined representation of both their data. This design encapsulates the shared experience as a dialogue between the subconscious minds of the two sleepers. Their inter-

nal states, inferred through EEG and other physiological data, are externalised as sound, creating an interaction that connects the sleep of the two individuals. The audience, observing from a central shared space, experiences a combination of both sonifications, alongside accompanying visualisations, thereby allowing them to notice points of synchronicity between the two sleepers. This installation encourages the audience to reflect on the nature of sleep, as both a personal and a collective experience.

Having established this central design, thematic meetings took place for focused discussions on components such as sound production, visual composition, and spatial design. These helped to identify common elements within the ideas of the researchers and establish a consensus on the aesthetic direction. In ideation sessions centred on sound, for example, the team would express their ideas for the musical component and share inspirational pieces. Visual inspiration also played a role in shaping the auditory aesthetic; a collage of images (see Fig. 6) showcases some of the ideas presented during a meeting on visual aesthetics, highlighting recurring motifs such as *waves* and *flow-like* elements that also subsequently informed ideas on sound design. These ideas aligned on an emphasis towards the dynamic nature of electromagnetic signals, these being measured directly from brain activity (through EEG) before being transmitted as data and sound. Additionally, the team noticed a shared vision for gradually evolving soundscapes with soft, delicate harmonies and a slow tempo, aiming to create an atmosphere that mirrors cyclic sleep patterns. These choices reflect the team's goal to balance data-driven design with an engaging, immersive experience.

Figure 6: A collage of images that were shared by members of the team during an ideation session, as inspiration pieces for visual aesthetics.

While smaller thematic meetings allowed for in-depth exploration of such ideas, larger group discussions synthesised the insights and integrated them into the overall design concept. All final creative decisions were made collaboratively, ensuring a balanced and inclusive approach. Where possible, elements from various suggestions were combined into a single concept. For example, a dome-shaped setting and the involvement of two sleepers had

initially been separate ideas, which were then brought together for the final design.

Ideas were evaluated against criteria such as feasibility, alignment with project goals, technical constraints, and potential for audience engagement. Concepts that effectively balanced artistic creativity with scientific rigour were set as a focus. However, some ideas had to be re-considered due to practical constraints. For example, the concept of a large-scale dome for visual projections was adapted to fit within a feasible space, evolving into an open, dome-shaped structure without a roof. These limitations prompted the team to re-focus on designs that could be implemented effectively given the available resources. This iterative process ensured that the final concept remained grounded in the project's core motivations, while adapting to real-world constraints.

An ethical constraint concerns the inclusion of an appropriate audience to the installation. The venue where it will be presented is open to people of all ages, and the groups of people which will attend the exhibition were therefore considered. The team discussed including minors as participants in the sleeping experience, but eventually agreed to exclude them, due to concerns regarding privacy, data protection, and informed consent, which are particularly sensitive regarding individuals under the age of 18. Moreover, for the adult participants who are included, the team decided that all collected data will be anonymised.

A crucial consideration also remained to maintain a balance between scientific or pragmatic perspectives and the more artistic aspects of the project. Much of the initial focus naturally gravitated towards practicalities, such as space configurations and data accuracy. While these considerations were important, they overshadowed deeper reflections on the aesthetic and experiential values of the installation. This imbalance prompted the need for further 'framing' sessions focused on the project's creative and artistic potential. This allowed the team to collectively re-balance the dual goals of the project: an artistic depiction of subjective sleep experience, implemented through science-based analysis of objective measurements.

To contextualise the piece to an audience unfamiliar with sleep science, the team explored ideas of framings centred around the existing design concept. For example, one focused on the interaction between the two sleepers (see Fig. 7), while other ideas included a 'sleep archive' which stores sleep experiences akin to books in a library, a dystopian narrative imagining a future without sleep, and a narrator which guides participants through the stages of sleep. One recurring notion was the previously-explored emphasis on shared experience of the subconscious, as the piece facilitates a dialogue between the subconscious minds of the two sleepers. Another common thread was audience immersion: rather than merely observing, the audience is invited into a sensory environment that evokes the experiences of sleep for them too, thereby opening a window into the interaction between the two sleepers. A central theme emerged from these ideas: communication between two subconscious minds and a conscious audience. The sonifications could here be viewed as personal,

improvised performances by the sleeping individuals, in which their subconscious minds hold an expressive influence over a creative output. This framing prompted the question “*Who are you when you are asleep?*”. The researchers reflected on the inherently personal nature of sonified sleep data, emphasising that transforming someone’s sleep into sound creates an intimate auditory narrative. This personal aspect, in combination with the public audience experience, underscored the installation’s dual focus on individual identity and shared connection.

Figure 7: Example of a framing which explores the interaction between two sleepers, created by a member of the team (Annika Partmann).

The team worked to ensure that efforts consistently aligned with the core challenges, stepping back regularly to reflect on the broader purpose of the installation. This allowed for adaptation to practical constraints while preserving the integrity of the work, ultimately laying a strong foundation for now-refined concepts to be transformed into the final implementation. Having determined the design concept, the current question now stands: *How can this design be actualised as a physical installation, while adapting to the practical constraints of the project?*

4.4 Deliver: Implementing the Final Work

We will now delineate the prototyping, testing and final implementation of the installation - tasks which are still upcoming.

4.4.1 System Design

Building upon the outcomes of the Develop phase, the planned installation will consist of a dome-shaped environment and two separate ‘pods’ - secluded, private environments which are separated from the dome, where two individuals will be invited to nap (see Fig. 8). These pods

were chosen partially for ethical reasons, considering the psychological effects that sleeping in public might have. This will ultimately also be beneficial for the installation itself, creating an environment in which participants feel comfortable and are able to fall asleep.

Participants will be provided with earbuds and a Hypnodyne ZMax⁵, a non-invasive headband for real-time sleep measurement. The ZMax measures EEG signals through two channels, as well as physiological data such as movement, respiration, and heart rate. The two participants will then enter the pods, where they are encouraged to relax and sleep for 30 minutes. Meanwhile, real-time measurements will be transmitted wirelessly from the ZMax to the custom software, which transforms their data into soundscapes. For sound generation, the team will use Pure Data (Pd) [30]⁶, an open source visual programming language often used for audio and multimedia purposes. Pd was chosen due to being modular, flexible, and accessible, thus making it particularly suitable for real-time sonification. Shared repositories, using Git version control, further facilitate the remote collaboration by hosting sleep feature extraction pipelines, written in Python. Through a combination of both Pd and Python, a dynamic mapping is applied between raw physiological measurements and the parameters of a real-time audio synthesis system. The audio system is expected to be multi-layered, including harmonising drone-like musical sounds, procedural elements which emulate natural sounds (e.g., ocean waves, rainfall), and coloured noises (e.g., pink, brown), all of which will be combined and subsequently passed through digital effects (e.g., reverb, delay). Examples of these sonic layers have already been produced during the Develop phase, via the aforementioned mock-up exercises. The overall aim is to immerse the listener in a spacious, fluid sonic environment consistent with previously-explored sleep metaphors. To emphasise the continuity of the space and avoid jarring changes which might disturb sleepers, a decision was made to exclude percussive elements, instead emphasising soft melodic components, which are gradually modulated based on the sleep data. A conscious decision was also made to avoid high frequencies, which are perceived as disturbing to sleep [31], instead focusing on sounds most prominent in the midrange.

Since participants are asked to nap for 30 minutes, they are expected to enter a state of light sleep (stages N1 and N2), characterised by alpha (8-12 Hz, indicative of relaxation) and theta (4-8 Hz, a marker of drowsiness) brain waves. Ratios between different frequency band amplitudes will be applied to gradually modulate the musical sounds, selecting harmonic intervals representative of the sleep experience. To account for noise within the measurements, highly reactive musical components will be less prevalent, and controls (e.g., low-pass filters) will be used to exclude rapidly-changing elements in the data. Simultaneously, consistent, slow sounds will be added, to allow for participant relaxation. Deeper sleep (N3) may also be reached, entailing an increased presence of slow-waves

⁵ Link to Hypnodyne: <https://hypnodynecorp.com/index.php>

⁶ Link to Pure Data: <https://puredata.info/>

Figure 8: Draft sketch, showing an idea for the floor plan of the space.

(delta frequency power, 0.5-4 Hz) characterised by a consistent oscillatory behaviour. This will also be accounted for, by embedding these oscillations directly within the sonification. The soundscapes will also be subject to high-level musical constraints, such as a shared key or tempo, which ensure the paired sleepers' outputs retain some coherence between one another regardless of the two sleep states.

Simultaneously, EEG-based visualisations which evoke the shared motif of waves will be projected in the dome-shaped space, to accompany the synchronised soundscapes. These will be created using TouchDesigner⁷, a visual programming environment widely used for interactive multimedia applications due to its modularity and real-time data capabilities. The visuals will be generated through a combination of techniques, including particle systems generally used for dynamic cloud effects, noise-based generators to create fluid textures and abstract shapes, and geometry manipulation to produce evolving, dynamic geometric forms. Additionally, the visuals will be audio-reactive, synchronising with the soundscapes to create a cohesive, immersive experience. Educational content will also be incorporated within the installation, including written content, diagrams, and graphs, for the audience to learn and reflect on the scientific foundations of sleep.

4.4.2 Prototype Development

Having planned a general system design, the next steps will focus on development of a prototype. For this, the team will start discussing more deeply how to shape the physical installation, considering six components: sound, visuals, data collection, space, content and communication, and coordination and presentation. This new phase of the project will involve two parallel workflows. On one side, the team will organise into flexible smaller groups based on domain expertise, as well as personal interest and knowledge built during previous stages of the project. On the other, time will be reserved for broader discussions involving the whole group, to reach a consensus on common

⁷ Link to TouchDesigner: <https://derivative.ca/>

aspects of the installation. This aims to simplify the approach to each facet of the installation, facilitating rapid generation of ideas and implementation of project features. The subsequent joint discussions then allow the team to re-examine these developments, expanding the perspective and exploring them in detail to reach a common ground.

4.4.3 Development Challenges

The implementation of this installation entails some practical challenges. One is that the members of the team are based in several different locations across Europe, making the need to meet to work together on system testing and practical construction before the exhibition particularly important. Another important challenge is resource constraints for the implementation. As previously mentioned, limitations in equipment, space, and budget occasionally forced the team to scale back ambitious concepts or rethink aspects of the project. Such practical restrictions may compel the team to adapt or simplify conceptual elements to align with what is realistically achievable, leading to further adaptations before the presentation. Finally, data privacy should be considered, relating to the processing of sensitive measurements (i.e., neuroimaging recordings such as EEG), which requires providing participants with the knowledge to give fully-informed consent. This includes preparing for any psychological effects that recording their data might encompass, and explaining the measurements themselves, which they may not be familiar with beforehand.

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we outlined the context for a novel interdisciplinary art project, along with the phases of divergence and convergence that led to the design of an interactive installation, which explores sleep as a shared experience through sonification. An overview was also given of the next steps to be followed for implementation of this installation. Throughout the paper, we emphasised the importance of this project's background: a collaboration between ten researchers from different disciplines, using objective measures to explore and share the subjective experience of sleep through music.

Acknowledgments

This project is the result of a collaborative effort among ten researchers, who contributed equally as part of the EU MSCA Doctoral Network 'Lullabyte'. The doctoral network is fully financed by a MSCA grant from the EU Horizon Program ('Lullabyte', grant no. 101072977).

This paper was written by (in no order): Abhishek Choubey, Samuel Morgan, Silvia Genovese, Tinke van Buijtene.

This paper was reviewed by (in no order): Ali Saberi, Anika Partmann, Bagmish Sabhapondit, Michelle George, Tristan O'Leary, Zhenxing Hu.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] C. M. Shapiro, F. Boquiren, V. Boquiren, and D. Sherman, "Sleep in art and literature," *Atlas of clinical sleep medicine*, pp. 1–10, 2009.
- [2] S. Datta and R. R. MacLean, "Neurobiological mechanisms for the regulation of mammalian sleep–wake behavior: reinterpretation of historical evidence and inclusion of contemporary cellular and molecular evidence," *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, vol. 31, no. 5, pp. 775–824, 2007.
- [3] J. Barbera, "Sleep and dreaming in greek and roman philosophy," *Sleep medicine*, vol. 9, no. 8, pp. 906–910, 2008.
- [4] M. Caraccio and M. H. Kryger, "Salvador dalí: hypnagogic hallucinations in art," *Sleep Health: Journal of the National Sleep Foundation*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 1–2, 2023.
- [5] P. Williams, *Bach: The Goldberg Variations*. Cambridge University Press, 2001.
- [6] M. Richter, "Sleep," CD, 2015.
- [7] M. Bird, M. McMahan, S. W. Rajaratnam, S. Drummond, and C. Parry, "Dormitorium," in *Matthew Bird: Dormitorium*, 2017.
- [8] "2018 sleep sounds / sydney contemporary art fair — sally anderson," <https://sallyleeanderson.net/forthcoming-sleep-sounds-2018>, (Accessed on 11/17/2024).
- [9] E. B. Issa and X. Wang, "Sensory responses during sleep in primate primary and secondary auditory cortex," *Journal of Neuroscience*, vol. 28, no. 53, pp. 14 467–14 480, 2008.
- [10] T. Andrillon and S. Kouider, "The vigilant sleeper: neural mechanisms of sensory (de) coupling during sleep," *Current Opinion in Physiology*, vol. 15, pp. 47–59, 2020.
- [11] E. Capezuti, K. Pain, E. Alamag, X. Chen, V. Philibert, and A. C. Krieger, "Systematic review: auditory stimulation and sleep," *Journal of Clinical Sleep Medicine*, vol. 18, no. 6, pp. 1697–1709, 2022.
- [12] S. Pauletto and A. Hunt, "A toolkit for interactive sonification." in *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Auditory Display (ICAD)*, Sydney, Australia, 2004.
- [13] T. Hermann, A. Hunt, J. G. Neuhoff *et al.*, *The sonification handbook*. Logos Verlag Berlin, 2011, vol. 1.
- [14] D. Worrall, "Sonification design," *Cham: Springer*, 2019.
- [15] R. McGee and D. Rogers, "Musification of seismic data," in *Proceedings of the international conference on auditory display (ICAD), Canberra, Australia*, 2016.
- [16] N. Misdariis, E. Özcan, M. Grassi, S. Pauletto, S. Barrass, R. Bresin, and P. Susini, "Sound experts' perspectives on astronomy sonification projects," *Nature Astronomy*, vol. 6, no. 11, pp. 1249–1255, 2022.
- [17] M. Quinton, I. McGregor, and D. Benyon, "Sonifying the solar system," in *Proceedings of the 22nd International Conference on Auditory Display (ICAD)*, Australian National University, Canberra, 2016.
- [18] P. Lindborg, S. Lenzi, and M. Chen, "Climate data sonification and visualization: An analysis of topics, aesthetics, and characteristics in 32 recent projects," *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 13, p. 1020102, 2023.
- [19] A. Lucier, *Music for solo performer*. Lovely Music, 1982.
- [20] V. Straebel and W. Thoben, "Alvin lucier's music for solo performer: experimental music beyond sonification," *Organised Sound*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 17–29, 2014.
- [21] D. Rosenboom, *On being invisible*. Music Gallery Editions, 1977.
- [22] G. Leslie and T. R. Mullen, "Moodmixer: Eeg-based collaborative sonification." in *Proceedings of the International Conference on New Interfaces for Musical Expression (NIME)*, Oslo, Norway, 2011, pp. 296–299.
- [23] L. Forcucci, "Music for brainwaves: Embodiment of sound, space and eeg data," *Body, Space & Technology*, vol. 17, no. 1, 2018.
- [24] A. Våljamäe, T. Steffert, S. Holland, X. Marimon, R. Benitez, S. Mealla, A. Oliveira, and S. Jordà, "A review of real-time eeg sonification research," in *Proceedings of the 19th International Conference on Auditory Display (ICAD)*, Lodz, Poland, 2013.
- [25] G. Weinberg and T. Thatcher, "Interactive sonification of neural activity," in *Proceedings of the 2006 conference on New interfaces for musical expression*, 2006, pp. 246–249.
- [26] S. Sanyal, S. Nag, A. Banerjee, R. Sengupta, and D. Ghosh, "Music of brain and music on brain: a novel eeg sonification approach," *Cognitive neurodynamics*, vol. 13, pp. 13–31, 2019.
- [27] D. Gustafsson *et al.*, "Analysing the double diamond design process through research & implementation," Master's thesis, 2019.
- [28] A. S. Bregman, *Auditory scene analysis: The perceptual organization of sound*. MIT press, 1994.
- [29] S. Lenzi and P. Ciuccarelli, "Designing tools for designers: the data sonification canvas," 2024.
- [30] M. S. Puckette, "Pure data," in *Proceedings of the International Computer Music Conference (ICMC)*, Thessaloniki, Greece, 1997.

- [31] R. J. Scarratt, O. A. Heggli, P. Vuust, and K. V. Jespersen, "The audio features of sleep music: Universal and subgroup characteristics," *PloS One*, vol. 18, no. 1, p. e0278813, 2023.

SleepSound: Charting the Nighttime Soundscape and Sleep Quality in Hong Kong through Machine Listening and AI-supported Information Design

PerMagnus Lindborg
City University of Hong Kong
pm.lindborg@cityu.edu.hk

Sara Lenzi
University of Deusto
sara.lenzi@deusto.es

Shirley Xin Li
University of Hong Kong
shirley.li@hku.hk

Xiao Li
University of Hong Kong
lixiaozq@hku.hk

ABSTRACT

Sleep is an essential part of health. One factor that affects sleep quality is soundscape, the acoustic environment as perceived. In the *SleepSound* project, we aim to collect field data and harness machine listening for an AI-supported assessment of soundscape quality for healthy sleep. Why is this important? Our initial literature review reveals that there is little known about Hong Kong's domestic acoustic environment and practically no research has been published on people's perception of their own nighttime soundscape, or how it may affect sleep. A case in point is the Noise Control Ordinance (1989), which regulates noise from e.g. construction sites but leaves much of neighbourhood environments open to interpretation. Without a deeper understanding of soundscape, solving inevitable conflicts might be left to arbitrary judgements. Given this situation, our project aims to develop methods to chart the nighttime soundscape and its impact on sleep. Restorative sleep is important for everyone and crucial for vulnerable individuals e.g. with a medical condition. The present research project builds on our recent study in a nighttime hospital ward, where patients wore sleep trackers to detect disturbances, and soundscape audio was captured. *SleepSound* will venture further by focusing on the context of domestic bedrooms for normally healthy residents in Hong Kong.

1. INTRODUCTION

SleepSound aims to investigate sleep and soundscape within domestic bedrooms in Hong Kong, to determine how sleep quality is impacted by specific sound sources. As illustrated in **Figure 1**, our approach is to collect objective data with a custom Field Kit (**Section 4**), including actigraphy sleep tracking, binaural audio recording, and data logs of ambient temperature, humidity, and lighting in two surveys ($N \approx 80$ over 3 nights; and $N \approx 24$ over 14 nights) with pre- and post-onsite interviews to grasp individual and cultural differences. We analyse multivariate time series using a pre-trained audio neural network and develop an AI-supported prediction model, with sleep tracking logs and machine listening recordings

Copyright: © 2025 Lindborg et al. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15032456>

as input for a joint assessment of soundscape and sleep quality. Finally, we outline a proof-of-concept that presents users with actionable information. Going beyond snoring detection, the app will collect individualised data, analysing all prevalent sound types that may cause annoyance and sleep disturbance in the user's environment. Field data, AI modelling, and information design generated by the project will serve research in soundscape, sleep, environmental psychology, and urban studies. It will prepare the ground for future applications in urban and interior design, nursing, and precision medicine, helping to improve quality of life.

Figure 1. Overview of *SleepSound*.

2. BACKGROUND

2.1 Sleep

Good sleep is an essential component of people's health and quality of life (Banks & Dinges 2007; Chang et al. 2020). Even occasional disturbance by noise affects performance and mood (Bonnet 1985; Schulte-Fortkamp & Fiebig 2023 Section 1.3.4). Sleep problems are a major public health concern because of the negative impacts on

physical and mental health (Ford et al. 2015) compounded with social and economic costs (Streatfeild et al. 2021). Notwithstanding, there is no broad consensus for what sleep quality really is. A meta-study evaluated research into environmental factors in the bedroom environment for healthy subjects using objective measurement methods (Xu & Lian 2022); however, other researchers emphasise that subjective factors must be included (Sancho-Domingo et al. 2021; Byusse et al. 1988, p. 194). Somewhat surprisingly, sleep quality might be unrelated to quantity (Fabbri et al. 2021) as there might be health issues associated with both too little (Grandner et al. 2010) and too much sleep (Jike et al. 2018). Humans display individual and culturally conditioned patterns of activity (circadian rhythm, chronotype; Cheung, Li, et al. 2023). Sleep disorders such as insomnia and apnea are core symptoms of many illnesses, including depression and generalised anxiety, which are associated with high economic and social cost (Streatfeild et al. 2021).

In Hong Kong, one study found that 39% of residents suffer from insomnia, with higher rates amongst women, and significant associations with joblessness and long-term illnesses (Wong & Fielding 2011). These rates are worryingly high by international comparison (Helsestart 2024). A study on circadian rhythms amongst patients in Hong Kong identified a dramatic lowering of physical activity during COVID-19 which adversely affected health and quality of life. The authors argued that strong community resilience would make these effects temporary (Lee et al. 2021), though it is unclear if this has come true.

Since sleep is a complex and important matter of everyone's life, it is to be expected that sleep research is a large and interdisciplinary field. Any single researcher or group would have to focus on one aspect, and thereby, aim to make a valuable contribution. Sleep quality is impacted by physical environment factors such as area and residential type (Lai et al. 2009), lighting, smell, and thermal comfort (Lan et al. 2017), and noise (EEA 2021; Smith et al. 2022; Xu & Lian 2022). Moreover, it is mediated by individual differences including genetic factors (Barclay et al. 2011), lifestyle, coping ability (Andringa 2010; Payne 2013), and auditory tolerance to noise (Fong et al. 2018; Lindborg & Friberg 2016). In the proposed Project we focus on *soundscape*.

2.2 Noise in Hong Kong

The quality of the acoustic environment influences our ability for core affect regulation and attention restoration (Andringa 2010) and memory reactivation and consolidation (Carbone & Diekelmann 2024). Environmental noise has a large impact on public health (EEA 2021) and in densely populated Hong Kong the situation might be dire. A noise exposure survey in 203 domestic residences found an average noise level of 63.1 dBA (To et al. 2015; we have calculated this level as the dB-averaged LAeq1h across the 20 areas in the study). As evidenced in a 2023 media report: "Noise pollution is a major problem...If it is not construction noise - rock hammers and drills - then multi-storey living brings its own cacophony of annoying sounds, including

neighbours... piano playing about five times a day... vacuuming at 1 am" (Knott 2023).

The Noise Control Ordinance (NCO 1989) covers a range of issues. Regulations for noise-sources from construction sites, percussive piling (NCO Sections 6–8/A), alarms (Section 13A/B), or transport (Section 27) detail technical measures such as acceptable noise levels (e.g LAeq) that hinge on a 'noise sensitive receiver', e.g. resident or business in the closest vicinity (Environmental Protection Agency; EPA 2024/08). Rules are stricter for nighttime noises "causing annoyance to any person...11 pm to 7 am, or on a general holiday" (NCO Section 4). By contrast, NCO is vague about annoyance caused by domestic activities in the 'general neighbourhood' (EPA 2024/03). While recognising potentially disturbing sounds, including "any musical or other instrument... loud-speaker, megaphone... amplifying sound... any game or pastime... trade or business... air-conditioning... animal or bird" (NCO Part II Section 5), specifications about limits are absent from regulatory control, because the "*nature of the noise sources [makes it] not possible to specify fixed acceptable noise levels or noise measurement procedures to be used in assessing the acceptability of the noise... noise from domestic premises and public places is to be responsively dealt with by the [local] Police on a reasonableness approach.*" (EPA 2024/08, Concise Guide, p. 2; our italics).

By contrast, we argue that recent advances in machine learning and artificial intelligence, outlined in **Section 2.4**, provide requisite tools to develop descriptors and measurement procedures that support a better assessment of soundscape quality in nighttime domestic premises. Our approach *does not replace* the 'reasonableness' that NCO requires of the Police, but *supports* it. It is a main goal with the Project to generate knowledge to enable human-centric design to promote better nighttime soundscape quality in residential areas and to bring NCO (1989) closer to international standards on noise annoyance (ISO 15666 2021).

2.3 Soundscape and health

Soundscape is "the acoustic environment as perceived or experienced and/or understood by a person or people" (ISO 12913-1 2018; Schafer 1977), embracing e.g. public outdoor spaces (Aletta & Kang 2018; Lenzi et al. 2021), indoor commercial spaces (Lindborg 2015, 2016), hospitals (Lenzi et al. 2024). See also the Frontiers Research Topic on *Human perception of environmental sound* (Aletta et al. 2022). The international standard for soundscape types (ISO 12913-2 2018) is based on concepts advanced by Schafer, Truax, Westerkamp, and others (Schafer 1977; Schulte-Fortkamp & Fiebig 2023).

While the negative impact of noise on health is well known, and noise levels have increased in hospitals over the past five decades (Busch-Vishniac & Ryherd 2019), the concept of *soundscape for health* (Lercher & Dzhambov 2023) might still raise eyebrows. Health aspects affected by environmental noise include hearing problems, stress, and cardiovascular health (Teixeira et al. 2021). In previous research, the first author of the present paper showed that levels of everyday-ish acoustic

environments significantly affect the autonomic nervous system (Lindborg 2013). Responses are specific to the environment (Lindborg 2016) because of interactions with expectation (Payne 2013) and individual differences such as personality dimensions and noise sensitivity (Lindborg & Friberg 2016; Fong et al. 2018).

Soundscape has a natural affinity with environmental psychology. Increasingly, acoustic measurements, e.g. sound pressure level (SPL, LAeq), are complemented by perceptual ratings of qualities such as pleasantness, eventfulness, calmness, and vibrancy (Axelsson et al. 2010; ISO 12913-2 2018; Aletta & Kang 2018). By default, people understand *sound as evidence of action* (Schafer 1977), which implies that a context-dependent, robust taxonomy of constituent sound sources is crucial (e.g. Lindborg 2016; Lenzi et al. 2024).

2.4 AI model design

Machine listening (Parker & Dockray 2023) is a concept developed from machine learning (artificial intelligence, deep neural networks) for speech and music applications, and more recently, also applied to soundscape. A pre-trained audio neural network (PANN; Kong et al. 2020) can detect and classify sound events when trained on specific sound types, including those found in domestic environments (Mesaros et al. 2016). Related research produced Google’s AudioSet with millions of YouTube clips classified in hundreds of sound types (Gemmeke et al. 2017). Annoyance can be predicted from individual sound sources (Mitchell et al. 2022; cf. Lindborg 2016), which via the attention mechanism in a Transformer network (Vaswani et al. 2017) yields both classification and annoyance estimation (Hou et al. 2023). Our model will explore cross-attention to achieve joint source classification and sleep disturbance prediction (Figure 2). In our approach, the propensity for differing sound sources to lead to sleep disturbance can thus be captured and modelled. Affective qualities and contextual factors contribute, via perceptual ratings of sound sources and ambient data logs, to the assessment of environmental quality. The main target is the precise identification of sounds that cause sleep disturbance, and by combining sleep data, soundscape descriptors, and individual differences, create an AI-supported model, which leads to a proof-of-concept application for Hong Kong residents (EMDesk & Futuro 2024).

2.5 Related research

Nighttime hospital soundscape. The first and second authors recently published a study on the perceived quality of a nighttime hospital soundscape (Lenzi et al. 2024), investigating the relationship between sound, annoyance, and sleep quality in a multi-patient neurology ward using a mixed-methods approach. Interviews were conducted with nurses (n = 7) to understand their experiences with sound. Questionnaires and Fitbit sleep tracking devices (n = 20) assessed patient sleep quality, and listeners (n = 28) annotated 429 nighttime audio recordings to identify over 9,200 sound events with associated annoyance. Results show that while snoring dominated the nighttime

soundscape, staff-generated sounds such as speech and footsteps contributed more to accumulated annoyance due to their extended duration. Our results suggest that patient sleep quality can be improved by focusing on design interventions that reduce the impact of specific sounds.

Urban soundscape. The first and second authors examined the soundscape of a city plaza in the Basque Country as it changed during shifting Covid-19 social restrictions (Lenzi et al. 2021). We collected daily soundscape recordings and other data over three months, and experts (n = 23) annotated sound sources and associated qualities. Descriptors (rated and computationally extracted) such as acoustic richness, loudness, and prevalence of natural, vocal, and technological sounds, gave evidence to how new social regulations obliged people to adapt and reshape their social activities, for example by reducing the use of motor vehicles and spending more time outdoors.

Figure 2. Model architecture (draft). Dual-branch convolutional neural network with cross-attention-based fusion (DCNN-CaF); after Hou et al. (2023).

3. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Our proposed research on sleep and soundscape in Hong Kong is complex in that it involves all the senses. Sleep disturbances may result from external or internal factors, or a combination. External factors are due to nature (temperature, humidity, odour), machinery and human activities (light and noise pollution), and sleeping arrangement (e.g. single/couple). Internal factors are due to individual differences: sex, age, and health condition; personality traits and sensitivity to stressors such as physical comfort, light, and noise. Time patterns might evolve in circadian (~24 h), infradian (e.g. weekday/weekend, menstrual cycle), and seasonal (yearly) cycles. Our literature review indicates that there is not enough known about the nighttime soundscape in Hong Kong, and that the Noise Control Ordinance is clearly lacking in regards to domestic environments. Soundscape research offers powerful tools for understanding the influence of environmental factors on people’s health and quality of life (Chang et al. 2020; Schulte-Fortkamp & Fiebig 2023). To research sleep and soundscape in Hong Kong, the proposed Project adopts a multimethodology, combining appropriate quantitative and qualitative

methods (Mitchell et al. 2020; Ibáñez et al. 2018; Xu & Lian 2022). We aim to answer the following questions.

- *What characterises Hong Kong's nighttime soundscape? What are the sounds and sources, and by what actions and interactions are they generated?*
- *Under which conditions and by how much do specific sound types cause annoyance and sleep disturbance for Hong Kong residents?*
- *How can we algorithmically model soundscape impact on sleep quality, considering individual differences?*
- *What is an appropriate vocabulary, in Cantonese, English, and Mandarin, to characterise soundscape and sleep quality in domestic environments in Hong Kong?*
- *What design should an application interface have to inform lay users about soundscape quality and its impact on their sleep, and empower them with actionable information?*

4. METHODS

The 'Field Kit' (**Figure 3**) will contain sensor devices for sleep tracking (actigraphy, see **Section 4.2**), audio recording (binaural), and ambient logging (digital sensors), connected to a single-board computer (Raspberry Pi) running custom software (Puredata, Python; see Pisano & Lindborg 2024 in review), and equipped with a small user interface screen for participants to retain control of data collection. We will construct and deploy eight (8x) kits in two field data collection surveys. Note that since the design implies a fairly invasive procedure, in particular audio recordings in people's bedrooms, it is crucial to resolve ethical and privacy concerns at an early stage. As for population sampling, we control for age, gender, single/couple bedroom, and type of residential area.

Figure 3. *Field Kit overview.* Digital and physical components, with cable connections to single-board microcomputer. Red = XLR audio. Blue = USB data. Dotted blue = Bluetooth.

In the First Survey, we measure sleep quality, soundscape quality, and participant profile in a larger group of participants (target is $N = 80$), over 3 consecutive nights. Participants wear sleep trackers while audio recordings are made automatically. They respond to questionnaires about sound types and soundscape quality

in each evening, and perceived sleep quality each morning. Finally, they self-report demographic and other information. In the Second Survey with Interviews, we work with a smaller number of participants ($N = 24$) volunteering from the preceding survey. In addition to actigraphy and automatic audio recordings during up to 14 nights, participants make perceptual measurements every other evening and morning, and keep a sleep diary. This will capture granular time series data for patterns of weekday/weekend and to some extent weather. The researchers will brief the participants throughout the survey to keep their motivation up. We conduct on-site semi-structured interviews before Night 1 and after Night 14 to gain in-depth understanding of issues related to their bedroom soundscape quality and sleep.

4.1 Soundscape quality

Audio recordings. Following best soundscape practices (Mitchell et al. 2020), we will make stereo audio recordings using binaural techniques to capture the bedroom's acoustic environment. Two microphones will be inserted into a *binaural dummy head* (O'Connor & Kennedy 2021; Kennedy 2020). Note that current analysis and modelling (e.g. Hou et al. 2023) typically uses mono audio; however, stereo (binaural, Ambisonics) provides richer information and flexibility (Mitchell et al. 2020).

Ambient data logging. We select digital devices for data logging of temperature, humidity, and lighting conditions in the participant's bedroom (cf. Xu & Lian 2022, Sections 3.1.4 and 3.2.4), using an open-source approach (<https://www.yoctoproject.org/>).

Acoustic and psychoacoustic descriptors. Sound pressure level and room reverberation will be measured on-site by the researchers when setting up equipment using calibrated equipment (IEC 60942: 2017; cf. Lindborg 2015). Acoustic indicators (LAeq, LCEq, and Ldos[night]) and psychoacoustic (Loudness [Nx], Sharpness, Roughness) will be extracted computationally from binaural audio recordings (ISO 12913:3 2019, Section D).

Soundscape perceptual qualities (subjective, quantitative) ratings on semantic scales of sound type and qualia such as [ISO]Pleasant, [ISO]Eventful, calm, vibrancy, and more (Axelsson et al. 2010; ISO/TS 12913-2:2018; Lindborg 2015, 2016). We will develop a field ratings protocol based on our experience and best practices (Mitchell et al. 2020), in particular employing scales to measure to what extent participants perceive that specific sound sources and events may have affected their sleep (as in Lenzi et al. 2024, Section 3.1.1). In analysis, perceptual ratings will be integrated with objective measurements from actigraphy and audio recordings (ISO 12913:3 2019).

4.2 Sleep quality

Sleep tracking (objective, quantitative). Actigraphy is a non-invasive method to monitor sleep as well as circadian patterns of rest and activity. A wrist-worn device can capture high resolution raw data and validated descriptors of sleep architecture (e.g. sleep time, efficiency, falling-asleep latency, fragmentation index). Actigraphy shows

excellent agreement with polysomnography, the ‘gold standard’ (Corlateanu et al. 2017; Xu & Lian 2022), and for field data collection has a distinct advantage in that it does not alter the individual’s usual sleep patterns (Landry et al. 2015; Chen, Li, et al. 2024). Note also that actigraphy can to some extent be made with accelerometers in smartphones (Langhom et al. 2023).

Self-report (subjective, quantitative). We are developing a protocol suitable for Hong Kong context, to include a *Sleep diary* (qualitative; see overview in Ibáñez et al. 2018, Section 2.3) and *Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index* (PSGI; Byusse et al. 1988, p. 209-) in its validated brief version (BPSQI; Sancho-Domingo et al. 2021) to assess perceived sleep quality and to help discriminate between ‘good’ and ‘poor’ sleepers.

Interviews (subjective, qualitative) are conducted pre- and post- measurements, and will be semi-structured to grasp individual perspectives, e.g. how participants experience their nighttime sleep environment, events, situations, life stories. Interviews will be conducted onsite (in their domestic premises) by a research assistant speaking Cantonese, English, or Mandarin, as appropriate.

4.3 Participant profile

Self-report (subjective, quantitative). The protocol will gather demographic information (age, sex, gender, occupation, single/couple status, residence; note that Hong Kong areas vary greatly in characteristics, which influences residents’ lifestyle and sleep habits (Nag & Pradhan 2021). Furthermore, we determine Chronotype (aka Circadian rhythm type) with the *reduced Morningness/Eveningness Questionnaire* (rMEQ; Adan & Almiral 1991; note the validated Chinese version, e.g. Cheung et al. 2023); Noise sensitivity (Weinstein’s index, in Heinonen-Gozunov’s revised version; note the related concept of noise tolerance, cf. Fong et al. 2018); and Personality traits, e.g. NEO-P-I (Costa & McCrae 1992) or Ten-Item Personality Index (Gosling et al. 1992; Lindborg & Friberg 2016; Lindborg 2013).

5. PILOT STUDY

We conducted a pilot study in Hong Kong in September-October 2024.

Participants & procedure. Online questionnaire with QuestionPro. Convenience and snowball sampling. After consenting, participants (N = 10) self-rated Circadian Type (CT; estimated with rMEQ), and Sleep Quality (SQ; BPSQI), and measured Acoustic Quality (AQ; LAeq1min, LCEq1min) in their bedroom with an iPhone app, NoiseLab-Lite.

Results. Participants: age mean 27, range 21...31 years; 8 female; all students; no hearing problem. SQ: mean 0.65, range 0.53...0.73 (scale 0...1: higher is better quality). CT: 4 morning, 6 evening. AQ: 5 low, 5 high noise level.

Analysis. We conducted linear regression with Sleep Quality as outcome. A parsimonious model (adj. $R^2 = 0.83$) was found with AQ as significant predictor ($\beta = -0.47$, $p = 0.011^*$), i.e. higher noise level was associated with lower sleep quality; and a significant interaction

between AQ and CT ($\beta = -0.81$, $p = 0.001^{**}$), i.e. for Evening types this effect was stronger.

Sound Types. The participants named 25 sounds in total, which were interpreted in four categories (ISO 13912:2018). Prevalence and mean pleasantness (scale: -2...+2) were: Traffic 28%, -0.57; Other 48%, -1.1; Humans 20%, 0.0; Nature 4%, 1.0. The most common sounds were: air conditioning (36%, -1.1), car (16%, -0.75), home appliances (12%, -1.0), traffic (12%, -0.33), and movement (12%, 0.33).

These results from a small investigation indicated a significant association between higher noise level in participants’ bedrooms and lower sleep quality, which was pronounced amongst Evening circadian types, aka ‘night owls’. Noise from air conditioning was the most commonly heard, and perceived negatively. A few sound types were positive, such as other people’s movement or actions, and nature sounds. Human and nature sound types were more often heard by Morning types, aka ‘early birds’.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The *SleepSound* project aims to contribute to public health in Hong Kong and potentially beyond by investigating how the nighttime soundscape affects sleep quality at domestic premises. Good sleep is essential to quality of life, and crucially important for vulnerable citizens e.g. with a medical condition. In this project, we harness machine listening to design an AI-supported assessment of soundscape quality for healthy sleep.

In our preliminary review of the research literature in the field, we have identified a lack of knowledge about Hong Kong’s soundscape and its impact on sleep. We must ask: *In what way, and by how much, are the specific sound sources found in local domestic acoustic environments interacting with people’s circadian rhythm and sleep quality, given individual differences such as noise tolerance and personality traits, and environmental factors such as weather?* The Noise Control Ordinance (NCO 1989; EPA 2024) regulates noise emission from various sources, such as traffic and construction piling, but leaves the judgement of nuisance in domestic and neighbourhood environments open to interpretation, stating only that it must be ‘reasonable’. By contrast, our project takes a data-driven approach that intersects urban studies, public health, and data science. We collect field data, develop a machine listening model, and outline an information design capable of producing a joint assessment of soundscape and sleep quality that pertains to the acoustic and social context.

The first goal is to collect data on sleep and soundscape in Hong Kong in two field surveys using a custom-built Field Kit. The second goal is to analyse time series data to establish associations between specific sound types and sleep disturbance answering central research questions. Thirdly, we will be preparing the next-step development of an application. Looking further ahead, the proof-of-concept and design plans for an integrated digital solution will increase the potential for collaboration with an industrial partner at a real-world, patented, commercial application. We will follow an established pathway towards commercialisation of research such as the stages

of Technological Readiness (EMDesk & Perfecto 2024). Our product would be a smartphone application with expanded sensing devices for high-quality sleep tracking and environmental logging. Smartphones can be quite powerful e.g. using movement tracking to predict sleep states in research applications such as *mindLAMP* (Langholm et al. 2023). Our approach goes further by combining actigraphy with environmental sensing, especially sound, for greater depth and precision.

There is potential to involve the general public in citizen science projects on soundscape research for better health. One large-scale application would be to develop an application for a wearable, continuous 24/7 monitoring of sound sources that have an annoying and potentially harmful impact on people in their daily life - at work, children at school, sensitive people with underlying disorders. We believe there is great interest in creating a precise, affordable, and personalised AI-supported solution to help improve soundscape and quality of life.

The ultimate goal with the *SleepSound* project is to empower general audiences by directly addressing some of the underlying physical and environmental issues that impact on health and quality of life in Hong Kong, initially in regards to sleep and the domestic soundscape. The findings and knowledge generated by the Project will inform standardisation processes and policy making in the context of updating and modernising the Noise Control Ordinance, which dates from 1989. In future research we will seek to collaborate with health services in Hong Kong for clinical studies aimed at developing novel approaches for improving the soundscape in hospitals, continuing our research on the nighttime soundscape in convalescence wards (Lenzi et al. 2024). Clinical studies must take into account the interoperability of complex systems, security of patients, confidentiality of data, and standardisation to enable upscaling. Our research will help address the high rates of insomnia in Hong Kong, which may affect other places where people sleep in the same room or unit, such as school/company residency, nursing homes, and Hong Kong's 'subdivided rental units'.

In conclusion, we expect the *SleepSound* project to make significant contributions to understanding soundscape for healthy sleep. Our research will reach well beyond academia to feed public interest in understanding how soundscape affects their sleep; propose ways to mitigate against noise; help resolve noise-related neighbourhood grievances; support future policy development; and create an AI-supported assessment of sleep and environmental quality preparing for a 'SleepSound app'.

The field data collection, and deep analysis of the relationships between soundscape, acoustic and environmental descriptors, and sleep quality in a sample of the population, will provide knowledge for researchers in urban studies, sleep medicine, perception psychology, social sciences, and policy. It will prepare the ground for future applications in urban and interior design, nursing, and personal health. The goal is to help improve quality of life in Hong Kong, and beyond.

Acknowledgments

This text is part of a project grant application submitted in November 2024 to the General Research Fund of Hong Kong SAR, China. Follow us for updates on <https://soundlab.scm.cityu.edu.hk/sleepsound/>.

7. REFERENCES

- [1] A. Adan A, Almirall H. Horne & Östberg morningness-eveningness questionnaire: A reduced scale. *Personality and Individual Differences*. 1991 Jan 1;12(3):241–53.
- [2] Aletta F, De Coensel B, Lindborg P. Human perception of environmental sounds. Research Topic in *Frontiers in Psychology*. 2021;12:714591.
- [3] Aletta F, Kang J. Towards an urban vibrancy model: A soundscape approach. *International journal of environmental research and public health*. 2018;15(8):1712.
- [4] Andringa TC. Soundscape and core affect regulation. *Proc InterSpeech* 2010.
- [5] Axelsson Ö, Nilsson ME, Berglund B. A principal components model of soundscape perception. *JASA*. 2010;128(5):2836–46.
- [6] Banks S, Dinges DF. Behavioral and Physiological Consequences of Sleep Restriction. *Journal of Clinical Sleep Medicine*. 2007 Aug 15;03(05):519–28.
- [7] Barclay NL, Eley TC, Maughan B, Rowe R, Gregory AM. Associations between diurnal preference, sleep quality and externalizing behaviours: a behavioural genetic analysis. *Psychol Medicine*. 2011 41(5):1029–40.
- [8] Bonnet MH. Effect of sleep disruption on sleep, performance, and mood. *Sleep*. 1985;8(1).
- [9] Busch-Vishniac I, Ryherd E. Hospital soundscapes: Characterization, impacts, and interventions. *Acoustics Today*. 2019;15(3):11.
- [10] Buysse DJ, Reynolds CF, Monk TH, Berman SR, Kupfer DJ. The Pittsburgh sleep quality index: A new instrument for psychiatric practice and research. *Psychiatry Res*. 1988 12;28(2).
- [11] Carbone J, Diekelmann S. An update on recent advances in targeted memory reactivation during sleep. *Sci Learn*. 2024 Apr 15;9(1):1–10.
- [12] Chang KKP, Wong FKY, Chan KL, Wong F, Ho HC, Wong MS, et al. The Impact of the Environment on the Quality of Life and the Mediating Effects of Sleep and Stress. *Intl J Envir Res and Public Health*. 2020 17(22):8529.
- [13] Chen J, Chan NY, Li CT, Chan JWY, Liu Y, Li SX, et al. Multimodal digital assessment of depression with actigraphy and app in Hong Kong Chinese. *Transl Psychiatry*. 2024 18;14(1).

- [14] Cheung FTW, Li X, Hui TK, Chan NY, Chan JWY, Wing YK, et al. Circadian preference and mental health outcomes in youth: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Sleep Med Rev.* 2023 1;72:101851.
- [15] Corlățeanu A, Covantev S, Botnaru V, Sircu V, Nenna R. To sleep, or not to sleep – that is the question, for polysomnography. *Breathe.* 2017 Jun 1;13(2):137–40.
- [16] Costa PT, McCrae RR. Normal personality assessment in clinical practice: The NEO Personality Inventory. *Psychological Assessment.* 1992;4(1):5–13.
- [17] EEA. European Environment Agency: Exposure of Europe’s population to environmental noise. Dec. 2021.
- [18] EPA. Environmental Protection Agency of Hong Kong: Neighbourhood Noise; and Guidelines & References 2024.
- [19] Fabbri M, Beracci A, Martoni M, Meneo D, Tonetti L, Natale V. Measuring Subjective Sleep Quality: A Review. *Intl J Envir Research and Public Health.* 2021 18(3):1082.
- [20] Fong DYT, Wong JYH, Huang L. Effect of noise tolerance on non-restorative sleep: a population-based study in Hong Kong. *BMJ Open.* 2018 Mar 1;8(3):e020518.
- [21] Ford ES, Cunningham TJ, Croft JB. Trends in Self-Reported Sleep Duration among US Adults from 1985 to 2012. *Sleep.* 2015 May 1;38(5):829–32.
- [22] Gemmeke JF, Ellis DPW, Freedman D, Jansen A, Lawrence W, Moore RC, et al. Audio Set: An ontology and human-labeled dataset for audio events. *Proc IEEE ICASSP* 2017.
- [23] Gosling SD, Rentfrow PJ, Swann Jr WB. A very brief measure of the Big-Five personality domains. *J Research in personality.* 2003;37(6):504–28.
- [24] Grandner MA, Patel NP, Gehrman PR, Perlis ML, Pack AI. Problems associated with short sleep: Bridging the gap between laboratory and epidemiological studies. *Sleep Med Rev.* 2010 1;14(4).
- [25] Helsestart. Global Insomnia Statistics in 2022 & 2024. *Helsestart.no*, 2024.
- [26] Hou Y, Ren Q, Zhang H, Mitchell A, Aletta F, Kang J, et al. AI-based soundscape analysis: Jointly identifying sound sources and predicting annoyance. *JASA* 2023 15;154(5):3145–57.
- [27] Ibáñez V, Silva J, Cauli O. A survey on sleep questionnaires and diaries. *Sleep Medicine.* 2018 Feb 1;42:90–6.
- [28] IEC 60942: 2017 Electroacoustics—Sound Calibrators. Geneva, Switzerland; 2017.
- [29] ISO 12913-1: 2014 Acoustics—Soundscape—Part 1: Definition and Conceptual Framework. International Organization for Standardization: Geneva, Switzerland; 2014.
- [30] ISO 12913-2: 2018 Acoustics—Soundscape—Part 2: Data collection & reporting requirements.
- [31] ISO 12913-3: 2019 Acoustics—Soundscape—Part 3: Data analysis.
- [32] ISO 15666: 2021 Acoustics — Assessment of noise annoyance by means of social and socio-acoustic surveys. 2021
- [33] Jike M, Itani O, Watanabe N, Buysse DJ, Kaneita Y. Long sleep duration and health outcomes: Systematic review, meta-analysis and meta-regression. *Sleep Med Rev.* 2018 1;39.
- [34] Kennedy J. [TCD_FVA]. OpenAural. <https://www.thingiverse.com/thing:4691843>
- [35] Knott K. Noise annoys: Hongkongers driven to distraction by daily din which experts say is making the city sick. *South China Morning Post* 2023 Mar 5.
- [36] Kong Q, Cao Y, Iqbal T, Wang Y, Wang W, Plumbley MD. PANNs: Large-Scale Pretrained Audio Neural Networks for Audio Pattern Recognition. *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing.* 2020;28:2880–94.
- [37] Lai ACK, Mui KW, Wong LT, Law LY. An evaluation model for indoor environmental quality (IEQ) acceptance in residential buildings. *Energy & Buildings* 2009 1;41(9):930–6.
- [38] Lan L, Tsuzuki K, Liu YF, Lian ZW. Thermal environment and sleep quality: A review. *Energy and Buildings.* 2017 Aug 15;149:101–13.
- [39] Landry GJ, Best JR, Liu-Ambrose T. Measuring sleep quality in older adults: a comparison using subjective and objective methods. *Front Aging Neurosci.* 2015 Sep 7
- [40] Langholm C, Byun AJS, Mullington J, Torous J. Monitoring sleep using smartphone data in a population of college students. *npj Mental Health Res.* 2023 Mar 17;2(1):1–6.
- [41] Lee PMY, Huang B, Liao G, Chan CK, Tai L bun, Tsang CYJ, et al. Changes in physical activity and rest-activity circadian rhythm among Hong Kong community aged population before and during COVID-19. *BMC Public Health.* 2021 1;21(1):836.
- [42] Lenzi S, Lindborg P, Spagnol S, Kamphuis D, Özcan E. Perceived quality of a nighttime hospital soundscape. *Noise Mapping* 2024 1;11(1).
- [43] Lenzi S, Sádaba J, Lindborg P. Soundscape in Times of Change: Case Study of a City Neighbourhood During the COVID-19 Lockdown. *Frontiers psychol.* 2021 12(412).
- [44] Lercher P, Dzhambov AM. Soundscape and Health. In Schulte-Fortkamp et al. eds. *Soundscapes:*

Humans and Their Acoustic Environment. Springer Intl Publishing 2023.

- [45] Lindborg P. Physiological measures regress onto acoustic and perceptual features of soundscapes. *Proc ICME3*, University of Jyväskylä, Finland 2013.
- [46] Lindborg P. Psychoacoustic, physical, and perceptual features of restaurants: A field survey in Singapore. *Applied acoustics*. 2015;92:47–60.
- [47] Lindborg P. A taxonomy of sound sources in restaurants. *Applied acoustics*. 2016;110.
- [48] Lindborg P. Which Timbral Features Granger-Cause Colour Associations to Music? *Proc Intl Conf Timbre*, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece; 2020. p. 75–8.
- [49] Lindborg P, Caiola V, Chen M, Ciuccarelli P, Lenzi S. Re(de)fining Sonification: Project Classification Strategies in the Data Sonification Archive. *J Audio Eng Soc* 2024;72.
- [50] Lindborg P, Friberg A. Personality traits bias the perceived quality of sonic environments. *Applied Sciences*. 2016;6(12):405.
- [51] Lindborg P, Lenzi S, Chen M. Climate data sonification and visualization: An analysis of topics, aesthetics, and characteristics in 32 recent projects. *Frontiers Psych* 2023;13:1020102.
- [52] Mesaros A, Heittola T, Virtanen T. TUT database for acoustic scene classification and sound event detection. In: *2016 24th European Signal Processing Conference (EUSIPCO)*. 2016
- [53] Mitchell A, Erfanian M, Soelistyo C, Oberman T, Kang J, Aldridge R, et al. Effects of Soundscape Complexity on Urban Noise Annoyance Ratings: A Large-Scale Online Listening Experiment. *Intl J Envir Research and Public Health*. 2022 Jan;19(22):14872.
- [54] Mitchell A, Oberman T, Aletta F, Erfanian M, Kachlicka M, Lionello M, et al. The Soundscape Indices (SSID) Protocol: A Method for Urban Soundscape Surveys. *Applied Sciences*. 2020 10(7):2397.
- [55] Mitchell A, Oberman T, Aletta F, Kachlicka M, Lionello M, Erfanian M, et al. Investigating urban soundscapes of the COVID-19 lockdown: A predictive soundscape modeling approach. *JASA* 2021 150(6):4474–88.
- [56] Nag C, Pradhan RK. Impact of lifestyle on circadian orientation and sleep behaviour. *Sleep and Biological Rhythms*. 2012 10:94–9.
- [57] NCO. Cap. 400 Noise Control Ordinance. Hong Kong Legislation 1989.
- [58] O'Connor D, Kennedy J. An evaluation of 3D printing for the manufacture of a binaural recording device. *Applied Acoustics*. 2021 1;171:107610.
- [59] Parker JEK, Dockray S. 'All possible sounds': speech, music, and the emergence of machine listening. *Sound Studies*. 2023 3;9(2):253–81.
- [60] Payne SR. The production of a perceived restorativeness soundscape scale. *Applied acoustics*. 2013;74(2):255–63.
- [61] Pisano G, Lindborg PM. Developing the Open Ambisonics Toolkit: Background, Design, Evaluation. 2024 in review.
- [62] Sancho-Domingo C, Carballo JL, Coloma-Carmona A, Buysse DJ. Brief version of the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (B-PSQI) and measurement invariance across gender and age in a population-based sample. *Psychol assessment*. 2021 33(2):111.
- [63] Schafer RM. *The soundscape: our sonic environment & tuning of the world*. Destiny 1977.
- [64] Schulte-Fortkamp B, Fiebig A. Soundscape: The Development of a New Discipline. In *Soundscapes: Humans and Their Acoustic Environment*. Springer Intl Publishing 2023.
- [65] Smith MG, Cordoza M, Basner M. Environmental Noise and Effects on Sleep: An Update to the WHO Systematic Review. *Envir Health Persp* 2022 130(7):076001.
- [66] Streatfeild J, Smith J, Mansfield D, Pezzullo L, Hillman D. The social and economic cost of sleep disorders. *Sleep*. 2021 Nov 1;44(11):zsab132.
- [67] Teixeira LR, Pega F, Dzhambov AM, Bortkiewicz A, da Silva DTC, de Andrade CAF, et al. The effect of occupational exposure to noise on ischaemic heart disease, stroke and hypertension. *Envir Intl*. 2021 1;154:106387.
- [68] To WM, Mak CM, Chung WL. Are the noise levels acceptable in a built environment like Hong Kong? *Noise & Health*. 2015 Dec;17(79):429.
- [69] Vaswani A, Shazeer, Parmar, Uszkoreit, Llion, Gomez, et al. Attention is all you need. In: *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 2017.
- [70] Wesselius HM, Van Den Ende ES, Almsa J, Ter Maaten JC, Schuit SC, Stassen PM, et al. Quality and quantity of sleep and factors associated with sleep disturbance in hospitalized patients. *JAMA internal medicine*. 2018;178(9):1201–8.
- [71] Wong WS, Fielding R. Prevalence of insomnia among Chinese adults in Hong Kong: a population-based study. *J Sleep Research*. 2011;20(1pt1):117–26.
- [72] Xu X, Lian Z. Objective sleep assessments for healthy people in environmental research: A literature review. *Indoor Air*. 2022 May;32(5):e13034.

Semantic and Spatial Sound-Object Recognition for Assistive Navigation

Daniel Gea

Faculty of Engineering, University of Porto
dngiap@gmail.com

Gilberto Bernardes

INESC TEC, Faculty of Engineering,
University of Porto
gba@fe.up.pt

ABSTRACT

Building on theories of human sound perception and spatial cognition, this paper introduces a sonification method that facilitates navigation by auditory cues. These cues help users recognize objects and key urban architectural elements, encoding their semantic and spatial properties using non-speech audio signals. The study reviews advances in object detection and sonification methodologies, proposing a novel approach that maps semantic properties (i.e., material, width, interaction level) to timbre, pitch, and gain modulation and spatial properties (i.e., distance, position, elevation) to gain, panning, and melodic sequences. We adopt a three-phase methodology to validate our method. First, we selected sounds to represent the object's materials based on the acoustic properties of crowdsourced annotated samples. Second, we conducted an online perceptual experiment to evaluate intuitive mappings between sounds and object semantic attributes. Finally, in-person navigation experiments were conducted in virtual reality to assess semantic and spatial recognition. The results demonstrate a notable perceptual differentiation between materials, with a global accuracy of $.69 \pm .13$ and a mean navigation accuracy of $.73 \pm .16$, highlighting the method's effectiveness. Furthermore, the results suggest a need for improved associations between sounds and objects and reveal demographic factors that are influential in the perception of sounds.

1. INTRODUCTION

In a world where sight is often prioritized, blind and visually impaired (BVI) individuals face significant challenges in semantic and spatial navigation. When a sighted person encounters an obstacle, they intuitively navigate around it. For BVI individuals using a sound-based system, a simple beep lacks the detail needed for intuitive navigation. Using the same beep for all obstacles creates ambiguity, as different objects require different responses. Although vision allows us to form a mental map of our surroundings, a binary sound system limits spatial awareness, making navigation in unfamiliar spaces challenging for blind individuals [1].

In this context, assistive technology for BVI individuals calls for two levels of recognition: semantic and spatial.

Semantic navigation consists of recognizing the attributes and functions of objects, allowing us to distinguish between *obstacles* to be circumvented and *delimiters*, i.e., fixed boundaries that define the limits of accessible areas. Spatial navigation involves understanding physical layouts, i.e., identifying the distances, positions, and elevations of objects.

In recent decades, obstacle detection systems have increasingly relied on computer vision, utilizing cameras and algorithms to identify obstacles for users [2]. While ultrasonic and laser detection are traditionally more accurate, camera-based methods are becoming popular due to their accessibility on devices like smartphones and wearable glasses. These systems detect obstacles and identify features like color and texture, enhancing usability. However, computer vision systems face limitations in real-world conditions, such as low lighting, adverse weather, and visual obstructions, along with current technological constraints.

This study proposes a sonification method, i.e., the process of converting data into non-speech audio signals [3], to translate semantic and spatial object-related information into non-speech audio cues, enhancing the BVI individuals' understanding of their surroundings. In the context of this study, sonification translates spatial and semantic information about objects into sound cues that can assist users in navigating. Semantic information helps distinguish elements like pavements, traffic lights, and doors, while spatial information conveys objects' left or right position, distance, and elevation.

The novelty of the proposed method lies in sonification mappings that convey semantic (object function, width, and interaction) and spatial (distance, position, elevation) properties designed explicitly for BVI navigation. The proposed mappings are tested in perceptual and navigation experiments to evaluate their effectiveness.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews audio-driven semantic and spatial navigation strategies. Section 3 details the proposed sonification method, namely the mappings between objects and their timbral qualities and the interactions between users and objects with sound transformations. Sections 4 and 5 present the evaluation and results of the sonification method. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper by highlighting its main contributions and directions for future work.

Copyright: © 2025 Daniel Gea et al. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15032513>

2. RELATED WORK

Auditory display methods attempt to map data to sound for intuitive understanding, addressing challenges such as cognitive load and auditory fatigue. These approaches prioritize user-friendly designs that balance clarity, aesthetics, and functionality, especially for visually impaired users [4].

Auditory displays include sonification, auditory icons, and musification methods, which have been instrumental in conveying data to users, especially those with visual impairments [5]. These auditory approaches lie on a symbolic-analogic continuum, where symbolic sounds like earcons serve as basic notifications. In contrast, more analogic displays such as auditory icons reflect event-specific details, enhancing user interaction with relevant context [6–8].

Sonification techniques in outdoor navigation experiments enable users to interpret information despite background noise, reducing cognitive load and overcoming language barriers [9]. This technique employs auditory attributes such as pitch, timbre, amplitude, and spatiality to establish intuitive connections between data characteristics and sound, fostering greater understanding and situational awareness.

Auditory icons and earcons serve as distinct event indicators. While auditory icons leverage intuitive associations—like glass breaking to signal an error—earcons require a learned association between abstract tones and data elements [5]. Morphocons presents another innovative auditory display technique. Unlike earcons, which associate fixed sounds with specific meanings, morphocons create a dynamic sonic grammar by modifying parameters such as rhythm and frequency. This approach allows for adaptable sounds that convey abstract information, making them accessible to both blind and sighted users [10].

For Presti et al. [11], musification extends beyond basic sonification by incorporating tonality, modal scales, and higher-level musical features (i.e., polyphony, tonal modulation). Other techniques for sonification include integrating both speech and non-speech cues, these systems can convey layered information through metaphors of shared human experiences, reducing cognitive load and enhancing accessibility in complex environments [12].

In sound-assisted navigation, auditory dimension mappings make spatial data interpretable. For example, properties like distance are mapped through repetitive increasing or decreasing sound frequencies—continuous values—while others, such as position and object width, are mapped to more straightforward binary categories—discrete values—to avoid information overload [13].

Research emphasizes the importance of auditory aesthetics when designing auditory icons and earcons for users, noting preferences for lower frequencies and reduced loudness to avoid user discomfort, particularly with high frequencies that many find unpleasant [14]. In sound-guided navigation experiments [13], the authors demonstrated that users' emotional responses to sounds significantly impact task performance and engagement, highlighting the im-

portance of sonification designs that balance clarity, confidence, and pleasantness [15].

Despite significant advances in auditory display and sonification technologies, several limitations remain. Most existing methods rely on symbolic or abstract earcons, thus requiring users to learn associations between sounds and events, potentially increasing cognitive load and limiting usability. Furthermore, while auditory icons can more intuitively represent events, they can be confused with environmental sounds, background noise, or a lack of universally intuitive mappings. Current sonification approaches also struggle to balance the amount of information conveyed without overwhelming users, often requiring careful calibration of auditory dimensions such as pitch, volume, and spatialization to avoid user fatigue or sensory overload. High-frequency sounds and specific auditory mappings can be unpleasant or counterproductive for users, limiting the overall user experience and accessibility, particularly for individuals with sensory sensitivities.

3. SONIFICATION METHOD

Based on principles of spatial cognition and sound perception, this section presents a sonification method to assist people from the BVI in navigating outdoor and indoor environments. It aims to transform critical spatial and semantic information about obstacles into non-speech sounds, enabling users to perceive their surroundings through sounds.

In detail, the method tackles four primary challenges faced by BVI individuals. First, it recognizes the position and distance of objects in the surroundings at any height. Second, distinguish between obstacles (i.e., trash bins, chairs, doors, poles, etc.) and objects delimiting areas of navigation (i.e., walls, curbs, stairs, etc.). Third, understanding spatial layouts by recognizing specific objects to navigate unfamiliar environments, such as an outdoor street with a conventional road and a small square or an indoor office workplace. Fourth, preserving auditory surrounding awareness while enhancing spatial and semantic understanding of the surroundings.

These challenges are addressed by the sonification of *semantic* and *spatial* properties of surrounding objects. Semantic properties characterize the nature and function of objects within the environment and the user. The term *obstacles* refers to objects that can be navigated around, such as poles or benches. The term *delimiters* describes objects that define boundaries, such as walls or curbs, indicating the end of a path. *Width* indicates an object's width or size. And *interaction* refers to an object's affordance level for BVI users, emphasizing those objects that users may find relevant and wish to interact with (i.e., doors, chairs, traffic lights, etc.). The mappings of semantic attributes to sound are detailed in Section 3.1.

Spatial properties encompass attributes related to the physical space and positioning of objects. These include 1) the *distance* to an object from the user location, 2) the *position* to the object's lateral placement relative to the user's path, and 3) the object's *elevation* to the ground level (i.e., the elevation of steps, curbs, or stairs). The mappings of

spatial attributes to sound are detailed in Section 3.2.

The selection of objects for indoor and outdoor environments is shown in Table 1 and was informed by frequent appearances in extensive reviews of photographs of the streets and offices. In addition, some references were drawn from previous studies with similar experimental setups [1].

List of Objects for Experiments		
Benches	Bin trashes	Bollards
Bushes	Chairs	Columns
Constructions	Crosswalk	Curbs
Doors	Elevators	Fences
Fountains	Mailboxes	Potholes
Ramps	Roads	Single-steps
Stairs	Statues	Street lights
Tables	Traffic light	Trees
Vases	Walls	Windows

Table 1. List of objects adopted in our experimental sonification method.

3.1 Semantic properties

The sonification of semantic properties of objects included the following four primary elements: obstacles, delimiters, width, and interaction. Obstacles identification is represented by the timbre and amplitude envelope of their sonic material characteristics—such as brick, glass, metal, and wood, the most common construction materials in cities and interior spaces. Delimiters are represented by a simple sinewave within the 100-140 Hz range to contrast with the complex sounds of obstacles. These uncircumventable boundaries, like walls or construction barriers, define indoor and outdoor layouts.

The width of the obstacle is mapped to the pitch of its sound. We adopted discrete pitch values instead of a continuous scale to simplify the implementation of the method. We defined three categories of width: narrow, medium, and wide. The medium width serves as the baseline, with pitches adjusted one octave higher for narrow obstacles (multiplying the baseline frequency by 2) and one octave lower for wide obstacles (dividing the baseline frequency by 2).

Interaction is indicated by gain modulation and categorized into three levels: high, low, and none. Objects with high interaction (i.e., doors, traffic lights, crosswalks) are beneficial, while those with low interaction (i.e., benches, trash cans, mailboxes) have moderate utility. Objects without interaction (i.e., walls, trees, flowerpots) offer no practical affordance during navigation. Interaction is conveyed through discrete modulation of sound gain, implemented using additive synthesis with sinewave oscillators. The sound undergoes a modulation rate of 5 Hz for high-interaction objects and, for low-interaction objects, a modulation rate of 1 Hz. This modulation is applied through audio processing software, where the gain is modulated by altering the amplitude of the base sound.

We sonify objects in terms of timbre and amplitude envelope following a methodology proposed in [16] to iden-

Figure 1. UMAP visualization of the content-based audio description space of obstacles’ materials for the semantic labels wood, metal, glass, and brick.

tify acoustic attributes that best differentiate semantic labels of non-auditory cues, aiming to adopt the most intuitive sounds for a given material. Departing from semantic queries of the four most common object’s materials, wood, metal, glass, and brick, a collection of 15 sound samples per semantic label retrieved from the crowd-sourced platform Freesound.¹ A mathematical space of acoustic content-based descriptors, such as spectral brightness, roughness, and MFCCs, covers temporal, spectral, rhythmic, and tonal descriptions. From the resulting (multi-dimensional) space of about 50 features, a two-dimensional uniform manifold approximation and projection (UMAP) is created, as shown in Figure 1. After removing the outliers and attentively listening to the sounds at the center of each material’s clusters, we selected representative sounds.

3.2 Spatial properties

The work of Presti et al. [11] inspires the spatial mappings adopted, who establish correlations between object properties and specific sound dimensions, organized to be meaningfully interpreted by the auditory sense [18].

The sonification of spatial properties of objects features the following three elements: distance, position, and elevation. Distance from the object is mapped to the gain, with closer objects having higher gain values and further objects having lower gain values. The distance range considered is from 4 meters (-20 dB) to 40 cm (0 dB). The gain adjustment follows a logarithmic relationship, using continuous values between these two points, with the sound intensity gradually increasing as the object approaches the user.

The position provides an indicator of the laterality of the object from the user and is mapped to the sound panning. When an object is directly ahead, the sound is equally panned to the left and right channels. As the object moves to the left or right, the panning adjusts accordingly, making the sound more pronounced in the corresponding channel.

¹ <https://freesound.org/> (accessed on November 13, 2024) is a repository of sounds where users upload labeled sounds by their semantic attributes. The platform allows for textual queries and outputs a list of audio samples ranked by the proximity to the query. Furthermore, each sample is annotated with features based on acoustical content computed by the Essentia library [17].

The detection range is based on the average shoulder width of a person (approximately 40 cm) plus an additional 20 cm, resulting in a detection field of about 60 cm. If no object is detected, no sound is played. The panning effect is achieved by linear interpolation between the left and right channels.

Elevation indicates changes in the ground level (i.e., steps, stairs, or ramps) through melodic tone sequences. Two tones are played consecutively for a single step or a ramp: the first tone represents the lower octave, and the second represents the higher octave. When the elevation increases—stepping from the road to the pavement—the sequence ascends, and vice versa when descending. For stairs, a sequence of four tones progresses by one octave each. All tones last one-quarter note (at ≈ 70 BPM), except for the last tone, which is held slightly longer (whole-note) to help users identify the start and end of the sequence and other modified properties.

One of the main intentions for these properties is to mimic the physical behavior of any sound source, which has been the study of psychoacoustics and simulated in multiple virtual environments to convey more realistic sound scenes.²

4. EVALUATION

The evaluation of our method is twofold. 1) A perceptual listening experiment assessing the intuitive association between the *semantic* properties of objects to the sound mapping designed and detailed in Section 3.1. 2) An in-person navigation experiment to assess the joint *semantic* and *spatial* navigation abilities in both blind and sighted participants within a 3D virtual reality (VR) environment. Additionally, 3) the data collection process for both experiments and 4) the methods used for data analysis are described.

4.1 Perceptual Listening Test

A listening test was conducted to validate the mappings developed in the sonification method by examining how well participants can *intuitively* interpret the semantic information conveyed, namely the *obstacles*' material identification, as well as their *width* and degrees of *interaction*.

4.1.1 Test Structure

The listening test was implemented using LimeSurvey³ and comprised three groups of questions, each with four questions, totaling 12 questions per participant. The test was preceded by a demographic section that collected information on age, nationality, vision type, and musical knowledge. Each group evaluated a specific relationship between sound and semantic properties, with responses recorded in a confusion matrix format [19]. The question groups are as follows:

- *Obstacles material-timbre*: each question presented one audio clip with five possible answer options: A)

²The repository containing the tested sounds is available on GitHub (<https://github.com/dngea/Semantic-and-Spatial-Sound-Object-Recognition-for-Assistive-Navigation>).

³<https://www.limesurvey.org/> (Last accessed April 23, 2024).

Brick, B) Glass, C) Metal, D) Wood, or E) None of the above.

- *Width-pitch*: each of the four questions was a question structured like a matrix response and included three audio clips (same material, varying pitch), with three answer options for each sound: A) Narrow, B) Medium, or C) Wide.
- *Interaction-modulation*: each of the four questions was a question structured like a matrix response and included three audio clips (same material, varying modulation levels), with three response options for each sound: A) No interaction, B) Medium interaction, or C) High interaction.

Participants were instructed to rely solely on judgment, with no prior knowledge of the mappings, as there were no correct answers. Questions within each group were randomized to minimize order bias. Only semantic properties were tested, as spatial properties are more useful for locating objects than recognizing them. Additionally, adding more questions could increase complexity and cause participants to discontinue the test.

4.1.2 Participants

The listening test was primarily distributed through mailing lists within the University of Porto, online academic communities, via the Association for Visually Impaired Individuals in Portugal⁴, and international research communities focused on music and sound⁵. In total, 50 participants completed the entire survey, resulting in a total of 600 trials conducted. Participants ranged in age, with a slightly higher concentration in the 45–54 age group. Fourteen reported being “blind or low vision,” while the remaining 36 reported being “sighted”. Regarding musical knowledge, 26 participants claimed to have either “Strong or basic knowledge”, while 29 stated having “No experience.” Most participants were from “Spain” (23) and “Portugal” (19).

4.2 In-person Navigation in Virtual Reality

This experiment evaluated spatial navigation in blind and sighted participants within a 3D VR environment, providing users with both semantic and spatial object properties. Participants were tasked with navigating two simulated scenarios. Both semantic and spatial properties were assessed, thus adopting the totality of the proposed sonification method detailed in Section 3.

4.2.1 Experimental Set Up

We have adopted Unity⁶ to create a VR simulation of the two indoor and outdoor scenarios under evaluation, where common tasks can be tested, such as crossing a street or walking through an office. The virtual environment was

⁴ACAPO <https://www.acapo.pt/> (Last accessed November 24, 2024).

⁵NIME <https://www.nime.org/>, ISMIR <https://ismir.net/> (Last accessed April 20, 2024).

⁶Unity Technologies, <https://unity.com> (Last accessed November 24, 2024).

chosen to avoid the complexity of integrating sonification with AI-based object recognition, focusing solely on sonifying objects rather than developing detection algorithms.

The experimental framework builds on prior research, which utilized audio cues in a virtual maze [20], and investigations into mental mapping for spatial navigation [21]. Participants used an external controller—specifically, a smartphone equipped with a gyroscope—to simulate forward movement and lateral rotation. Forward movement was activated by pressing a button, with a footstep audio cue indicating a walking speed of 1.20 m/s. As participants navigated, objects emit sounds through headphones, requiring them to adjust their paths based on auditory cues, while the absence of sound indicated a clear trajectory. Visual input was entirely omitted to simulate a blind navigation experience. An examiner supervised the experiment, monitoring participants’ locations and interactions within the virtual environment.

4.2.2 Experiment Dynamics and Tasks

Participants received a briefing on the study’s objectives and procedures, followed by the experiment, with a total duration of approximately 45 minutes. During this training session, they were introduced to the objects listed in Table 1 and their corresponding sounds. They familiarised themselves with the movement controls, identical to those used in the experiment maps. The experiment was structured as follows: it began with the outdoor map, where participants were given a raised relief map—which represented the layout of the 3D scenario built in Unity, as shown in Figure 2—to help them navigate. They were informed that the objects in this space were the same as those encountered during training. Participants were instructed to move from point A (marked by a raised dot) to location B, which remained consistent across all experiments and represented a reasonable endpoint within the map, offering a trajectory with moderate challenges and objects. Employing a think-aloud methodology, participants were required to identify the semantic and spatial properties of each sound they heard before attempting to guess the corresponding object. After approximately 5 minutes of navigation, they were asked to position themselves on the relief map or inform the examiner when they believed they had reached location B. This same methodology was applied during the indoor map navigation. Therefore, the experiment consisted of three primary tasks:

1. **Recognition of Sound Cues:** Participants identify sound cues, associating them with semantic (obstacles, delimiters, width, interaction) and spatial (distance, position, elevation) properties.
2. **Object Recognition:** Participants apply deductive reasoning in a think-aloud format to identify objects based on sound cues. This process encourages participants to articulate their thought processes, aiding in data analysis.
3. **Self-Location:** Participants identify landmarks and their positions using contextual information, the raised relief map, and their starting point. They are

Figure 2. Comparison of raised relief and 3D map visualizations for indoor and outdoor settings. Each sub-figure is labeled with a) Raised relief outdoor, b) Outdoor 3D map, c) Raised relief indoor, and d) Indoor 3D map.

instructed to navigate from point A to location B, utilizing auditory cues to aid their journey.

4.2.3 Participants

Invitations to participate in the study were disseminated through word-of-mouth and mailing lists, resulting in the recruitment of 10 participants: five BVI participants sourced from a mailing list of ACAPO, in the city of Porto, and five sighted participants recruited via the University of Porto mailing list. Table 2 summarizes the participants’ demographic details. Five of the 10 participants (average 23.5 years old) were females. Breaking down the visual conditions, three participants were classified as blind, two had low vision, and five were sighted. Most participants (eight) were students, and two were employed. Regarding musical proficiency, four had no experience, four had basic knowledge, and two had a solid musical background. All participants were familiar with current digital technologies. Given the experiment’s VR context, video game experience was also recorded, as it could affect navigation abilities. Five participants reported no video game experience, while the other five had some or considerable experience.

4.3 Data Collection

The perceptual listening test used a quantitative data collection process with predefined questions to ensure data validity. Administered via LimeSurvey, the survey included three sections examining the relationships between semantic properties and sounds: obstacle material-timbre, width-pitch, and interaction-modulation. Participants answered 12 questions each, resulting in 600 trials (12 questions ×

ID	Sex	Age	Vision	Music Exp.	Game Exp.
P1	F	20	Low	No	No
P2	M	21	Low	Low	Low
P3	F	22	Blind	Low	No
P4	F	24	Sighted	Low	High
P5	M	27	Sighted	No	No
P6	M	25	Blind	High	High
P7	F	21	Blind	Low	No
P8	M	23	Sighted	High	High
P9	F	24	Sighted	High	No
P10	M	27	Sighted	High	Low

Table 2. Participants’ demographic information

50 participants). Responses were recorded in a confusion matrix format.

In the in-person navigation experiment, 10 participants navigated two maps with 27 objects and 42 unique sound combinations. Data collection included both quantitative and qualitative components. Quantitative data focused on object recognition, self-positioning, and the identification of sound properties, documented in a confusion matrix. A total of 270 trials (27 sound combinations \times 10 participants) were conducted.

Qualitative data was gathered through think-aloud methodology, with participants providing feedback via open-ended questions and completing the System Usability Scale (SUS) questionnaire at the session’s end.

4.4 Data Analysis

In both experiments, we report the results in terms of accuracy, computed as the ratio of correctly categorized stimuli to the total number of tests for a given category. In detail, for the perceptual listening test, accuracy measures the number of correct associations between the sound properties. For the in-person VR experiment, it measures the number of correctly identified obstacles’ semantics and their spatial properties. Results are reported for the total number of participants per experiment and sub-groups of visual condition, musical knowledge, age, and nationality. Descriptive statistics, including the average and standard deviation, measuring the dispersion of the values from the mean, are reported per group. To infer statistical differences between groups, we adopted the non-parametric Mann-Whitney U test.

5. RESULTS

5.1 Recognition of Sound and Semantic Properties Mappings

The global accuracy for the semantic object recognition tasks from the online listening test was $.69 \pm .13$. When examining the individual mappings, we obtain an accuracy of $.66 \pm .42$ for *obstacle material-timbre*, $.64 \pm .48$ for *width-pitch*, and $.75 \pm .43$ for *interaction-modulation*. Significant variability in participant responses is observed while presenting relatively high average accuracy, suggesting differing levels of familiarity and understanding of the sound associations.

Metal and glass were identified as the most recognizable materials within the *obstacle material-timbre* associations,

Figure 3. Accuracy of obstacles’ semantic properties. a) Accuracy of obstacle materials, b) confusion matrix for obstacle material, c) accuracy for width-pitch, and d) accuracy for interaction-modulation.

with $.95 \pm .06$ and $.72 \pm .13$ average accuracy, respectively. Wood and brick proved most challenging to distinguish, with an accuracy of $.49 \pm .15$. In Figure 3 b), a confusion matrix illustrates a tendency among participants to mismatch wood and brick while consistently identifying metal and glass.

Similar statistics resulted for *width-pitch* associations, with high-pitch narrow objects achieving an accuracy of $.67 \pm .07$. Individual contributions showed that wood and brick performed notably well, scoring $.64 \pm .1$ and $.62 \pm .1$, respectively. However, glass lagged with a score of $.53 \pm .07$, suggesting that the acoustic properties of materials significantly influence participants’ ability to make accurate associations. This finding contrasts with the *obstacle material-timbre* results, revealing that different auditory dimensions interact in complex ways.

For the *interaction-modulation* dimension was particularly recognizable for high-interaction sounds with $.75 \pm .07$ accuracy. These results suggest a strong link between modulation and interaction associations, indicating that participants were better equipped in this auditory category.

5.2 Navigation Performance

The in-person navigation experiment evaluated the participants’ performance in recognizing sound cues, identifying objects, and self-locating within the virtual environment. Participants achieved an average accuracy of $.73 \pm .16$ across all tasks, with sound recognition output the highest accuracy at $.88 \pm .14$, reflecting the effectiveness of the sonification technique. Object recognition followed with a score of $.72 \pm .13$, while the most challenging task—self-location—scored an accuracy of $.60 \pm .2$.

In the sound cues recognition task, timbre attained an

overall accuracy of $.88 \pm .12$, with pitch and modulation scoring $.9 \pm .1$ and $.93 \pm .05$, respectively. Volume and panning also received high ratings of $.94 \pm .05$ and $.94 \pm .1$. In contrast, tone intervals scored lower at $.77 \pm .2$, indicating high variability in participants' responses. The material recognition was improved in comparison with the perceptual experiment, with accuracy results of $.86 \pm .1$ for wood, $.85$ for metal, $.80 \pm .17$ for glass, $.93 \pm .12$ for brick, and $.94 \pm .1$ for sinewaves. This improvement is noteworthy, particularly following training sessions before the experiment, which reduced accuracy dispersion across materials.

The object recognition task showed participants encountered an average of ten objects per map, with an overall accuracy of $.72 \pm .13$, correctly identifying about seven out of ten objects. Recognition times decreased significantly with repeated encounters, from 10.5 seconds on the first encounter to 6.0 seconds by the sixth. Qualitative feedback indicated increased confidence as participants became familiar with the objects, although some felt overwhelmed by multiple stimuli.

The self-location task was challenging, with participants averaging $2.4 \pm .6$ instances of disorientation before examiner intervention, improving to 1.4 ± 1.28 afterward. The average experiment duration was about 7 minutes, with more time spent on the indoor map due to its size and complexity. Self-location accuracy improved from $.44 \pm .20$ before intervention to $.62 \pm .27$ afterward. The heatmap analysis in Figure 4 highlights areas of prolonged engagement, emphasizing the need to gather information before making navigational decisions.

Figure 4. Comparison of a) outdoor and b) indoor hotspots of average stop time.

5.3 Comparison of Demographic Factors

Demographic comparisons provided valuable insights into the influence of musical background and vision condition on accuracy. Participants with some musical training achieved a higher overall accuracy ($.79 \pm .14$) than those without musical knowledge ($.63 \pm .24$). Significant statistical differences (p-value of $.029$) were found, suggesting that musical knowledge is critical to improving sound recognition abilities. Although participants with musical training demonstrated higher accuracy in *obstacle material-timbre* and *width-pitch* associations, these differences did not reach statistical significance, indicating the need for further exploration.

Comparative analysis revealed that sighted participants had slightly higher accuracy ($.49 \pm .34$) than blind and low-vision participants ($.45 \pm .38$), though no significant statistical differences were found ($p = .86$). This may be due to the limited representation of blind and low-vision participants, who comprised 22% of the sample. Age also played a role, with younger participants (ages 18-24) showing lower accuracy ($.32 \pm .70$) and greater variability, while older participants had more consistent accuracy ($.56 \pm .64$). This highlights the impact of age on auditory perception and sound association.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

We proposed a sonification method to assist BVI individuals in navigating two (outdoor and indoor) environments by mapping spatial and semantic information about objects into non-speech sounds.

Our evaluation of the proposed mappings in an online listening test showed an overall accuracy of $.69 \pm .13$ in recognizing semantic attributes of objects, indicating that participants could make meaningful associations between sounds and object properties. The analysis highlighted variability in performance across different sound dimensions, underscoring sound perception's inherent complexity and subjectivity, emphasizing the need for refinement in sound design to improve recognition rates.

An in-person navigation experiment in VR further confirmed the effectiveness of auditory cues in aiding navigation, achieving an average accuracy of $.73 \pm .16$ across three primary tasks: recognition of sound cues, identification of objects, and self-location within a virtual environment. The strong correlation between sound cue recognition and repeated exposure improved accuracy in object recognition, with an overall accuracy of $.72 \pm .13$, emphasizing the importance of a robust base of intuitive sounds to reduce the learning curve in real-world applications. Self-location tasks proved challenging, highlighting the added difficulty simulated 3D spaces pose for both BVI and sighted individuals. However, after the examiner intervention, participants showed notable improvement in spatial perception, overcoming the initial disorientation common in such complex environments.

Qualitative feedback from participants regarding the prototype was positive, indicating satisfaction with the clarity and logical structure of the sound mappings. This was supported by a System Usability Scale (SUS) score of 75, exceeding the industry average of 68 and indicating strong usability. However, the feedback also pointed to potential areas for improvement, particularly concerning user experience in navigating complex environments. This emphasizes the need for continued system refinement to enhance usability and further accommodate the diverse needs of participants.

Overall, the findings from this research highlight the potential of sonification techniques as valuable aids for BVI individuals, enhancing spatial awareness and navigation through auditory cues. By integrating sound perception with practical navigation tasks, we gain insight into how intuitive sounds can support learning and navigation. Fu-

ture research should involve a more diverse participant pool and investigate the effects of sound training on recognition abilities, leading to better auditory interfaces for improved accessibility.

Future work will focus on refining the sonification method by adjusting sound categories and testing them in sound perceptual experiments to reduce subjectivity. Expanding these experiments across various channels will help gather more comprehensive data. Additionally, integrating sonification with computer vision can improve real-world navigation systems.

While current research emphasizes vision, our experiments suggest hearing plays a crucial role. Exploring non-verbal sound-based languages could prove essential, embracing the abstract nature of sound as a strength. Ultimately, our work aims to demonstrate that the sum of these efforts creates more effective systems for the BVI community.

7. REFERENCES

- [1] E. Nuhn, K. Hamburger, and S. Timpf, "Urban sound mapping for wayfinding – a theoretical approach and an empirical study," *AGILE: Giscience Series*, vol. 4, pp. 1–13, 2023.
- [2] M. Hersh, "Wearable travel aids for blind and partially sighted people: A review with a focus on design issues," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 14, p. 5454, 2022.
- [3] G. Kramer, *Auditory Display: Sonification, Audification, And Auditory Interfaces*, 1994.
- [4] D. Gomez, J. Bologna, and T. Pun, "See color: an extended sensory substitution device for the visually impaired," *Journal of Assistive Technologies*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 77–94, 2014.
- [5] D. K. Mcgookin and S. A. Brewster, "Understanding concurrent earcons," *ACM Transactions on Applied Perception*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 130–155, 2004.
- [6] B. N. Walker and G. Kramer, "Auditory displays, alarms, and auditory interfaces," in *International Encyclopedia of Ergonomics and Human Factors*, 2006, pp. 1021–1025.
- [7] B. N. Walker and M. A. Nees, "Theory of sonification," in *The sonification handbook*, 2011, vol. 1, pp. 9–39.
- [8] B. N. Walker and L. M. Mauney, "Universal design of auditory graphs: A comparison of sonification mappings for visually impaired and sighted listeners," *ACM Transactions on Accessible Computing (TACCESS)*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 1–16, 2010.
- [9] I. I. Bukvic, G. D. Earle, D. Sardana, and W. Joo, "Studies in spatial aural perception: establishing foundations for immersive sonification," *Unpublished work*, 2019.
- [10] F. Morando, A. Lepetit, J. Espinosa, and S. Trentin, "Morphocons: A new sonification concept based on morphological earcons," *Proceedings of the 13th International Conference on Auditory Display (ICAD 2006)*, pp. 307–312, 2006.
- [11] G. Presti, D. Ahmetovic, M. Ducci, C. Bernareggi, L. Ludovico, A. Baratè, F. Avanzini, and S. Mascetti, "Watchout: Obstacle sonification for people with visual impairment or blindness," New York, NY, USA, p. 402–413, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3308561.3353779>
- [12] T. L. Smith and E. B. Moore, "Storytelling to sensemaking: A systematic framework for designing auditory description display for interactives," New York, NY, USA, p. 1–12, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3313831.3376460>
- [13] T. Senan, B. Hengeveld, and B. Eggen, "Sounding obstacles for social distance sonification," in *Proceedings of the 17th International Audio Mostly Conference*, September 2022, pp. 187–194.
- [14] K. Kurakata, T. Mizunami, and K. Matsushita, "Sensory unpleasantness of high-frequency sounds," *Acoustical Science and Technology*, vol. 34, no. 1, pp. 26–33, 2013.
- [15] A. Sharif, O. Wang, and A. Muongchan, "What makes sonification user-friendly? exploring usability and user-friendliness of sonified responses," pp. 1–5, 10 2022.
- [16] Z. Cao, A. Pinto, and S. Bernardes, "Bisaid: Bipolar semantic adjectives icons and earcons dataset," in *Proceedings of the Sound and Music Computing Conference*, 2024.
- [17] D. Bogdanov, N. Wack, E. Gómez, S. Gulati, P. Herrera, O. Mayor, G. Roma, J. Salamon, J. R. Zapata, and X. Serra, "Essentia: An audio analysis library for music information retrieval," in *International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference*, 2013. [Online]. Available: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:11200511>
- [18] G. Eshetu, *Factors affecting instructional leaders perception towards educational media utilization in classroom teaching*. Anchor Academic Publishing, 2015.
- [19] K. W. Ma, H. M. Wong, and C. M. Mak, "A systematic review of human perceptual dimensions of sound: Meta-analysis of semantic differential method applications to indoor and outdoor sounds," *Building and Environment*, vol. 133, pp. 123–150, 2018.
- [20] E. Gandolfi and R. Clements, "Alternative embodied cognitions at play evaluation of audio-based navigation in virtual settings via interactive sounds," *Journal For Virtual Worlds Research*, vol. 12, no. 1, 2019.
- [21] A. Afonso-Jaco and B. F. G. Katz, "Spatial knowledge via auditory information for blind individuals: Spatial cognition studies and the use of audio-vr," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 13, p. 4794, 2022.

EXPERIMENTER EFFECT IN A GUIDED BREATHING EXPERIMENT

Georgios Marentakis

Department of Computer Science and Communication
Østfold University College
BRA Veien 4, 1757 Halden, Norway
georgios.marentakis@hiof.no

Victoria Grace

Muvik Labs
Florida
United States of America
vic@muviklabs.io

ABSTRACT

Guided breathing is a widely used technique for relaxation and stress recovery and a core feature of many biofeedback applications. The design of feedback cues to support guided breathing has received significant attention and there are several proposals using different feedback modalities and their combinations. Studies that investigate the effectiveness of such designs are often done in the laboratory under supervision by the experimenter. Even though it is known that the presence of the experimenter is a factor that may influence participant performance, the extent to which such an effect appears in guided breathing experiments is unknown. To examine this possibility, we designed an experiment in which participants performed guided breathing in the laboratory with and without supervision by the experimenter. The results indicate that the presence of the experimenter affected the stress levels reported by participants and the efficacy of guided breathing which increased when participants performed the experiment unsupervised.

1. INTRODUCTION

Guided breathing is an increasingly focal factor in e-health and is often found in biofeedback applications [1]. Slow breathing helps regulate stress levels [2] and can lead to improved physical and mental health [3]. Numerous commercial applications (e.g., Inner Balance, emWave2, my-Breath, Pranayama), games e.g., [4], tangible interfaces e.g., [5], or virtual reality and artistic interventions [1] use breathing biofeedback. Convenience users, veterans [6], drivers [7], children [8], students [9], athletes [10], and other user groups [2] have benefited.

Breathing biofeedback may be delivered in an open and/or a closed loop. In closed loop applications, users typically adjust their breathing while monitoring relevant psychophysiological parameters. These are often related to stress and include respiration rate, electrodermal activity, heart beat, heart rate variability (HRV), or their derivatives. In open loop applications, users adjust their breathing based on visual, auditory, tactile, or multimodal guided breathing cues.

Copyright: © 2025 Georgios Marentakis et al. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15032536>

Several feedback designs have been proposed in the literature but not all studies evaluate the efficacy of the feedback cues in guiding breathing. It appears though that auditory, visual, and haptic modalities can be used to deliver guided breathing cues equally well [11]. The efficacy of guided breathing cues is typically evaluated in controlled experiments conducted by an experimenter in the laboratory, a common practice in behavioral research. However, existing studies suggest that the presence of an experimenter may influence participants' behavior and the outcome of the experiment [12]. This may be especially important in experiments that evaluate technology that aims to modulate private, covert, and potentially sensitive aspects of behaviour such as stress but also the emotions or well-being of participants.

Given this motivation, our research question investigates the extent to which the presence of experimenter may affect the stress levels reported by participants and the resulting efficacy of guided breathing cues in a controlled experiment. The article is organized as follows. First, we provide background on both breathing biofeedback and on the experimenter presence effect on which we ground our research question. Subsequently, we present a quantitative evaluation study, the results, and a discussion of the findings.

2. BACKGROUND

2.1 Designing Guided Breathing Cues

Guided breathing is a very old technique for effecting our psychophysical state used to both relax but also agitate people. Slow or deep breathing, in particular, is often used for calming down people, commonly in situations that may lead to increased stress. The design of guided breathing techniques has been receiving increased interest during the design of biofeedback applications providing feedback cues for guided breathing.

Feedback for performing guided breathing can be provided visually using simple geometric shapes [2], written instructions or an animation indicating breathing phases, for example, an opening and closing circle as a cue for inhaling or exhaling e.g., [6]. Other researchers propose using peripheral visual cues such as modifications in background screen lighting or brightness [13]. Visual feedback for guided breathing may also involve more complex animations as done when creating biofeedback games e.g., [8] or virtual reality scenes and installations [1]. Auditory

feedback providing guided breathing cues can be speech instructions that cue to breathing phases, non-speech sound such as metronome or simple tones [14], musical sound e.g., [15], but also modulated pink or white noise [16]. Breath-like cues have also been used to guide breathing [17]. The use of music is also common in which case musical parameters are modulated to provide subliminal cues to a desired breathing rate. Multimodal cues may appear in commercial applications (e.g., Breathing Zone, Breathe+), but also in guided breathing videos found on online platforms, but also researcher papers e.g., [16]. Audiovisual cues are very common as they are easy to provide in contemporary devices [18]. Audio, visual, and audio visual cues can work equally well in guiding slow breathing [11]. Tactile, force-feedback, and pneumatic cues have also been used with success [16,19,20].

2.2 The Experimenter Presence Effect

The experimenter, or experimenter presence, effect relates to possible interference in the performance of a test subject during an experiment due to the presence of the experimenter. In their review, Guerin [12] discuss the 'mere presence' effect as one of several cases of social facilitation in performance. They report that the majority of the studies in which the experimenter watched the subject found effects of the experimenter presence. These are likely due to evaluation apprehension, self-presentation, or self-attention effects [12]. They note that it is common that experimenters are viewed as experts, even if they are not, and suggest that the 'presence of a conspecific can increase the drive or arousal of a person because of the uncertainty in the conspecific's behaviour' [12]. Task-specific mediating factors, such as ceiling effects or predictable observer behavior, can potentially limit the size of the experimenter presence effects [12]. For example, a lack of evaluative perception by participants may reduce the influence of experimenter presence. Klein et al. in their review [21] et al also suggest that the experimenter presence influences participant performance. Participants may be influenced to behave in accordance with what they believe experimenters want and try to be "good" subjects [22]. Slight changes in overt behavior of the experimenter between conditions can also influence outcomes.

The experimenter presence may be facilitating to task performance but not necessarily so, especially for more complex tasks [12]. More recently, Belletier et al [23] look into resource limitations due to the presence of others while performing complex tasks focusing on potential impact on the working memory. They used a memorization task and also introduced a secondary task to reduce availability of attention. Concurrent articulation was introduced in some conditions to prevent the use of verbal rehearsal. An effect of the experimenter presence appeared only when verbal rehearsal was prevented indicating that social presence hinders attentional but not non-attentional maintenance in working memory. Garcia-Marques et al [24] in their meta-analysis also find that social presence modulates Stroop interference. Stroop interference is observed in the context of the Stroop task which involves the presentation of a list

of words used as color names (e.g., red, green, etc) that are printed in ink colors that may or may not match the color associated with the presented word. Participants exhibit lower Stroop interference when performing the task in the presence of others than in isolation. The effect was stronger with an attentive audience compared to an inattentive one and null for an evaluative audience. The latter finding may, however, be task-specific as performance in a Stroop task is less sensitive to motivational factors. Interestingly, even if there is evidence that the experimenter presence may modulate results, in their review, Palmer et al [25] find that the majority of articles in behavioural studies do not specify the exact conditions related to experimenter presence. Research shows that experimenter presence influences behavior and stress responses in both humans and animals, highlighting the universal nature of this effect [12,26]. Further evidence from digital health studies emphasizes that human interaction, even when minimal, can enhance engagement and outcomes, particularly in therapeutic settings where participant motivation is critical [27]. These findings underscore the importance of investigating how experimenter presence impacts outcomes in stress-modulating interventions, such as guided breathing. Our study uniquely examines these effects on self-reported stress relief and biofeedback outcomes.

2.3 Summary and Research Question

The literature indicates that visual, auditory, tactile but also multimodal cues have often been used in guided breathing applications and can successfully guide users to perform slow breathing. Slow breathing is known to have the ability to help users calm down, reduce stress, and thus improve their health and well-being. Starting from initially simple cues and instructions, researchers are designing increasingly complex cues using different modalities in different settings. The effectiveness of guided breathing cues needs often to be validated and this process takes place in the laboratory most often in the presence of an experimenter who oversees the experiment.

However, research indicates that the performance of participants may be modulated by the very presence of the experimenter [12,21,26]. It also shows that the experimenter presence effect is task dependent and can be facilitating but also detrimental to task performance while it depends on several parameters related to how the subject perceived the experimenter as well as the specific design of the experiments. The extent to which such an effect will appear in a novel experimental context is very hard to predict without collecting empirical data. As a first step in investigating the impact of the presence of the experimenter on guided breathing, we seek here to identify whether the presence of the experimenter may modulate self-reported stress level and the reported efficacy of the feedback cues during the performance of a guided breathing task.

3. METHOD

As mentioned above, the research question we want to answer is how the presence of an experimenter influences

Figure 1: An illustration of the stimuli used in the experiment. The top panel shows instances of the visual stimulus which consisted of oscillating concentric circles of variable radius. The middle panel shows the auditory waveform and the diminishing loudness cues. The lower panel is the spectrogram showing the bell sound and its harmonics and the drone of rising and falling pitch contour.

Figure 2: Setup of test sessions. I is introduction, S1-S2 are stressor trials (1min 15 sec) and T1-T2 are test guided breathing trials (2 min).

stress modulation during guided breathing tasks. Unlike previous studies, which examined experimenter presence broadly in behavioral contexts [12], this research applies the concept to guided breathing. The research question was evaluated in a controlled experiment. By systematically varying experimenter presence, we aim to understand its impact on stress relief outcomes, providing critical insights for both supervised and self-guided interventions.

The experiment contained both stressor and guided breathing (test) trials. This is not uncommon in the design of experiments that evaluate the efficacy of interventions aiming to reduce stress. The goal is to increase the participants' stress level in the stressor trials so that the efficacy of the intervention can be assessed right after by exposing participants to the treatment (in our case the guided breathing stimulus) in the test trials.

The experiment followed a mixed design with two independent variables. The first was feedback *modality* which was within-subjects and had two levels: visual and auditory. The second was *experimenter presence* and was between-subjects. It had two levels (supervised and unsupervised). There were two dependent variables. The first was the reported stress level of users measured using a Visual Analog Scale (VAS), a common and reliable way to assess stress [28]. The second was stress load and stress relief, calculated as the difference in reported stress levels after exposure to the stressor and the guided breathing stimulus, respectively. By comparing the values of both dependent variables in the supervised and unsupervised conditions, we attempted to establish whether the presence of the experimenter had a significant effect and exactly how it affected the reported levels in the experimental trials.

3.1 Stimuli

Figure 1 shows the visual and auditory stimuli used in the test trials. The visual stimulus consisted of concentric circles whose radius increased throughout the inhale phase and decreased throughout the exhale phase. When stimulus modality was visual, a static drone sound without any cues to the breathing cycle was played in the background to provide a similar context as in the auditory conditions. The auditory stimulus consisted of a bell sound which signaled the beginning of the inhale and of the exhale breathing cycles. The bell's pitch was higher in the inhale compared to the exhale phase. An additional cue was given by a white-noise based drone signal whose pitch swept upwards during the inhaling phase and downwards during the exhale phase. The drone signal was heard over an ambience of stacked notes whose amplitude was modulated by slow moving LFOs. These notes were in harmony with the alternating entrainment sounds. The circle used in the visual condition was also shown in the auditory condition. However, it remained static and provided no cues to the guided breathing.

In the stressor trials, participants watched a video which instructed them to perform a number of mental arithmetic operations under time pressure while listening to a distressing sound stimulus (a sawtooth wave with a fundamental that swept upwards increasing to uncomfortable levels to accentuate the effect and the time pressure) and report the result. Mental arithmetic under time pressure is often used to induce stress e.g., [29]. Test trial duration was 2 minutes and stressor trial duration 1 minute and 15 seconds. The stimulus was prepared for a slow (5 breaths per minute) respiration pace.

3.2 Participants

Two groups of 16 healthy adults ($\mu = 26.4$ years, $\sigma = 7.47$ years, 20 male, 12 female) participated in the study. Subjects did not report any respiration problems. They provided informed consent before the experiment. Participation was voluntary and could be terminated at any time.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 3: a. Absolute VAS stress level on test (guided breathing) trials. b. Difference in VAS stress level after test (guided breathing) trials. c. Absolute VAS stress level on the stressor trials. d. Difference in VAS stress level after stressor trials. Brackets indicate standard error.

3.3 Procedure

Each experiment session started with explaining what will happen in the experiment followed by a demonstration of breathing along the stimuli from the experimenter. Subsequently, the interleaved test and stressor trials were presented as illustrated in Figure 2. The order of presentation of the feedback modalities was counterbalanced across participants. When participants were supervised the experimenter remained in the room, otherwise the experimenter left the room as soon as instructions were given and the demonstration was finished. The subjects could call the experimenter as soon as the test was finished. After completing a test or stressor trial participants provided a stress rating on a VAS scale between 0 and 100. Each session lasted about 1 hour. Participants entered stress levels using the VAS also before engaging in the first trial.

3.4 Instructions

At test trials, participants were instructed to 'Try to relax and sync your breath to the stimuli in the video'. After exposure to each video participants were instructed to 'Enter how stressed you feel using the slider below'. In the stressor trials, participants were instructed to perform the mental arithmetic task while listening to the sound played.

3.5 Setup

The stimuli for the test and stressor trials were prepared and stored in video files. The order of presentation was controlled by a MAX/MSP patch running on a PC. The patch guided participants through the trials. In each trial, participants pressed a button when ready to start. This triggered the display of the relevant video which was either a stressor or a test video containing auditory or visual cues as appropriate. After exposure, participants indicated their perceived stress level using the VAS which was displayed as a slider on the screen. The experiment was performed in a quiet laboratory environment. Sound was played by a Steel Series headset.

3.6 Hypotheses

We hypothesize that (H1) reported stress levels will be reduced after exposure to the guided breathing stimuli in the test trials and (H2) increased due to exposure to the stressor stimuli in the stressor trials. Furthermore, we hypothesized (H3) that an effect of experimenter will be observed, as this is the most common finding in the literature. Given that we were not able to find a similar experiment in the literature, we did not form a hypothesis with respect to the direction of the effect.

4. RESULTS

The dataset we analyzed consisted of the participant stress levels reported using the VAS after each stressor or test trial as well as the stress relief or load data, estimated as the difference in the reported stress levels (VAS) after and before being exposed to the stimulus presented in each test and stressor trial, respectively. Data can be seen in Figure 3. The presentation of the results and the statistical analysis is centered on examining the effect of the experimenter presence.

A check for outliers was performed using the `boxplot.stats` function of R. This removed 2 out of the 128 reported stress level data points (VAS scale) and 12 out of the 128 stress load and stress relief data points. The underlying distribution of the data sets in each condition was examined visually and using a Shapiro-Wilk test. When analyzing the VAS scale data, in 6 out of the 8 conditions the hypothesis that data come from a normal distribution was rejected and non-parametric tests were used. When analyzing the stress relief and load data, this happened in only 2 out of the 8 conditions, and given the robustness of ANOVA to small violations in the assumptions, we performed a parametric test.

Figure 3a illustrates reported stress levels in the guided breathing trials. On average, reported stress levels were lower in the unsupervised condition. The effect of experimenter presence was examined using a Kruskal-Wallis test and turned out to be significant, $\chi^2(1) = 3.8911$, $p = 0.048$ thus reported stress levels after exposure to the guided breathing stimulus were significantly lower when unsupervised. In Figure 3b, the stress relief due to exposure to the guided breathing stimulus is shown. We see that exposure to the guided breathing stimulus reduced stress levels. The extent to which the reduction was significantly different than 0 was examined using a t-test. The outcome was significant ($p < 0.01$) for all conditions in the experiment. Again, stress relief appears to increase in the unsupervised conditions. A 2-way mixed ANOVA with *modality* as within-subjects factor and *presence* as a between-subjects factor was performed showing that the effect of *experimenter presence* was significant, $F(1,30) = 5.27$, $p = 0.028$, $\eta^2 = 0.12$. Stress relief was significantly higher when unsupervised.

In Figure 3c, we see the reported stress level after exposure to the stressor stimulus. On average, a higher stress level after exposure is reported when unsupervised. The effect of experimenter presence was examined using a Kruskal-Wallis test but turned out not to be significant ($p = 0.23$). In Figure 3d, stress load is reported. On average, exposure to stressor trials increased stress load. The extent to which the increase was significantly higher than 0 was examined using a t-test. The outcome was significant ($p < 0.01$) for all conditions in the experiment. Again, a 2-way mixed ANOVA with *modality* as within-subjects factor and *experimenter presence* as a between-subjects factor was performed on the stress load. The effect of *experimenter presence* was significant, $F(1,30) = 10.45$, $p = 0.002$, $\eta^2 = 0.20$. Reported stress load was significantly higher when participants were unsupervised.

5. DISCUSSION

This study was a first step in examining whether the presence of the experimenter may have an effect on reported stress levels during a guided deep breathing experiment. In a controlled experiment, participants took part in interleaved stressor and guided breathing trials which were either supervised or unsupervised by the experimenter. Participants reported their perceived stress level using a visual analogue scale after each trial was completed. Stress load and relief were calculated as the difference in reported stress levels before and after exposure to a guided breathing test or stressor stimulus. We examined the effect of experimenter presence for both the absolute reported stress level (VAS scale data) as well as for stress load and relief.

Reported stress level increased significantly after exposure to the stressor trials and decreased significantly after exposure to test trials. This is in accordance with hypothesis H1 and H2.

Focusing on the guided breathing trials, we did find a significant effect due to the presence of the experimenter both when examining reported stress levels (VAS data) and when examining stress relief data. When unsupervised, participants reported significantly lower stress after exposure to the guided breathing stimulus compared to when supervised. Stress relief was also significantly higher when unsupervised compared to when supervised. Focusing on the stressor trials, the effect of the experimenter presence was significant when analyzing stress load. Furthermore, participants also reported higher stress levels after exposure to the stressor when unsupervised compared to when supervised, however, the effect was not significant.

Taken together, these results provide evidence for the existence of an experimenter presence effect in guided breathing experiments. The effect was most evident in conditions in which participants were exposed to the guided breathing stimulus in which case it was significant for reported stress level (VAS) and stress relief. In the stressor trials, even if a similar tendency appears in the reported stress level (VAS), the effect was only significant when analyzing stress load. Concluding, it can be argued that the reported findings are in agreement with the trend for observing a significant effect due to the presence of the experimenter in the behavioural studies in the literature [12] and partially confirm H3.

Some interesting observations can also be made concerning the direction of the effect. The tendency is to report significantly lower absolute stress levels after exposure to the guided breathing stimulus when unsupervised compared to when supervised. Reported stress relief is also significantly higher when unsupervised compared to when supervised. A similar tendency appears for the stress load data, which is also significantly higher when unsupervised compared to when supervised. Taken together, these results imply that the presence of the experimenter may reduce the reported efficacy of the intervention. A similar, even if not significant, tendency is similar for the reported stress levels, as these are higher when unsupervised compared to when supervised.

Concluding, the findings of this study highlight the nu-

anced role of the experimenter presence in guided breathing interventions and raise broader questions about how the delivery of auditory design strategies and facilitation methods impact user engagement and intervention efficacy. In practical applications, the way interventions are delivered, whether through a personalized session curated by a facilitator, AI-driven customization, or generic pre-recorded content, could profoundly influence the perceived relevance and efficacy of the experience. These aspects will be the objective of future investigations in this topic.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Motivated by the different findings in the literature pertaining to the effect of the experimenter presence, we performed a controlled evaluation study in which participants performed guided breathing with and without an experimenter being present. We measured reported stress level after exposure to the test stimuli or stressor trails. Exposure to the test stimuli and stressor trials worked as expected and stress levels respectively decreased and increased. The results provide supportive evidence with respect to a significant effect due to the presence of the experimenter. Specifically, the presence of the experimenter affected significantly reported stress levels in the guided breathing trials as well as stress relief and stress load in both guided breathing and stressor trials. Participants tended to report a lower efficacy of the test and stressor stimuli when the experimenter was present. Future research will look into verifying this result in the light of evidence from physiological data.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank Paul Aurelian Pop and Muhammad Umer for assisting in data collection.

7. REFERENCES

- [1] M. Prpa, E. R. Stepanova, T. Schiphorst, B. E. Riecke, and P. Pasquier, "Inhaling and exhaling: How technologies can perceptually extend our breath awareness," in *Proceedings of the 2020 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 2020, pp. 1–15.
- [2] L. Kennedy and S. H. Parker, "Biofeedback as a stress management tool: A systematic review," *Cognition, Technology & Work*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 161–190, 2019.
- [3] A. Steptoe and M. Kivimäki, "Stress and cardiovascular disease," *Nature Reviews Cardiology*, vol. 9, no. 6, p. 360, 2012.
- [4] T. Sonne and M. M. Jensen, "Chillfish: A respiration game for children with adhd," in *Proceedings of the TEI'16: Tenth International Conference on Tangible, Embedded, and Embodied Interaction*, 2016, pp. 271–278.
- [5] J. Costa, F. Guimbretière, M. F. Jung, and T. Choudhury, "Boostmeup: Improving cognitive performance in the moment by unobtrusively regulating emotions with a smartwatch," *Proceedings of the ACM on Interactive, Mobile, Wearable and Ubiquitous Technologies*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 1–23, 2019.
- [6] D. Plans, D. Morelli, S. Sütterlin, L. Ollis, G. Derbyshire, and M. Cropley, "Use of a biofeedback breathing app to augment poststress physiological recovery: Randomized pilot study," *JMIR formative research*, vol. 3, no. 1, p. e12227, 2019.
- [7] S. Zepf, N. El Haouij, J. Lee, A. Ghandeharioun, J. Hernandez, and R. W. Picard, "Studying personalized just-in-time auditory breathing guides and potential safety implications during simulated driving," in *Proceedings of the 28th ACM Conference on User Modeling, Adaptation and Personalization*, 2020, pp. 275–283.
- [8] T. Sonne, T. Merritt, P. Marshall, J. J. Lomholt, J. Müller, and K. Grønbæk, "Calming children when drawing blood using breath-based biofeedback," in *Proceedings of the 2017 Conference on Designing Interactive Systems*, 2017, pp. 725–737.
- [9] V. Deschodt-Arsac, R. Lalanne, B. Spiluttini, C. Bertin, and L. M. Arsac, "Effects of heart rate variability biofeedback training in athletes exposed to stress of university examinations," *PLoS one*, vol. 13, no. 7, p. e0201388, 2018.
- [10] S. J. Morgan and J. A. M. Mora, "Effect of heart rate variability biofeedback on sport performance, a systematic review," *Applied psychophysiology and biofeedback*, vol. 42, no. 3, pp. 235–245, 2017.
- [11] G. Marentakis, V. Grace, and J. Berger, "Multimodal Cues for guided breathing," in *Proceedings of the Forum Acusticum*. European Acoustics Association, 2023.
- [12] B. Guerin, "Mere presence effects in humans: A review," *Journal of experimental social psychology*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 38–77, 1986.
- [13] A. Ghandeharioun and R. Picard, "BrightBeat: Effortlessly influencing breathing for cultivating calmness and focus," in *Proceedings of the 2017 CHI Conference Extended Abstracts on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. ACM, 2017, pp. 1624–1631.
- [14] MH. Schein, B. Gavish, M. Herz, D. Rosner-Kahana, P. Naveh, B. Knishkowsky, E. Zlotnikov, N. Ben-Zvi, and RN. Melmed, "Treating hypertension with a device that slows and regularises breathing: A randomised, double-blind controlled study," *Journal of human hypertension*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 271–278, 2001.
- [15] G. Leslie, A. Ghandeharioun, D. Zhou, and R. W. Picard, "Engineering music to slow breathing and invite relaxed physiology," in *2019 8th International Conference on Affective Computing and Intelligent Interaction (ACII)*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 1–7.

- [16] J. Frey, M. Grabli, R. Slyper, and J. R. Cauchard, “Breeze: Sharing biofeedback through wearable technologies,” in *Proceedings of the 2018 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 2018, pp. 1–12.
- [17] G. Marentakis, D. Borthakur, P. Batchelor, J. P. Andersen, and V. Grace, “Using breath-like cues for guided breathing,” in *Extended Abstracts of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 2021, pp. 1–7.
- [18] J. Yu, J. H. Choi, S. Y. Ma, T. S. Jeung, and S. Lim, “Comparison between audio-only and audiovisual biofeedback for regulating patients’ respiration during four-dimensional radiotherapy,” *Radiation oncology journal*, vol. 33, no. 3, p. 250, 2015.
- [19] A. C. Haynes, C. Kent, and J. Rossiter, “Just a breath away: Investigating interactions with and perceptions of mediated breath via a haptic cushion,” in *Proceedings of the Eighteenth International Conference on Tangible, Embedded, and Embodied Interaction*, ser. Tei ’24. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2024.
- [20] T. Gemiciglu, T. Viranda, Y. Zhao, O. Yessenbayev, J. Arora, J. Wang, P. Lopes, A. T. Adams, and T. Choudhury, “BreathePulse: Peripheral Guided Breathing via Implicit Airflow Cues for Information Work,” *Proceedings of the ACM on Interactive, Mobile, Wearable and Ubiquitous Technologies*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 1–33, Nov. 2024.
- [21] O. Klein, S. Doyen, C. Leys, P. A. Magalhães De Saldanha Da Gama, S. Miller, L. Questienne, and A. Cleeremans, “Low Hopes, High Expectations: Expectancy Effects and the Replicability of Behavioral Experiments,” *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 572–584, Nov. 2012.
- [22] A. L. Nichols and J. K. Maner, “The Good-Subject Effect: Investigating Participant Demand Characteristics,” *The Journal of General Psychology*, vol. 135, no. 2, pp. 151–166, Apr. 2008.
- [23] C. Belletier and V. Camos, “Does the experimenter presence affect working memory?” *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, vol. 1424, no. 1, pp. 212–220, Jul. 2018.
- [24] T. Garcia-Marques and A. C. Fernandes, “Meta-Analysis of Social Presence Effects on Stroop Task Performance,” *Psychological Reports*, p. 00332941241227150, Jan. 2024.
- [25] M. G. Palmer and C. M. Johnson, “Experimenter presence in human behavior analytic laboratory studies: Confound it?” *Behavior Analysis: Research and Practice*, vol. 19, no. 4, p. 303, 2019.
- [26] G. M. Burghardt, J. N. Bartmess-LeVasseur, S. A. Browning, K. E. Morrison, C. L. Stec, C. E. Zachau, and T. M. Freeberg, “Perspectives – Minimizing Observer Bias in Behavioral Studies: A Review and Recommendations,” *Ethology*, vol. 118, no. 6, pp. 511–517, Jun. 2012.
- [27] J. L. Mair, A. Salamanca-Sanabria, M. Augsburger, B. F. Frese, S. Abend, R. Jakob, T. Kowatsch, and S. Haug, “Effective behavior change techniques in digital health interventions for the prevention or management of noncommunicable diseases: An umbrella review,” *Annals of Behavioral Medicine*, vol. 57, no. 10, pp. 817–835, 2023.
- [28] F.-X. Lesage, S. Berjot, and F. Deschamps, “Clinical stress assessment using a visual analogue scale,” *Occupational medicine*, vol. 62, no. 8, pp. 600–605, 2012.
- [29] A. Sawai, T. Motomura, T. Oshima, S. Sawai, T. Fujikawa, H. Fujii, Y. Bannai, Y. Takeda, M. Ohno, and O. Tochikubo, “Influence of acute mental arithmetic stress on taste and pungency,” *Journal of nutritional science and vitaminology*, vol. 65, no. 3, pp. 224–232, 2019.

Situationally-Induced Impairments and Child Care: The Case of Browsing an Audio Streaming Platform In Kangaroo Care

Kajol Rafi Kjetil Falkenberg

KTH Royal Institute of Technology

School of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science

{akrafi, kjetil}@kth.se

ABSTRACT

Neonatal care poses unique challenges for parents of premature babies, particularly during kangaroo care, a practice involving prolonged skin-to-skin contact to promote infant health and bonding. While beneficial, this method restricts mobility and requires a calm, low sensory stimulation environment. Many parents turn to audio content, such as music or podcasts, for relaxation and to shield against noise. However, conventional audio streaming platform (ASP) interfaces rely heavily on visual and manual input, making them difficult to use in these conditions. Through interviews and questionnaires with parents, we identified how situationally-induced impairments (SIIs) caused by kangaroo care hinder interactions with ASPs. To address these challenges, we propose to test a design concept (originally targeted to cater to SIIs more generally) involving on-body sensors, gesture-based interaction and multimodal feedback. These solutions enable intuitive audio management with minimal visual or manual reliance, enhancing accessibility and, presumably, supporting caregiver well-being. This work highlights the importance of inclusive, multimodal designs for contexts like neonatal care and contributes to broader accessibility efforts for users experiencing SIIs.

1. INTRODUCTION

Listening to audio content, such as music, podcasts, and audiobooks, is a common way for people to relax, focus, or escape everyday stressors. However, accessing and controlling this content often relies heavily on visual and manual interaction with digital platforms like Spotify, YouTube Music, or Audible. Such *audio streaming platforms* (ASPs) provide users with access to an expansive universe of audio content, and invoke deep personalisation to curate recommendations [1, 2].

An ASP's success in delivering a value-enriched user experience also depends on its ability to facilitate dynamic exploration: empower users to navigate through recommendations and content easily, and make decisions with less effort. However, this proposition, along with the high information density involved, introduces accessibility challenges. Engagement with an ASP while simultaneously engaged

in other activities like commuting, exercising, doing domestic tasks, or taking care of children, influences their interaction styles, navigation patterns and browsing choices. In such cases, users may experience varying degrees of *situationally-induced impairments* (SIIs): impairments in perceptive or cognitive capabilities that occur when external contextually-imposed factors place temporary constraints on the user [3]. The expression of SIIs are usually dynamic in nature since the contextual situation imposing the SIIs are often dynamic themselves, placing time-variant demands on the user's abilities.

One context where challenges of SIIs and interaction become pronounced is in neonatal care, specifically during *Kangaroo Care* where parents lie with their premature babies on their chest in prolonged periods of skin-to-skin contact [4]. It is common for kangaroo care to last for extended periods, up to several weeks. While kangaroo care is beneficial for the infant's health and bonding, it can be extremely stressful to parents for a number of reasons. Many parents engage with audio content for personal relaxation, as an auditory shield against background noise, or to regulate sleep. However, the anticipated low-stimulation situation of kangaroo care and the position of the child drastically restrict their freedom of movement. Visual and manual interaction with audio players gets impractical with risk of disrupting the contact with the baby.

The first author has developed SII-accommodating concepts for ASP interfaces that utilise gesture-based controls and spreads feedback between multiple modalities such as audio and haptic cues, to replace over-reliance on interactions with visual-heavy interfaces. That work builds on principles of *Ability-Based Design* (ABD), a sister-framework for accessible computing that advocates harnessing the potential of working with user abilities and environmental affordances [5, 6]. This design conceptualisation addresses broader implications for accessible interfaces for any scenario where SIIs restrict sensory or attentional resources—including those where the user is mobile, 'on-the-go'.

In this study, we probe how SIIs imposed on a user's physical, sensory and cognitive abilities when they're in a highly demanding contextual situation like kangaroo care can affect their interactions with ASPs, and explore accessible design solutions that accommodate their abilities. The developed concept designs aim to empower users to intuitively manage audio content without compromising their ongoing activities—in this case facilitating and administering kangaroo care. By investigating how to design accessible

Copyright: © 2025 Kajol Rafi et al. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15032563>

experiences to accommodate these unique challenges, we contribute to inclusive design approaches that account for diverse user needs in real-world, constrained environments.

2. BACKGROUND

2.1 Situationally-Induced Impairments

Situationally-induced impairments occur when an individual's abilities are temporarily limited by situational factors (specific circumstances), contextual factors (goals, state, and purpose), or environmental factors (physical and social setting) [3]; see also the World Health Organization's 2020 policy on disability. With ubiquitous computing, these impairments are increasingly relevant as varying situations introduce new challenges for interaction.

Factors contributing to SIIs include behavioral (e.g., walking [7], encumbrance [8]), environmental (e.g., noise, cold, out-of-reach devices [9]), attentional (e.g., multitasking [10], cognitive overload [11]), and affective, social, and technological (e.g., stress, norms, small devices). Designing with SIIs in mind enables adaptable, inclusive solutions—for example, a smartphone operable with one hand benefits both someone holding a baby and a person with one arm [3]. Despite progress, many devices lack situational awareness, necessitating further development in context-aware technology.

2.2 Frameworks in Accessible Computing

Accessible computing has evolved through various frameworks: Early frameworks, like Assistive Technology, provided tools for users with disabilities but risked stigmatization through add-on solutions [12]. Universal Design, influenced by the limitations of Assistive Technology, emphasized “one-size-fits-all” inclusivity but proved too rigid for personalized digital interactions [5]. Design for All aimed to extend accessibility into the digital realm but primarily addressed general rather than individual needs [13]. Similarly, Inclusive Design sought to minimize exclusion by considering diverse user abilities but struggled to scale due to designers' unconscious biases and limited capacity to account for all needs [14].

Building on these approaches, the Ability-Based Design (ABD) framework prioritizes user strengths and shifts the burden of adaptation from the user to the system [6]. The seven ABD principles¹ advocate for flexible, scalable, and dignity-preserving technologies that work with what users can do, asking, “*What can you do?*” rather than “*What can everyone do?*” [5]. This study employs the ABD framework to contextualize its findings in accessible computing.

2.3 Hands-Free Interaction

Voice- and gesture-based interaction enables users to control devices in an intuitive, mostly hands-free experience, which is useful when visual attention or touch input is limited [15]. Several commercial solutions exist for hands-free interaction; this is especially true for voice commands which are

¹ Ability, Accountability, Adaptation, Transparency, Performance, Context, Simplicity

widely accepted [16]. Dedicated gesture-based interaction has been popularized in console game architectures like Nintendo Wii and Kinect [17], and more recently virtual reality headsets, but still without reaching the same level of acceptance as voice input, or even succeeding in establishing standards for gesture input [18]. In the following we discuss some of the strategies in gesture-based input relevant to SIIs interaction with a handheld device.

One typical characteristic of many SII situations is an incapacity to use both hands normally, for instance when commuting. With this limitation, a device may be operated in different ways: *Same-side interaction* involves using the body part carrying the device to operate it, such as controlling a smartphone with the same hand that holds it. Examples include tilt-navigation [19] and wrist-as-joystick systems [20]. Although convenient, this method has mobility and visibility limitations [21]. *Opposite-side interaction* employs other body parts for control, such as the free hand manipulating a smartwatch, supporting more flexible, precise interactions, as seen in extended touchscreens [22] or multimodal touch-input methods [23].

Studies have proposed guidelines for designing gesture-based systems tailored to different contexts. Examples include mid-air gestures for blind users interacting with TVs [24], touchscreen adaptations [14], and motion gestures for hands-free TV control [25]. However, there is limited research on designing gesture protocols for users with situational impairments in high-information, mobile contexts like adaptive digital platforms.

There are several participatory approaches to gesture interaction design. Context-focused ideation aligns gestures with natural body movements [26], and device-focused elicitation invites users to propose gestures that are easy to learn and recall. Mixed approaches, combining user proposals and curated options, enhance accessibility [24].

2.4 Neonatal Care Units and Kangaroo Care

Premature infants, born before 37 weeks of gestation, often face significant health challenges. Neonatal care focuses on supporting these infants' survival and development, often requiring specialized interventions provided in Neonatal Intensive Care Units (NICUs): equipped medical environments offering life-sustaining treatments. While these units are vital for stabilizing premature infants, they can also be stressful for parents due to the medicalized setting [27]. When intensive care is not required, infants and their parents are moved to regular neonatal care units, often called family rooms.

Kangaroo care is a neonatal care method where an infant is placed skin-to-skin on a caregiver's chest [4]. Originating in the late 1970s as an alternative to incubators in resource-limited settings, the method is now globally recognized for its numerous benefits, including promoting thermal regulation, improving oxygenation, fostering breastfeeding, and strengthening parent-infant bonding.

Premature infants are typically connected to various medical devices, which makes the practice of kangaroo care challenging. Providing this type of care requires the parent to remain stationary for periods of up to several hours, or to

carefully reposition and lift the infant when movement, such as getting up for nursing, is necessary. During the parent's waking hours, they are expected to maintain silence.

3. METHOD

The study's method includes 1) a discovery phase interview process, 2) an ideation workshop, followed by a conceptualisation including a video prototype, and finally, 3) interviews with parents with lived experiences of neonatal care to probe an extreme case of SIIs. Participants were recruited through convenience sampling, with separate, non-overlapping groups for each of the three stages.

3.1 Discovery Research: Semi-Structured Interviews

Before the discovery research interview, participants documented their habits around audio content consumption. The interviews lasted 25–30 minutes and focused on when and how participants engaged with ASPs and audio content while being simultaneously engaged in another activity, how their environment and devices influenced their experience, and how they adapted to challenges. We avoided using terms like 'SIIs' to prevent bias, adhering to ABD principles. The interviews were recorded and transcribed, with a thematic analysis conducted to form insights.

3.2 Generative Ideation: Participatory Workshop

The goal of the workshop was to explore how users envision engaging in a listening session and interacting with their ASPs without relying on touching screen-based or reading visual-heavy interfaces. The participants were divided into two groups based on their audio engagement habits. The workshop had three phases, lasting 180 minutes:

Phase 1—Divergent Ideation: All participants were introduced to 'STUIQUIBOU', a hypothetical screenless and omnipresent ASP, conceptualised to encourage creativity by eliminating current technological limitations. They were instructed to brainstorm and sketch ideas for interacting with this omnipresent ASP using body gestures and sounds.

Phase 2—Prioritisation: The two groups were assigned a contextual situation each (chosen based on their audio engagement habits) to consider how they would interact with 'STUIQUIBOU' using their body gestures in such situations. They identified and prioritised body parts and gestures for interaction based on the context and the abilities they could exercise.

Phase 3—Concept Development: Each group was instructed to design a gesture-based interaction protocol, the supporting on-body artefact, and map out interaction flows and expected feedback from their on-body artefact. Participants considered social factors and ease of use while conceptualising, and communicated their concepts by role-play and demonstration.

The workshop was documented using audio recordings, photos, and written notes. Afterward, the recordings and sketches were transcribed, reviewed, and analysed using an inductive approach to identify key insights.

3.3 Conceptualisation and Realisation

We synthesized findings from the research and prior studies on gesture-based interaction to develop a proposed concept. This concept was sketched, role-played, and tested in two scenarios to assess gesture affordances and sensor data. Low-fidelity prototypes were created and refined into higher-fidelity versions using Figma. A video prototype was developed to demonstrate the concept.

3.4 Contextualising for Kangaroo Care

Finally, we recruited parents from a specialized social media group who had premature infants and had completed a neonatal unit stay of at least two weeks. For this study, the participants were not informed about the design concepts, SIIs, or problems of interacting with ASPs. We conducted both structured interviews and questionnaires which used a 5-step Likert scale response method. The interviews explored topics such as sleep deprivation and the impact of light and sound design in neonatal units, while the questionnaires focused on issues related to alarms, disturbances, kangaroo care, and coping strategies.

3.5 Ethical Considerations

All participants took part in the study voluntarily and provided informed consent. Their data has been anonymized and is handled with care and respect, in full compliance with ethical standards and guidelines. No sensitive data regarding the parents' premature infants was collected, as the study focused solely on their experiences with the sound and light environment to address sleep and interaction issues.

4. RESULTS

We present four main sets of results: (1) key findings from participant responses gathered during the discovery research, (2) relevant observations from participant responses during the participatory ideation process, as well as design considerations, (3) the concept proposal, and (4) implications of using ASP during kangaroo care. The ASP engagement and concept proposal is described in greater detail in a forthcoming thesis publication by the first author² as well as in the video prototype.³

4.1 Discovery Research

Five participants (4F, 1M, aged 24–27) completed semi-structured interviews. They reported normal or corrected vision and engaged with ASPs via smartphones, tablets, laptops, wired earphones, and wireless earphones. ASP providers included YouTube Music, Spotify, Deezer, and Apple Podcasts.

Participants integrated audio content (music, podcasts, or both) into various 'contextual situations', such as cooking, cleaning, laundry, showering, studying/working, exercising, social events, and commuting. Their motivations for audio engagement in such scenarios fell into three categories:

² <https://kth.diva-portal.org/smash/search.jsf?dswid=5048>

³ <https://youtu.be/-IQwnVwr8g8>

Focus and Flow: Audio helped sustain attention during activities like studying by blocking distractions.

Motivation: Tasks requiring energy, such as exercising or cleaning, were made more engaging with audio.

Companionship: Audio served as stimulation during repetitive or mechanical tasks.

Participants' likelihood of addressing unpleasant deviations in audio sessions depended on their activity, the perceived severity of the mismatch, and their willingness to interrupt the task:

High cognitive demand (e.g., navigation): Participants often avoided course corrections due to safety concerns or the inability to allocate visual attention to touch-based interactions.

Motivation-driven tasks: Sensitivity to mismatches was high, with participants more likely to course-correct despite interruptions to the contextual situation.

Focus-driven tasks: While engrossed in their activity, participants detected fewer deviations. However, once noticed, they preferred quick, low-effort adjustments to minimize disruption.

Monotonous tasks: Participants were divided between exploring new content and maintaining precise control over their audio experience.

Device affordances, environmental factors (e.g., public spaces), and contextual constraints (e.g., physical limitations during tasks) also shaped participants' corrective actions and tolerance for mismatches in audio preferences.

4.2 Ideation Workshop Outcome

The workshop involved five participants (3F, 2M, aged 23–30), all of whom relied on a combination of YouTube, Spotify, or TikTok as their primary ASP. Participants were divided into two groups—'Group Gym' and 'Group Cooking'—based on their audio engagement habits.

This section consolidates the key findings emerged from the workshop, and the design considerations for developing ASPs suited for such use cases. The considerations are also contextualized in the ABD framework [5, 6], to enable designers prioritizing accessibility in their design cycles.

Artefact Form: Participants envisioned on-body artefacts that track gestures and provide feedback. Group Gym prioritized artefacts that stayed secure during movement, proposing designs that adhered to the body. Group Cooking suggested artefacts to have flexibility: like a band to tie back hair could also be tied around the arm, emphasizing adaptability to different body parts based on user preferences.

When designing on-body artefacts, designers can consider forms that can stay securely on the user's body during movement, offer versatility in how they're worn, and serve functional purposes. This empowers users, while aligning with the ABD principles 'Accountability', 'Adaptation', and 'Transparency' [5, 6].

Body Part Selection: Group Gym excluded arms and legs, opting for head and neck gestures to avoid interference with exercise. Group Cooking preferred head, feet, and mouth gestures due to their unobstructed availability during cooking. These preferences aligned with commonly used

body parts in gesture-interaction protocols noted in prior studies [28].

For gesture design, prioritizing body parts minimally engaged in the main activity avoids interruptions and improves accessibility. This supports the 'Ability' principle of the ABD framework [5, 6] by leveraging available user capabilities.

Gesture Complexity: For commands involving variables like intensity or time, participants preferred parameterized gestures that conveyed more than binary inputs. These often relied on relative positioning of body parts to communicate dynamic information [24].

For gesture design in these cases, complex, parameterized gestures can be used to convey rich information efficiently, reducing reliance on fallback interfaces. This aligns with the ABD principles 'Ability' and 'Performance' [5, 6].

Intuitive Gestures: Participants favored gestures with natural, intuitive mappings to commands. Metaphorical gestures, based on prior interactions with digital systems, were the most popular.

Incorporating gestures based on familiar metaphors or cultural norms eases learning and recall—critical for SII-friendly interaction. The ASP interaction should tailor mappings to users' cultural contexts or provide customization options. This reflects 'Accountability', 'Adaptation', 'Transparency', and 'Performance' [5, 6].

Accidental Activations: Distinct, deliberate gestures were preferred to avoid false positives during overlapping movements. For example, Group Cooking designed a drag-action foot gesture for skipping songs that wouldn't interfere with typical kitchen activities. Group Gym proposed abstract gestures, such as finger rotations, to prevent disruptions during workouts.

Designers can also prevent unintended triggers through incorporating delimiter gestures, and improve reliability and user control. This aligns with the ABD principle 'Ability' [5, 6].

Complementary Gestures: Commands with opposite effects (e.g., skip forward/backward) were consistently, for all groups, paired with complementary gestures across groups for intuitive interaction.

Using reversible, complementary gestures (e.g., swipe left/right for "previous/next") to enhance learnability and recall reduces cognitive load. This reflects 'Ability', 'Accountability', and 'Transparency' according to the ABD framework [5, 6].

Audio Feedback: Participants noted that implicit feedback from audio changes (e.g., play/pause) often sufficed. For less obvious commands, explicit audio cues were proposed, such as ascending/descending pitch sequences to indicate session start/end. Subtle, affirming sounds like a soft "pling" were preferred for actions such as liking a song.

This shows that incorporating clear, unobtrusive sound cues can balance clarity and recall. Exploring earcons for accessible, hierarchical feedback aligns with the ABD principles 'Accountability' and 'Transparency' [5, 6].

Speech Feedback: Speech feedback was suggested for commands where auditory changes weren't apparent.

Designers can use speech for high-density, abstract, or

time-sensitive feedback, and offer user customization (e.g., voice tone, speed) to ensure inclusion. This aligns with all ABD principles [5, 6].

Visual Feedback: Group Cooking proposed minimizing visual distractions by relying on other modalities (e.g., audio, tactile). For example, tactile cues like temperature variations in slippers reinforced selections. Group Gym envisioned a compact, gesture-activated visual interface with eye-tracking for hands-free exploration.

This points designers to reflect on the use of visual feedback, choosing it only when needed and integrate multiple modalities for flexibility. This supports ‘Ability’ and ‘Adaptation’ [5, 6].

Haptic Feedback: Pressure or temperature changes, was integrated to supplement other modalities. Groups used tactile signals to convey additional information, such as temporal fluctuations or discrete sensations (e.g., hot/cold). However, haptics were primarily employed as a supporting rather than a standalone modality.

Designers can utilize haptic feedback sparingly for time-sensitive or private notifications, and enable frequency adjustments to balance reinforcement and energy efficiency. This reflects the ‘Adaptation’ principle [5, 6].

4.3 The Concept Proposal

Next, we present the proposed concept, developed by combining the findings and considerations outlined in previous sections with insights from prior research. Through the design choices made during the conceptualization and prototyping stages, we hypothesize that this concept represents one possible approach to improving the usability and accessibility of ASPs for users experiencing SIIs.

The proposal includes a multimodal watch interface with visual, audio, speech, and haptic feedback to support engagement under SIIs. The system offers two interaction modes: *Same-Side Interaction* and *Opposite-Side Interaction*. Same-side, ideal for one-handed use, combines a watch and an optional sensor-embedded ring for precise input (see Fig. 1, upper left, [II] and [III]), with both devices using embedded IMUs for gesture and tilt detection. Opposite-side interaction involves the free hand alongside the watch and relies solely on the watch for input (see Fig. 1, upper left, [I]), catering to users who prefer or need both hands. Users can interact with the devices standalone or as a pseudo-remote for a streaming device. The descriptions and images here assume the watch is worn on the left hand.

This multimodal watch interface hosts two interactive tiles: the ‘Wall Tile’ (see Fig. 1, up and center) for browsing curated content collections, and the ‘Play Tile’ (see Fig. 1, upper right) for managing the current listening session. These tiles are visualised to act as ‘two sides of a coin’, allowing quick switching between them.

The ‘Wall Tile’ organizes collections (songs, playlists, albums curated by the user) in two circular rings (inner: up to five, outer: up to seven), with a non-interactive anchor at 9 o’clock showing playback status. The gestures and the gesture-interaction mappings designed around this tile concern broader navigation and selection. Each gesture initiates a distinct response from the interface, such as a visual

cue for a new recommendation queue, audible feedback confirming the success of an action, or haptic vibrations indicating transitions between sections.

The ‘Play Tile’ displays track metadata, cover art (doubling as a dynamic timeline), and a volume control arc. Users can perform auditory controls such as play/pause, skipping tracks, or altering volume here. The Play/Pause icon shifts to functions like Skip, Fast-Forward, or Reverse via gestures and also serves as a cursor for volume adjustments. For this tile, gestures designed involve hand movements such as single squeezes, rotating the wrist, and other fine motor actions like tapping and flicking. Each action is accompanied by specific user feedback, including visual changes in the cursor icon, auditory confirmations, or tactile responses (e.g., haptic feedback). For instance, rotating the wrist adjusts the volume along a tilt-based axis, rotating the forearm refreshes the content queue, while a single squeeze can activate or deactivate cursor mobility. These feedback mechanisms ensure users receive clear confirmation of their interactions and enhance the overall usability of the system.

A centrally located cursor, based on the ObjectPoint model [19], supports tilt-based same-side interaction, and we introduce “magnetic” properties for snapping to actionable sectors. We also introduce haptic feedback from embedded actuators, along with audio, speech cues to help users navigate effectively, even with limited visual attention.

The concept designates a triple-pinch gesture by the watch hand as the delimiter gesture. This activates the watch and sensors to interpret subsequent gesture-actions. An example interaction sequence utilizing same-side interaction is demonstrated in Fig. 1.

A companion smartphone interface allows users to personalize the experience to complement their own abilities and needs. Users can curate Wall Tile content, pre-specifying playlists and albums to match their preferences. They can optimize the tile layouts and gesture recognition by selecting the preferred watch-wearing hand and choose between same-side or opposite-side interaction modes, which adjust device pairing and sleep mode settings. Feedback customization options conceptualised include haptic feedback frequency, selecting from three voice accents, and choosing one of five speech feedback speeds, ensuring a flexible and accessible interface.

4.4 Findings and Implications for Kangaroo Care

We recruited participants from a pool of 25 parents (mothers) who had experienced prolonged visits (average ten weeks) at a neonatal care unit; this included both intensive care (average two weeks, typically less than one week) and family-type rooms. We conducted eight interviews, received additional comments, and collected 14 completed questionnaires using the 5-point Likert-scale. All reported having used kangaroo care to a very large degree, and primarily in a reclined sitting position, and all had experienced sleep disorders during this time.

According to the interviews, the two main factors that disrupted sleep or rest were related to stress, and to necessary nursing, such as breastfeeding, nasogastric feeding, breast pumping, and similar recurring activities, confirmed

Figure 1. *Upper Row*—Left: Proposed devices. Opposite-side interaction mode uses only a watch [I], while same-side interaction pairs a ring [II] with a watch [III]. Center: The 'Wall Tile' on the watch displays collections A1–5 (inner circle) and B1–7 (outer circle), with a non-interactive pink sector at 9 o'clock. The cursor navigates between collections. Right: 'Play Tile' shows audio content, with cover art doubling as a timeline and an arc indicating volume. The central cursor-icon cycles through Reverse, Previous, Play/Pause, Next, and Fast-Forward. *Lower Row*: A visual depiction of the concept in practice: via an example interaction flow of a user engaging with our concept and utilizing same-side interaction mode.

in the questionnaire (mean=4.6). Less pronounced but still important factors were light and sound pollution, and unscheduled visits from nurses. In the questionnaire, the medical equipment was considered to be disturbing for the parent (mean=3.9), but less so for the child (mean=3.0). One coping strategy against noise that several mentioned in the interview was using an ASP, although the questionnaire showed that they only listen slightly above 'neither often nor seldom' (mean=3.1). Most reported that they needed to pause the playback very often, and a majority that it was difficult to control the device. In addition, several mentioned that eyemasks were used to reduce visual impressions.

5. DISCUSSION

5.1 Device Choices and Interaction Styles

The decision to not develop custom hardware for the on-body artefact aligns with the ABD principle 'Commodity' [5, 6]. Leveraging the watch, a widely available technology, makes the product available for a broader range of users. The inclusion of same-side and opposite-side interaction modes invokes both the proposed design considerations regarding artefact form, and the principle of 'Adaptation' in the ABD framework. This design choice enables users

to choose between parallel interaction styles based on their situational needs and abilities [5, 6].

The Wall Tile interface demonstrates how a thoughtful layout can improve usability by balancing access to information with reduced visual clutter. Building on circular menus and tilt-based selection accuracy [19], its design addresses the wrist's uneven range of motion by making the 9 o'clock sector non-interactive—a key area of high error for left-handed wearers. This adaptation is hypothesised to better support user interactions when constrained by SIIs, and improve interaction accuracy in such contexts.

Unlike ObjectPoint's freeform cursor movement, we hypothesised the "sticky" model will improve precision and stability. By incorporating multimodal feedback, such as tactile and audio cues, this design also builds on recommendation to enable eyes-free, wrist-only interactions [19].

This proposal uses a gyroscope based on a model which represents hand and arm movements as rotational gestures around joints like the wrist, elbow and shoulder [29], also explored in the Wrist-as-a-Joystick concept [20]. Gyroscopes offer high accuracy in detecting multi-axis rotations, making them ideal for tracking short-duration gestures, compared to accelerometers that are prone to noise or magnetometers that are unreliable in dynamic environments.

Additionally, the gyroscope's ability to recognize gesture patterns with low computational cost reduces energy consumption and eliminates the need for sensor fusion [29], contributing to a more sustainable design.

The triple-pinch was selected as the delimiter gesture for its ease of performance, low risk of accidental activation, minimal movement requirements, and discreetness. It reliably meets criteria for same-side interaction-friendly delimiters [30] and is detectable via gyroscopic data. While their top recommendation, the doubleRotate (Flick Wrist), was considered, its inward/outward variations made it more suitable as complementary gestures for additional actions.

5.2 Implications for Kangaroo Care

The experiences and circumstances of the participants are highly individual and distinct compared to those of parents with full-term babies. As anticipated, many participants highlighted how their mobility was significantly limited due to the need to remain stationary, constrained by the medical equipment cables connected to their bodies, infants, and surrounding furniture. A few still considered that interacting with a mobile phone was unproblematic, but this may either correspond to a very limited use, due to the circumstances, or to using the phone without actually interacting much.

It is beyond reasonable doubt that the light and sound environment in neonatal care units are a stressor to the parents. However, participating mothers report that their main concerns relate to nursing routines; in the interview, they commonly mention that nursing routines are very frequent, up to several times per hour, which implies that these are also the main cause of ASP disruptions. From the questionnaire and interview results, we speculate that these factors are interdependent in terms of being disruptive to sleep and rest, and their combined effect is detrimental. A possible, although small, improvement could therefore be to ease navigation, especially in effortlessly pausing and resuming play by gestures.

Compared to the design concepts presented, the case of kangaroo care would entail a suitable subset of involved body parts and gestures. Arm, torso and head movements are typically restricted, while leg and finger movements are more attainable. Similarly, voice input, as well as feedback in the auditory or haptic domain, are impacted by the low sensory stimulation requirement. Simpler visual feedback could however possibly be part of a design solution.

6. CONCLUSION

This study highlights the impact of situationally-induced impairments on a user's capability to navigate and engage with audio streaming platforms, and the subsequent accessibility challenges they face. Findings from interviews and workshops indicate that traditional ASP interfaces, which are visually intensive and screen-based, often fail to accommodate SIIs and their impact on user abilities. This study advocates for the principles of Ability-Based Design, and proposes considerations for designing more accessible gesture-based interactions and multimodal feedback. We

also present a concept incorporating gesture-based, multi-modal interfaces, and hypothesize how it could provide an avenue for supporting more adaptable and accessible audio interactions for users experiencing SIIs.

While promising, further testing is recommended to validate this conceptual approach and its design choices in a broader range of scenarios and practical settings. Based on our findings, we suggest that the design concept, initially conceived for general users, could also benefit parents in kangaroo care situations, where movement restrictions and the need for a low-sensory environment impact interactions with audio-playing devices. This extreme use case further supports the validity and applicability of the solution.

Future work should include physical prototyping, task-based testing, exploring the role of sound feedback strategies that are adaptive to different situations—encountered, for instance, by parents in kangaroo care. Future work should also involve exploring accessibility for users with a variation of situationally-induced impairments to ensure equitable access for all.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank all the participants for their invaluable contributions to this study. The authors would also like to thank Arjun Menon and Christopher Swanson for their advice and support.

References

- [1] D. Hesmondhalgh, "Is music streaming bad for musicians? Problems of evidence and argument," *New Media & Society*, vol. 23, no. 12, pp. 3593–3615, 2020.
- [2] A. Li, A. Wang, Z. Nazari, P. Chandar, and B. Carterette, "Do podcasts and music compete with one another? Understanding users' audio streaming habits," in *Proceedings of The Web Conference 2020*, ser. WWW '20, ACM, 2020, pp. 1920–1931.
- [3] J. O. Wobbrock, "Situationally-induced impairments and disabilities," in *Web Accessibility*. Springer London, 2019, pp. 59–92.
- [4] A. Jefferies, "Kangaroo care for the preterm infant and family," *Paediatrics & Child Health*, vol. 17, no. 3, pp. 141–143, 2012.
- [5] J. O. Wobbrock, S. K. Kane, K. Z. Gajos, S. Harada, and J. Froehlich, "Ability-based design: Concept, principles and examples," *ACM Transactions on Accessible Computing*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 1–27, 2011.
- [6] J. O. Wobbrock, K. Z. Gajos, S. K. Kane, and G. C. Vanderheiden, "Ability-based design," *Communications of the ACM*, vol. 61, no. 6, pp. 62–71, 2018.
- [7] A. Abdolrahmani, R. Kuber, and A. Hurst, "An empirical investigation of the situationally-induced impairments experienced by blind mobile device users," in *Proceedings of the 13th International Web for All Conference*, ser. W4A'16, ACM, 2016.

- [8] A. Ng, S. A. Brewster, and J. H. Williamson, "Investigating the effects of encumbrance on one- and two-handed interactions with mobile devices," in *Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, ser. CHI '14, ACM, 2014, pp. 1981–1990.
- [9] M. Naftali and L. Findlater, "Accessibility in context: Understanding the truly mobile experience of smartphone users with motor impairments," in *Proceedings of the 16th international ACM SIGACCESS Conference on Computers & Accessibility - ASSETS'14*, ACM Press, 2014, pp. 209–216.
- [10] A. Mariakakis, M. Goel, M. T. I. Aumi, S. N. Patel, and J. O. Wobbrock, "Switchback: Using focus and saccade tracking to guide users' attention for mobile task resumption," in *Proceedings of the 33rd Annual ACM Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, ser. CHI '15, ACM, 2015, pp. 2953–2962.
- [11] L. Fridman, B. Reimer, B. Mehler, and W. T. Freeman, "Cognitive load estimation in the wild," in *Proceedings of the 2018 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, ser. CHI '18, ACM, 2018, pp. 1–9.
- [12] G. C. Vanderheiden, "Universal design and assistive technology in communication and information technologies: Alternatives or complements?" *Assistive Technology*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 29–36, 1998.
- [13] S. Harper, "Is there design-for-all?" *Universal Access in the Information Society*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 111–113, 2007.
- [14] S. K. Kane, J. P. Bigham, and J. O. Wobbrock, "Slide rule: Making mobile touch screens accessible to blind people using multi-touch interaction techniques," in *Proceedings of the 10th international ACM SIGACCESS Conference on Computers and Accessibility*, ser. ASSETS'08, ACM, 2008, pp. 73–80.
- [15] R.-D. Vatavu, "Gesture-based interaction," in *Handbook of Human Computer Interaction*. Springer International Publishing, 2023, pp. 1–47.
- [16] M. B. Hoy, "Alexa, Siri, Cortana, and more: An introduction to voice assistants," *Medical Reference Services Quarterly*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 81–88, 2018.
- [17] Z. Ren, J. Meng, and J. Yuan, "Depth camera based hand gesture recognition and its applications in human-computer-interaction," in *2011 8th International Conference on Information, Communications & Signal Processing*, IEEE, 2011, pp. 1–5.
- [18] T. Vuletic *et al.*, "Systematic literature review of hand gestures used in human computer interaction interfaces," *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, vol. 129, pp. 74–94, 2019.
- [19] A. Guo and T. Paek, "Exploring tilt for no-touch, wrist-only interactions on smartwatches," in *Proceedings of the 18th International Conference on Human-Computer Interaction with Mobile Devices and Services*, ser. MobileHCI '16, ACM, 2016.
- [20] J. Gong, X.-D. Yang, and P. Irani, "Wristwhirl: One-handed continuous smartwatch input using wrist gestures," in *Proceedings of the 29th Annual Symposium on User Interface Software and Technology*, ser. UIST '16, ACM, 2016, pp. 861–872.
- [21] M. Rahman, S. Gustafson, P. Irani, and S. Subramanian, "Tilt techniques: Investigating the dexterity of wrist-based input," in *Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, ser. CHI '09, ACM, 2009.
- [22] R. Xiao, G. Laput, and C. Harrison, "Expanding the input expressivity of smartwatches with mechanical pan, twist, tilt and click," in *Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, ser. CHI '14, ACM, 2014.
- [23] H.-S. Yeo, J. Lee, A. Bianchi, and A. Quigley, "Side-tap & slingshot gestures on unmodified smartwatches," in *Proceedings of the 29th Annual Symposium on User Interface Software and Technology*, ser. UIST '16, ACM, 2016, pp. 189–190.
- [24] N. K. Dim, C. Silpasuwanchai, S. Sarcar, and X. Ren, "Designing mid-air TV gestures for blind people using user- and choice-based elicitation approaches," in *Proceedings of the 2016 ACM Conference on Designing Interactive Systems*, ACM, 2016, pp. 204–214.
- [25] R.-D. Vatavu, "User-defined gestures for free-hand tv control," in *Proceedings of the 10th European Conference on Interactive TV and Video*, ser. EuroITV '12, ACM, 2012, pp. 45–48.
- [26] D. Wilde, A. Vallgård, and O. Tomico, "Embodied design ideation methods: Analysing the power of estrangement," in *Proceedings of the 2017 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, ACM, 2017, pp. 5158–5170.
- [27] A. Moen *et al.*, *European standards of care for newborn health: Core principles of NICU design to promote family-centred care*, EFCNI, 2018.
- [28] S. Villarreal-Narvaez, A. Sluÿters, J. Vanderdonckt, and R.-D. Vatavu, "Brave New GES World: A systematic literature review of gestures and referents in gesture elicitation studies," *ACM Computing Surveys*, vol. 56, no. 5, pp. 1–55, 2024.
- [29] P. Khanna *et al.*, "Accesswear: Making smartphone applications accessible to blind users," in *Proceedings of the 29th Annual International Conference on Mobile Computing and Networking*, ser. ACM MobiCom '23, ACM, 2023.
- [30] F. Kerber, P. Schardt, and M. Löchtefeld, "Wristotate: A personalized motion gesture delimiter for wrist-worn devices," in *Proceedings of the 14th International Conference on Mobile and Ubiquitous Multimedia*, ser. MUM '15, ACM, 2015, pp. 218–222.

A Scoping Review of Emerging AI Technologies in Mental Health Care: Towards Personalized Music Therapy

Natália Santos

Faculty of Engineering, University of Porto
up202100737@fe.up.pt

Gilberto Bernardes

INESC TEC, Faculty of Engineering,
University of Porto
gba@fe.up.pt

ABSTRACT

Music therapy has emerged as a promising approach to support various mental health conditions, offering non-pharmacological therapies with evidence of improved well-being. Rapid advancements in artificial intelligence (AI) have recently opened new possibilities for ‘personalized’ musical interventions in mental health care. This article explores the application of AI in the context of mental health, focusing on the use of machine learning (ML), deep learning (DL), and generative music (GM) to personalize musical interventions. The methodology included a scoping review in the Scopus and PubMed databases, using keywords denoting emerging AI technologies, music-related contexts, and application domains within mental health and well-being. Identified research lines encompass the analysis and generation of emotional patterns in music using ML, DL, and GM techniques to create musical experiences adapted to user needs. The results highlight that these technologies effectively promote emotional and cognitive well-being, enabling personalized interventions that expand mental health therapies.

1. INTRODUCTION

Music as a form of therapy is a historical practice, evidenced by historical records dating back to various ancient cultures, highlighting its healing properties [1]. The relationship between music and mental health has garnered increasing interest in recent decades and has been the subject of extensive research [2]. Music therapy (MT), at the intersection of medicine and music, has emerged in recent years as a promising approach to treating a variety of pathological conditions, including anxiety, depression, substance abuse, Alzheimer’s, eating disorders, sleep disorders, Autism Spectrum Disorder, Down Syndrome, among others [3–5]. However, the demands of such mental pathologies and the subjective nature of the musical experience present challenges in formulating universally effective interventions [2]. Advancements in artificial intelligence (AI) have directed attention to the field of machine learning (ML) and, more recently, deep learning (DL),

which has been established as a robust and versatile computational tool. Consequently, in recent years, this tool has emerged as a valuable resource in processing audio signals and music [6].

ML is a subset of AI that encompasses systems that learn patterns from data and make predictions or decisions without explicit programming, differing from classical statistical methods that rely on predefined equations and fixed models. Instead, ML algorithms automatically adjust their parameters based on data patterns, enhancing scalability and adaptability [7, 8]. DL, a specialized subfield of ML, expands on these principles by utilizing artificial neural networks with multiple layers (deep neural networks) to model and extract complex features from large datasets [9].

ML and DL applied to music encompasses two main research lines within music information retrieval (MIR) – focusing on extracting information from music data for various applications, such as genre classification, music recommendation, instrument recognition, sound source separation, sung voice detection, emotions recognition, and transcription – and generative music (GM) – related to the automatic creation of musical content [5, 6, 10–12].

The discussion around ML and DL applied to music has raised questions about the potential impact of this tool on MT, as it can be resourceful in detecting emotional responses to sound and music and in generating automatic music adapted to the particularities of each individual [6, 13]. Thus, it can become a complement to mental health professionals and a valuable asset to support therapists and patients, adding value to traditional treatments [5, 6, 14]. This article explores the applications of ML and DL technologies for music processing in mental health by reviewing existing studies across both domains.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 detailed the methods adopted to retrieve the relevant articles from the literature. Section 3 explores the connection between artificial intelligence and music, emphasizing the use of ML and DL. Section 4 focuses on the relationship between ML, DL, and GM in personalizing music therapy, presenting a new perspective on mental health treatments.

2. METHODOLOGY

The methodology adopted for our scoping review can be divided into three distinct stages. The first stage involved identifying keywords relevant to the search in scientific

Copyright: © 2025 Natália Santos et al. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15032577>

repositories (Section 2.1). The second stage focused on establishing methods for filtering the retrieved articles (Section 2.2). Finally, the third stage analyzed emerging research lines within the scoped domains (Section 2.3).

2.1 Selection and Keywords Refinement

To retrieve relevant literature for the scoping review, we defined three keyword sets based on the primary study topics. First, we considered two main technologies: ('machine learning' OR 'deep learning'). Second, we defined two music-related contexts: ('Music' OR 'Music Therapy'). Third, we established three application domains: ('Therapy' OR 'Mental Health' OR 'Mindfulness'). After retrieving the results, we observed a significant incidence of certain musical contexts, which were not initially included in the keywords set and could hinder important results: 'generative music,' 'automatic music generation,' and 'music recommendation,' 'emotion-based music recommendation' and 'emotion-integrated music recommendation.'

The final set of threefold keyword sets were combined, resulting in the following logical expression: (deep learning OR machine learning) AND (music OR music therapy OR generative music OR automatic music generation OR music recommendation OR emotion-based music recommendation OR emotion integrated music recommendation) AND (therapy OR mental health OR mindfulness).

2.2 Search and Screening Process

The search was conducted in two leading platforms: PubMed, due to its focus on the health field, and Scopus, chosen for its extensive coverage of reliable citations and well-known databases such as Elsevier, Springer Nature, Wiley-Blackwell, Taylor & Francis, SAGE Publications, Oxford University Press, Cambridge University Press, arXiv, DOAJ, SciELO, IEEE, ACM, European Patent Office (EPO) and United States Patent and Trademark Office (USPTO). The search was performed in October 2024, targeting articles published between January 2000 and October 2024.

Our initial search yielded 169 articles (114 in PubMed and 55 in Scopus). After removing 37 duplicates, 132 articles were considered. In the first screening stage, the articles' titles, abstracts, keywords, and conclusions were manually reviewed, excluding those whose primary focus was not on the application of ML or GM in mental health. As a result, 96 studies were excluded, leaving 36 studies eligible for further analysis.

In the final stage, the full texts of the selected studies were reviewed, from which nineteen articles were additionally excluded due to ($n = 13$) [do not focus directly on mental health or therapy] and ($n = 6$) [not having enough data on the ML technologies used]. After these steps, a total of 17 studies were included in the final analysis.

2.3 Organization and Categorization Process

From the final set of articles, we categorized them into two thematic research lines, summarized in Table 1. 1) The

correlation between emotions and music, specifically the modulation of listeners' emotional states and music emotion recognition and 2) the intersection of machine learning (ML), generative music (GM), and the personalization of music therapy.

The first line, discussed in Section 3, explores the application of ML and DL models to understanding emotions in music. This theme is examined from two perspectives: 1) the modulation of emotional responses in users by mapping physiological measurements to personalized recommendations, and 2) the automatic recognition and generation of music with controlled emotional content. The second line, covered in Section 4, delves into the interplay between ML, GM, and the personalization of music therapy, emphasizing a novel paradigm for mental health treatment.

3. DEEPENING THE UNDERSTANDING OF EMOTIONS AND MUSIC

Music has long been recognized as a powerful force that can profoundly affect a person's emotions and mental state [6, 22]. However, understanding how music interacts with the human brain and influences mental health is a complex and constantly evolving field [2]. The human brain's response to music is multifaceted and involves a complex network of neural processes. Since the early days of neuroscience, researchers have been interested in musical perception and its implications for cognition and emotion. Music comprises various elements, including harmony, rhythm, melody, timbre, and dynamics. Each of these elements uniquely influences how music is perceived and experienced emotionally. For example, musical rhythms can modulate the autonomic nervous system, affecting heart rate, blood pressure, and even breathing [2, 6].

Recent advances in DL technologies applied to music offer innovative approaches to understanding and analyzing music. Unlike traditional techniques of musical analysis, which often rely on simplified categorizations of musical elements, such as genre or style, DL can extract complex, non-linear patterns from music that may influence a person's emotional response. For instance, DL models can identify subtle variations in tempo, harmonic progressions, and dynamic shifts that are not easily captured by traditional linear statistical methods. These patterns may include syncopation, polyphonic textures, or microtonal variations, which can evoke specific emotional states such as calmness or tension [5, 6, 29]. This capability is further enhanced by the ability of DL to identify emotional features based on large datasets where human listeners have reported emotional responses to musical elements. For example, a DL model could learn associations between minor chord progressions and feelings of sadness or rapid tempo fluctuations with excitement based on datasets such as the EmoMusic Database or the DEAM dataset [16, 27, 30]. What makes DL particularly unique in this context is its capacity to simultaneously process multiple layers of musical information (e.g., melody, harmony, rhythm, and timbre) in a hierarchical manner, uncovering interactions between features that classical statistical approaches might overlook. This multi-layered analysis can be especially valu-

Research Line	Technologies	Tasks	Condition or Study Population	References
Modulating Listeners' Emotions	Machine Learning / Deep Learning	Biophysical measurements	Depression	[15] (EEG)
			Anxiety	[15] (EEG), [16] (GSR, HR)
	Listener's emotional response		Stress	[17] (EEG), [16] (GSR, HR)
			General Population	[18] (GSR), [19] (EDA, BVP, ST) [15] (EEG)
			Anxiety	[20], [21]
			Depression	[21]
Music Emotion Recognition	Machine Learning / Deep Learning	Listener's emotional response	General Population	[14]
			Dementia patients	[22]
Personalized Music Therapy	Machine Learning / Deep Learning / Generative Music	Listener's emotional response	ASD patients	[24], [25]
			Stress	[26], [27]
	Biophysical measurements		General Population	[5]
			Stress	[28] (HR, GSR)

Table 1. Categorization of the reviewed articles according to three main research lines. The table presents articles grouped into the areas of modulating listeners' emotions through music, music emotion recognition using ML techniques, and personalized music therapy. For each research line, the table lists the technologies used, the tasks analyzed, the studied populations or conditions, and the relevant references associated with each study. Biophysical measurements are indicated when adopted: electroencephalogram (EEG), heart rate (HR), galvanic skin response (GSR), electrodermal activity (EDA), blood volume pulse (BVP), and skin temperature (ST).

able in personalized music therapy, where tailoring music to an individual's emotional state requires a nuanced understanding of how complex musical patterns influence affective responses [5, 6, 29].

3.1 Understanding and Modulating Listeners' Emotional State

Several studies have explored ML combined with biophysical measurements and psychological assessments to create personalized musical systems that induce emotions and promote emotional well-being. These studies use various approaches to map listeners' emotional responses and generate music tailored to evoke desired emotional states, such as mindfulness, calmness, and relief from stress, fear, and anxiety.

Williams et al. [18] developed a real-time generative music system synchronized with the listener's galvanic skin response (GSR), using ML to create emotionally congruent compositions, focusing on emotional regulation and mindfulness promotion. Initially, a musical corpus was generated using Hidden Markov Models (HMM) and labeled with emotional tags based on perceptual questionnaires. Musical features were extracted to train a supervised learning algorithm with listeners' emotional responses. During the experimental phase, participants listened to the compositions generated while their physiological responses were monitored through GSR, followed by self-reported emotional assessments through questionnaires. The analysis revealed a correlation between the GSR readings and the perceived emotions, indicating that the generated music consistently influenced the listeners' emotional states. The system employed biofeedback as a control signal to adjust the generation of new compositions tailored to the listener's emotional state. The findings suggest promising applications in music therapy, mindfulness, and automated soundtrack generation, highlighting the potential of ML-based approaches for personalized emotional interventions.

Building on the work mentioned above, Williams et al. [14] trained a ML system to improve mental health by inducing affective states. This study focused on detecting emotions in music and creating musical sequences based on the probability that specific emotional states occurred in the listener. The results showed that listeners could easily discriminate between emotional states in the musical sequences and that the use of synthesized timbres was effective, indicating that this approach could be beneficial in therapeutic contexts.

Three studies [19–21] have explored the use of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and ML to analyze listeners' emotional responses and improve the effectiveness of music as a therapeutic tool. Rahman et al. [19] employed CNNs to classify musical genres and associated emotions, achieving high accuracy (99.2% for genre classification and 98.5% for emotion classification). The results emphasize the importance of physiological signals such as electrodermal activity (EDA), blood volume pulse (BVP), and skin temperature (ST) in identifying emotions triggered by music. They suggested the use of genetic algorithms to improve the accuracy of classification.

Wang et al. [20] used DL (CNNs and autoencoders) to process emotional and behavioral data, identifying patterns between music and emotional responses. They proposed personalized music recommendations to improve psychological well-being by reducing anxiety, increasing mental energy, and improving resilience. The results highlighted the potential of DL to integrate empirical data with psychological theories for personalized therapeutic and educational interventions. Joy et al. [21] utilized DL (namely, CNNs) in a mood recognition system, combining facial recognition and musical features (rhythm, melody) to create personalized playlists based on the user's emotional state. They show that CNNs improve the accuracy of music recommendations, contributing to emotional regulation and the treatment of conditions such as depression and anxiety.

Studies [31] [15] and [17] align in their exploration of EEG signals to recognize emotions and offer personalized musical interventions. Sanker et al. [31] proposed a music recommendation system utilizing Russell's valence-arousal model of emotions [32], achieving high accuracy in emotional classification (93.2% for valence and 95.3% for arousal). The research suggested improvements such as the integration of real-time EEG and the development of audio-focused databases. Complementarily, [15] reports advances in affective brain-computer music interfaces (aBCMI), which adjusts real-time music based on EEG signals. Using ML algorithms such as SVM, k-NN, and Random Forest, this system was designed to interpret and respond appropriately to users' emotional states, highlighting therapeutic applications for conditions such as depression and anxiety. Both studies underscore the potential of combining EEG and ML techniques to create personalized music for emotional regulation and well-being, suggesting that real-time integration could further enhance these interventions. In turn, study [17] proposed a system using EEG data and ML to detect stress levels and recommend personalized music to alleviate it. Based on K-Means and SVM, the system classified stress into three levels (low, medium, and high) with 95% accuracy. This approach personalized musical recommendations based on the detected stress level, adjusting song tempos to promote emotional well-being.

Parallel to this, Guo et al. [16] focused on an application called EMO-Music, which utilizes physiological signals from wearable devices, such as heart rate and skin conductance, to identify the user's emotional state and recommend therapeutic music. By employing the DL BERT model for data analysis of these physiological metrics, the system outperformed traditional methods in accuracy, demonstrating that this type of technology can effectively address conditions such as stress and anxiety, enhancing the personalization of therapeutic experiences.

These studies demonstrate the significant potential of ML/DL in creating personalized musical systems to induce specific emotions and promote well-being. Combining biophysical measurements, such as EEG, GSR, BVP, and ST, with ML offers a promising approach to developing more effective and targeted interventions, especially in therapeutic contexts. Using DL models to detect and classify emotions and recommend personalized music is a valuable tool for promoting mental health and emotional regulation.

3.2 From Analysis to Prediction: ML and GM in Musical Emotional Recognition

While some studies applying ML and GM aim to understand music by analyzing the listener's emotional responses, others focus on examining the emotional nature of music itself to predict which emotions it may evoke in listeners. Both approaches aim to use music therapeutically, but they follow opposite processes, creating a complementary field of research.

Emotion-driven music recommendations have gained attention in recent studies, including the work of Panwar

et al. [22], which emphasizes the use of social media for enhancing emotional models. By integrating information from platforms like Twitter, the authors sought to enrich the emotional model, offering a more contextualized analysis of listeners' emotions in different regions. The effectiveness of the model, combining CNN and recurrent neural networks (RNN), highlighted not only the ability to identify emotions in music but also suggested future applications, such as inducing specific emotions through music, particularly in a therapeutic context.

Many of the recent advances in MER, such as those presented by this study, can be seen as a continuation of the initial efforts of Panwar et al. [22] with greater sophistication in analysis and therapeutic context. Adopting more advanced technology, such as DL, increased the accuracy of emotional recognition and expanded therapeutic possibilities, providing a better adaptation of musical interventions to an individual's emotional state. Additionally, the study highlights the importance of incorporating contextual and physiological data to enhance the precision of emotion recognition, offering a more robust framework for personalized music interventions, particularly in mental health therapies.

On the other hand, the personalization of music therapy has also become a key objective of other studies applying ML to support the treatment of specific conditions, such as dementia. Nunes et al. [23] use ML to classify music genres and support personalized therapy for dementia patients. The study demonstrated that personalized playlists could improve quality of life and reduce neuropsychiatric symptoms by classifying music based on its association with positive emotional memories, particularly those from the patients' youth. The model's accuracy, exceeding 83%, reinforces the viability of such an approach but also underscores the need for therapist intervention to adjust musical choices based on individual patients' emotional responses. While ML can automate music classification and recommendation, the therapist's presence remains essential to maximize the therapy's effectiveness.

These innovative approaches in ML, DL, and music studies highlight the effectiveness of emotion recognition and recommendation techniques and open doors for using music as a therapeutic tool capable of inducing or regulating emotions precisely and personally. The combination of auditory, physiological, and social data, as observed in the various studies reviewed, offers new possibilities for personalizing music therapy, ensuring that interventions are more aligned with the emotional needs of patients, especially in therapeutic and well-being contexts. The ongoing integration of these approaches, with a focus on personalization and cultural context, reflects the transformative potential of ML in the field of music therapy and music emotion recognition.

4. MACHINE (DEEP) LEARNING, GENERATIVE MUSIC, AND PERSONALIZATION OF MUSIC THERAPY: A NEW PARADIGM IN MENTAL HEALTH

One of the most exciting promises of ML is the ability to personalize the musical experience for each person. Advanced algorithms can analyze a person's emotional and psychological profile, adapting the musical selection. Personalizing the musical experience involves adjusting this selection based on individual preferences, emotional state, and specific goals of each person. In the context of mental health, this approach can be powerful in creating tailor-made playlists aimed at relieving stress, promoting calmness, increasing motivation, or inducing feelings of happiness and well-being [5, 6, 14, 18].

DL algorithms use various techniques and computational models to analyze and understand music. It includes extracting musical features such as harmony, rhythm, melody, timbre, density, and others and identifying complex and subtle patterns that can influence a person's emotional response to music. Combined with an individual's emotional data and psychological profile, algorithms can generate highly personalized music recommendations tailored to their needs and specific preferences [5,6,29]. Studies have been developed to analyze how musical characteristics and parameters can influence individuals' musical experience and how GM can be an ally in creating personalized music. These studies can potentially revolutionize the fields of MT and psychology, offering new approaches to improving people's emotional and cognitive well-being.

4.1 Personalized Music and Mental Health: The Future of Music Therapy

The application of technologies such as ML and DL has proven promising in MT, allowing for greater personalization and effectiveness in therapeutic interventions. Raglio et al. [26] use decision trees to predict the efficacy of music therapy in promoting relaxation. Factors such as age, gender, education, musical training, and frequency of music listening were analyzed, and the model achieved 79% accuracy, identifying key variables such as initial relaxation levels and the combination of education and musical training. Furthermore, the study reinforced the relevance of ML-based methods, rather than DL, for identifying personalized predictive factors that maximize the therapeutic benefits of music.

Zhang et al. [24] focused on treating children with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) using DL-based interactive robots to improve musical perception and social interaction. The research employed gesture recognition and EEGs to assess the children's musical responses, achieving an average accuracy of 85%. These results highlight the role of music as a powerful therapeutic tool for promoting social skills and exploring the potential of technology in teaching and treating neurodevelopmental conditions. Santos et al. [25] introduced an GM application to capture the musical preferences of children with ASD. By allowing the children to manipulate musical parameters such as pitch, tempo, timbre, intensity, density, and per-

cussiveness to create personalized music. The study aimed to understand which musical elements were most effective for each individual. Although the technological approach differs from the interactive robots, both studies share the goal of personalizing music interventions. While the robot study focuses on social interaction and musical perception through gestures and physical responses, the generative app allows for a more individualized and exploratory musical creation, offering a way for the participants themselves to shape their therapeutic experience. These two studies, though distinct in the technology employed, converge on the importance of personalization and the child's active involvement in the therapeutic process.

Modran et al. [5] investigated how emotional and musical characteristics can predict the therapeutic effects of music through a multi-class neural network. Using a subset of the Million Dataset and techniques such as K-Fold cross validation, the model categorized emotions into four distinct groups, achieving an accuracy of over 94%. Furthermore, integrating attention mechanisms and contextual data contributed to a more refined recognition of music's emotional and therapeutic effects. They highlight gaps in previous research and propose an innovative solution to personalize music interventions according to each individual's emotional and musical profile, representing a significant advancement for music therapists and patients seeking personalized therapies.

Regarding stress reduction, two recent studies adopt DL to optimize the personalization of therapeutic music. Choi et al. [27] explored CNNs and Mel-scaled spectrograms to build optimized music datasets for relaxation. The model achieved an impressive accuracy of 98.7%, demonstrating that the music selected by the system was as effective as options validated by experts in reducing stress and promoting emotional well-being. This approach reduces the costs associated with the biological validation of playlists and expands the possibilities of creating more accessible and effective music interventions. Zhang [28] integrated emerging technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), big data, and mixed-density neural networks (MDNN) to monitor and reduce stress in university students. Wearable and environmental sensors collected real-time data – such as heart rate, skin conductivity, volume, and environmental temperature – and were processed through ML to enable immediate adjustments in therapeutic music to alleviate stress as detected. The approach emphasized the relevance of playlist personalization and demonstrated how combining music and technology can offer practical and dynamic solutions to enhance mental well-being.

The combined advancements from these studies strengthen the growing intersection between technology, music, and mental health. Integrating ML, DL, and emerging tools such as IoT and big data expands the capacity to create personalized interventions, maximizing the therapeutic effects of music. This evidence points to a promising future where music and technology unite to transform mental health approaches, promoting greater access and effectiveness for diverse populations and needs.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

This reviewed the intersection between MT and emerging AI technologies, focusing on ML, DL, and GM. It highlights current research lines on applying these technologies to transform the therapeutic experience, enabling highly personalized and effective interventions in the mental health field.

From this scoping review, two major lines of research emerged. The first examines musical emotions from a twofold perspective: modulation of listeners' emotional states in response to music, exploring the interplay between emotional, cognitive, and musical aspects, and application of ML, DL, and GM technologies to recognize and predict emotional patterns in musical contexts. The second research line highlights the potential of personalized music for mental health interventions by adapting musical contents to individual needs and enabling more effective therapeutic experiences. While ML and DL have contributed to a deeper understanding of emotional and cognitive interactions with music, GM has made it possible to create musical content tailored to the specific needs of each individual.

The studies analyzed show notable advances in identifying emotional patterns in music and the personalization of music recommendations based on biological, psychological, and contextual data. The evidence demonstrates the effectiveness of these technologies in promoting emotional and cognitive well-being and opens up new possibilities for the application of music in the treatment of a wide range of mental health conditions, ranging from emotional and cognitive disorders to more complex psychological disorders.

Although the results are encouraging, ethical, technical, and operational challenges must be addressed. The identified challenges point to the need for greater standardization in research protocols, given the use of divergent methods and metrics between studies, making direct comparisons difficult [6, 16–18, 31]. In addition, the limitation of small, demographically specific samples, such as autistic children [24, 25] or university students [28], compromises the generalizability of the results. Cultural gaps in understanding musical preferences and their emotional implications also highlight the importance of more inclusive and diverse approaches [23]. Another significant obstacle lies in oversimplifying human emotional responses through limited classifications, underestimating the complexity and dynamics of emotional states [5, 22].

From an ethical and technical point of view, the challenges related to the privacy and security of biometric data still require greater attention, especially in systems that use sensitive information, such as EEG and cardiac variation, to personalize therapies. The lack of validation in real clinical contexts also limits the applicability of technological solutions, which often remain confined to controlled environments or prototypes [18, 26]. Added to this is the lack of robust exploration into the cumulative and long-term impacts of GM and the reliance on subjective tools, such as questionnaires, to assess therapeutic effects [14, 15].

Furthermore, something concerning in the studies analyzed in the context of emotion detection is the tendency

to rely predominantly on objective measures such as EEG, GSR, BVP, and ST. While these biophysical signals can provide valuable insights, they risk neglecting the subjective experience of the individual. Emotional responses are inherently personal, and subjective assessments can offer critical perspectives on how emotions are felt and experienced. Over-reliance on objective data could lead to an exaggerated perception of the effects of music on mental health. Therefore, a balanced approach that integrates both subjective evaluations and objective measures is essential to capture a more holistic understanding of emotional states and their modulation through music therapy.

Emerging and underexplored areas offer ways to overcome these limitations and expand the therapeutic benefits of GM. Real-time dynamic adaptation, supported by immersive technologies such as virtual and augmented reality, is among the most promising fronts [16, 18, 24, 31]. Likewise, integrating multimodal stimuli – such as sonic, visual, and tactile – can further enrich therapeutic interventions. Future research should also explore the impact of underrepresented musical genres [24, 26], develop tools that simplify GM for therapists without technical training, and consider cultural and ethnographic nuances in individualizing interventions [29].

Other critical areas of research involve the use of advanced DL models to create music tailored to individual emotional states and psychological traits. Among these models are GANs, which use a generator and a discriminator to produce realistic, personalized music [33]. Probabilistic diffusion models, which start with random noise and refine the sound until detailed results are obtained, are also promising for music generation [34]. Transformer-based networks, capture long-term dependencies in musical sequences, generating more cohesive compositions. In addition, quantized variational autoencoders (VQ-VAE) create discretized representations of the music, facilitating the generation of new pieces with diversity and complexity [35]. StyleGAN, originally used for images [36], can be adapted to control stylistic aspects of music, such as rhythm and timbre, while multimodal approaches, such as CLIP, make it possible to generate music from emotional or psychological descriptions. The application of AI in longer therapeutic processes, with the ability to monitor and progressively adapt interventions based on emotional progress, also emerges as a relevant field that has yet to be investigated.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] M. H. Thaut, "Music as therapy in early history," *Progress in brain research*, vol. 217, pp. 143–158, 2015.
- [2] D. L. Bowling, "Biological principles for music and mental health," *Translational Psychiatry*, vol. 13, no. 1, 2023, 374.
- [3] J. H. Wakim, S. Smith, and C. Guinn, "The efficacy of music therapy," *Journal of perianesthesia nursing*, vol. 25, no. 4, pp. 226–232, 2010.

- [4] L. Gassner, M. Geretsegger, and J. Mayer-Ferbas, “Effectiveness of music therapy for autism spectrum disorder, dementia, depression, insomnia and schizophrenia: update of systematic reviews,” *European journal of public health*, vol. 32, no. 1, pp. 27–34, 2022.
- [5] H. A. Modran, T. Chamunorwa, D. Ursuțiu, C. Samoilă, and H. Hedeșiu, “Using deep learning to recognize therapeutic effects of music based on emotions,” *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 2, 2023, 986.
- [6] J. Liang, “Harmonizing minds and machines: survey on transformative power of machine learning in music,” *Frontiers in Neurorobotics*, vol. 17, 2023, 1267561.
- [7] N. Kühn, M. Goutier, R. Hirt, and G. Satzger, “Machine learning in artificial intelligence: Towards a common understanding,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2004.04686*, 2020.
- [8] G. M. d. M. Paixão, B. C. Santos, R. M. d. Araujo, M. H. Ribeiro, J. L. d. Moraes, and A. L. Ribeiro, “Machine learning na medicina: Revisão e aplicabilidade,” *Arquivos brasileiros de cardiologia*, vol. 118, pp. 95–102, 2022.
- [9] J.-P. Briot, G. Hadjeres, and F.-D. Pachet, “Deep learning techniques for music generation—a survey,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1709.01620*, 2017.
- [10] F.-F. Kuo, M.-F. Chiang, M.-K. Shan, and S.-Y. Lee, “Emotion-based music recommendation by association discovery from film music,” in *Proceedings of the 13th annual ACM international conference on Multimedia*, 2005, pp. 507–510.
- [11] J. Bevington and D. Knox, “Cognitive factors in generative music systems,” in *Proceedings of the 9th Audio Mostly: A Conference on Interaction With Sound*, 2014, pp. 1–8.
- [12] X. Wang and Y. Wang, “Improving content-based and hybrid music recommendation using deep learning,” in *Proceedings of the 22nd ACM international conference on Multimedia*, 2014, pp. 627–636.
- [13] M. Bhaumik, P. U. Attah, and F. Javed, “Emotion integrated music recommendation system using generative adversarial networks,” *SMU Data Science Review*, vol. 5, no. 3, 2021, 4.
- [14] D. Williams, V. J. Hodge, and C.-Y. Wu, “On the use of ai for generation of functional music to improve mental health,” *Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 3, 2020, 497864.
- [15] H. Glassman, D. Dwyer, N. John, D. Laesker, and M. So, “Affective brain-computer music interface in emotion regulation and neurofeedback: A research protocol,” *Undergraduate Research in Natural and Clinical Science and Technology Journal*, vol. 6, pp. 1–9, 2022.
- [16] H. Guo, J. Zhang, Y. Jiang, Y. Qi, S. Chen, Z. Chen, W. Lin, J. Cao, and S. hou Li, “Emo-music: Emotion recognition based music therapy with deep learning on physiological signals,” in *2024 IEEE First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence for Medicine, Health and Care (AIMHC)*. IEEE, 2024, pp. 10–13.
- [17] J. Patil, N. M. Ranjan, P. Dange, A. Patil, D. Salunke, and S. Borde, “Personalized stress mitigation through eeg based stress classification and music recommendation,” in *International Conference on Computing and Machine Learning*. Springer, 2024, pp. 181–191.
- [18] D. Williams, V. J. Hodge, L. Gega, D. Murphy, P. I. Cowling, and A. Drachen, “Ai and automatic music generation for mindfulness,” in *2019 AES International Conference on Immersive and Interactive Audio: Creating the Next Dimension of Sound Experience*. York, 2019.
- [19] J. S. Rahman, T. Gedeon, S. Caldwell, R. Jones, and Z. Jin, “Towards effective music therapy for mental health care using machine learning tools: human affective reasoning and music genres,” *Journal of Artificial Intelligence and Soft Computing Research*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 5–20, 2021.
- [20] T. Wang, Y. Zhao, and M. Yin, “Analysis and research on the influence of music on students’ mental health under the background of deep learning,” *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 13, 2022, 998451.
- [21] R. Joy, M. Thanka, J. Dhas, and E. Edwin, “Music mood based recognition system based on machine learning and deep learning,” *International Journal of Intelligent Systems and Applications in Engineering*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 904–911, 2023.
- [22] S. Panwar, P. Rad, K.-K. R. Choo, and M. Roopaei, “Are you emotional or depressed? learning about your emotional state from your music using machine learning,” *The Journal of Supercomputing*, vol. 75, pp. 2986–3009, 2019.
- [23] I. B. Nunes, M. A. de Santana, N. Charron, H. S. e. Silva, C. M. de Lima Simões, C. Lins, A. B. de Souza Sampaio, A. M. N. de Melo, T. C. V. da Silva, C. Tiodista *et al.*, “Automatic identification of preferred music genres: an exploratory machine learning approach to support personalized music therapy,” *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, pp. 1–17, 2024.
- [24] Y. Zhang, C. Zhang, L. Cheng, and M. Qi, “The use of deep learning-based gesture interactive robot in the treatment of autistic children under music perception education,” *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 13, 2022, 762701.
- [25] N. Santos, G. Bernardes, R. Cotta, N. Coelho, and A. Baganha, “Assessing musical preferences of children on the autistic spectrum: Implications for therapy,” *Sound and Music Computing*, Jul 2024.

- [26] A. Raglio, M. Imbriani, C. Imbriani, P. Baiardi, S. Manzoni, M. Gianotti, M. Castelli, L. Vanneschi, F. Vico, and L. Manzoni, “Machine learning techniques to predict the effectiveness of music therapy: A randomized controlled trial,” *Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine*, vol. 185, 2020, 105160.
- [27] S. Choi, J.-I. Park, C.-H. Hong, S.-G. Park, and S.-C. Park, “Accelerated construction of stress relief music datasets using cnn and the mel-scaled spectrogram,” *PLoS ONE*, vol. 19, no. 5, 2024, 0300607.
- [28] J. Zhang, “Iot-enabled musical therapy to alleviate physiological stress in college students using big data and mixed-density neural networks,” *Mobile Networks and Applications*, pp. 1–21, 2024.
- [29] L. Moysis, L. A. Iliadis, S. P. Sotiroudis, A. D. Boursianis, M. S. Papadopoulou, K.-I. D. Kokkinidis, C. Volos, P. Sarigiannidis, S. Nikolaidis, and S. K. Goudos, “Music deep learning: deep learning methods for music signal processing—a review of the state-of-the-art,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 17 031–17 052, 2023.
- [30] S. Shelke and M. Patil, “Exploring machine learning techniques for music emotion classification: A comprehensive review,” in *2024 11th International Conference on Computing for Sustainable Global Development (INDIACom)*. IEEE, 2024, pp. 1188–1195.
- [31] S. V. Sanker, N. B. R. S. Bilakanti, A. Thomas, V. P. Gopi, and P. Palanisamy, “Emotion-recognition-based music therapy system using electroencephalography signals,” in *Edge-of-Things in Personalized Healthcare Support Systems*. Elsevier, 2022, pp. 217–235.
- [32] J. A. Russell, “A circumplex model of affect.” *Journal of personality and social psychology*, vol. 39, no. 6, pp. 1161–1178, 1980.
- [33] J. Engel, K. K. Agrawal, S. Chen, I. Gulrajani, C. Donahue, and A. Roberts, “Gansynth: Adversarial neural audio synthesis,” 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1902.08710>
- [34] M. Plasser, S. Peter, and G. Widmer, “Discrete diffusion probabilistic models for symbolic music generation,” 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2305.09489>
- [35] S. Han, H. Ihm, and W. Lim, “Symbolic music loop generation with VQ-VAE,” *CoRR*, vol. abs/2111.07657, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2111.07657>
- [36] D. Jeong, S. Doh, and T. Kwon, “Träumerai: Dreaming music with stylegan,” 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2102.04680>

Sound Asleep: A study on the relationship between emotional state and sound preferences as sleep aid

Simon Hallak
KTH Royal Institute of Technology
shallak@kth.se

Abhishek Choubey
KTH Royal Institute of Technology
achoubey@kth.se

Sandra Pauletto
KTH Royal Institute of Technology
pauletto@kth.se

ABSTRACT

Sleep plays a vital role in our lives, yet many people experience sleep deprivation and sleep disorders that prevent them from getting adequate rest and being able to function well during the day. Not feeling emotionally well can be the cause of sleep deprivation. This study aims to investigate the relationship between emotional state and individual sound preferences to fall asleep. The study focuses on environmental sounds rather than music as the use of these sounds for sleep is under-explored. An online survey was conducted to assess whether people prefer different sounds to aid sleep depending on their emotional state. The results show that sounds such as Rain, Underwater sounds, and Singing Bowl sounds are preferred for negative emotional states. On the other hand, the sounds of Birds, Crickets, and Rain are selected more often for positive emotional states. Additionally, the paper describes the initial stages of a mobile app development that we are planning to use to implement the study's findings. The app asks the user for their emotional state and suggests to them three different sounds to regulate their emotional state and help them fall asleep.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sleep is one of the most essential aspects of life. We need sleep to perform our daily activities and maintain cognitive function and body health [1]. There are many reasons for sleep deprivation and sleep disorders. However, one of the causes is the individual's emotional state before falling asleep. [2]. Listening to music is effective in regulating emotion and reducing stress [3]. Many people also listen to sounds to help them fall asleep.

This study looks at the relationship between emotional state and how that might influence the sounds that one chooses to aid sleep. A survey was conducted to collect data from participants. The survey was constructed so that participants could rank different environmental sounds in terms of their preference when they imagined feeling a particular emotion before sleeping. Additionally, the paper proposes a prototype of a sleeping app that uses the data from the survey to recommend different sounds to the user

to aid sleep depending on the user's emotional state. The goal of the broader project is to develop a practical sound-based applications to help people regulate their emotional state and help them fall asleep.

2. BACKGROUND

2.1 Impact of Sleep Quality on Health

Sleep is essential for mental health, mood, cognitive function, heart, brain, and general physical health [1]. Insufficient sleep and untreated sleeping disorders are destructive to our health and well-being [1]. A systematic review [4] of 277 studies revealed that short sleep latencies, minimal awakenings, and no or few awakenings after sleep onset characterize good sleep quality. A sleep survey with 1000 students found that those categorized as having good quality sleep recorded fewer negative moods (depression, confusion, anger, and fatigue) throughout the day than those with bad-quality sleep [5]. In another study, participants experienced decreased sleepiness during the day in weekly and daily measures by increasing the duration of sleep during the night by 43 minutes per night [6].

Sleep deprivation and sleep disorders are on the rise in modern society [7, 8]. Sleep deprivation leads to a range of mental and physical health issues. A night of poor sleep can affect short-term memory [9]. The emotional state of a person can also be affected by sleep loss. Research shows reduced activation and happiness throughout the day when participants experience one or two nights of bad sleep, together with increased anger, depression, and fatigue [10]. People who experience poor quality sleep throughout the week have also reported high levels of stress compared to people with good quality sleep [5].

Insomnia is the most common sleep disorder [11]. Individuals who experience insomnia report difficulties falling asleep, returning to sleep after experiencing a nocturnal awakening, and experiencing fatigue when awakening in the morning [12]. The presence of sleep disorders and their consequential impact on mental and physical well-being in humans underscores the need to obtain good quality sleep.

2.2 Sleep Enhancement

Due to the widespread occurrence of sleep problems and their potential impact on human health, several sleep enhancement interventions, both pharmacological and not, have been suggested in scientific studies. Pharmacolog-

Copyright: © 2025 Simon Hallak et al. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15032113>

ical interventions such as medicinal interventions are often used, but provide a short-term solution. Additionally, there are some concerns about long-term use of these medications, due to the risk of side effects, abuse, and dependence [13–15]. Non-pharmacological methods, on the other hand, are more sustainable in the long term and do not have apparent side effects [16, 17]. These include hot baths, breathing techniques, and stretching before bed [18].

Another widely used technique is auditory stimulation, which has been shown to improve sleep quality. Some of these stimuli include the use of white and pink noise, as well as music, binaural beats, natural sounds, sound synchronization, etc [19, 20]. A sound-augmented blanket has been shown to be effective in promoting relaxation and potentially improving sleep quality [21]. However, research on the relationship between auditory stimuli to aid sleep and the emotional states experienced during the day and at the onset of sleep is significantly lacking. Specifically, understanding which types of auditory stimulation are most beneficial for sleep based on specific emotions remains underexplored.

2.3 Emotions, sound and sleep

Emotions can have a direct impact on people’s sleep quality. Negative emotions have been shown to produce a decrease in sleep efficiency, total sleep, and percentage of REM (rapid eye movement) sleep, and increase awakenings [2]. The use of auditory stimulation is effective in affecting emotions and can potentially improve sleep quality. For example, Juslin and Sloboda [22] showed that soft, unchanging music evokes feelings of peace, while slow tempos induce tranquility. Research indicates that people often use music before bedtime to regulate emotions and alleviate negative thoughts [3]. Moreover, exposure to pink noise during sleep has been associated to stabilizing emotional states and promoting deep sleep [23]. Active auditory stimulation at night has shown promise in reducing cortisol levels and mitigating stress [24, 25]. Similarly, subjects exposed to binaural beats coupled with natural sounds have been shown to experience diminished negative emotional states such as tension, anger, and depression [26]. Furthermore, personal preferences have been shown to be important when it comes to sound. To help customize music to individual preferences, one study [27] developed four sleep music profiles based on sleep engagement and music openness. Despite these useful findings, there remains a gap in understanding how auditory stimuli can be tailored to individuals’ emotional states during sleep onset.

This project investigates individuals’ preferences for sounds conducive to sleep when experiencing various emotional states, and describes the initial prototype for an app that suggests sounds for sleep on the basis of a person’s emotional state before sleep. The focus of this project is specifically on environmental sounds as this type of stimuli, and its relation to emotions and sleep, is particularly understudied.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 4 describes the listening test conducted to identify as-

sociations between emotional state and preferred sounds for sleep; Section 6 describes an initial prototype for a sleep enhancing app that, based on the user’s emotional state, suggests different sounds for aiding sleep; Sections 7 and 8 discuss the results and conclude respectively.

3. METHOD

An online survey was conducted to identify people’s sleep habits and their sound preferences given a particular emotional state. Based on these results, an initial prototype for a sleep app is proposed.

4. ONLINE SURVEY

A survey was conducted to determine whether the choice of sound for sleep could depend on the emotional state a person is experiencing. In the survey, participants were asked to answer questions about their sleep habits and their use of sound as a sleep aid. They were then asked to imagine feeling a particular emotion and rank different sounds in terms of whether they would choose them as a sleeping aid when feeling that emotion. For simplicity, we have chosen four emotions to cover each quadrant of the circumplex model of emotions [28]. These are: *Happy*, *Sad*, *Calm*, and *Stressed*. *Happy* represents high arousal with a positive valence; *Sad*, low arousal with a negative valence; *Calm*, low arousal with a positive valence; and *Stressed*, high arousal with a negative valence.

4.1 Survey structure

The survey contained a subset of the *Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index* questions [29] to gather information about participants’ sleep habits. Participants who relied on sound for sleep were asked detailed questions about the kind of sounds they would usually listen to. Subsequently, participants were instructed to imagine themselves experiencing a given emotion before sleep, and rank six different sounds placing on top the sound they thought would help them relax and fall asleep. The emotional states and sounds were presented in a randomized order to minimize order effects. All audio stimuli were normalized to -30 LUFS in Audacity¹. At the start of the test, participants were required to put headphones on, listen to a short audio file of white noise at -30 LUFS, adjust their audio volume to a comfortable level, and then they were explicitly asked to maintain this level throughout the test. At the end of each ranking, participants had the opportunity to write free text comments to explain their ranking choices.

4.2 Stimuli

Six sounds were chosen based on the research literature [19, 20] about the types of sounds people use for sleeping. They were categorized into three different groups: Pitched sounds, Natural sounds, and Animal sounds. Each category contained two different sounds. These were chosen on the basis of research on sound and emotions [22]. In particular: slow tempos, soft volumes and little loudness

¹ <https://www.audacityteam.org>

variation are associated with tranquil, soft and peaceful states, with higher pitched sounds being associated with more serene states and lower pitched sounds with more tranquil states. Chimes and Singing Bowls were chosen as examples of higher and lower pitched sounds, respectively. Birds and Crickets were chosen to represent softness by having soft volumes and little dynamic variation. Rain and Underwater sounds were chosen as natural sounds with differing slow tempos.

4.3 Participants

We recruited a total of 78 participants. Twenty-one people were recruited from our close social network, while the remaining 57 were recruited from the Prolific online platform². In this paper, we will refer to these groups as *Local Group* and *Global group*, respectively. Local Group is divided into 9 males and 12 females, with average age 26 and a standard deviation (SD) of 6.1 all living in Sweden. Global Group is divided into 30 males and 27 females, with average age 29 and SD of 8.2, and recruited from across the globe, including regions such as Africa, South America, North America, Europe, and Asia. Extending the test to Prolific allowed us to recruit participants of different ages and genders, from all over the world, and with no connection to the researchers, reducing potential bias and increasing the reliability of the results.

At the start of the survey, participants were asked how they felt and the results of participants who declared feeling emotionally unwell were excluded from the study. Prolific participants were recruited with the following screening criteria: half males, half female, without hearing difficulties, without diagnosed or ongoing mental health issues such as depression. All participants were provided with information about the survey before starting and were explicitly informed that they could withdraw at any time. The Local Group did the test without compensation. The Global Group was compensated with the standard hourly rate of 9£ pro-rata.

5. RESULTS

5.1 Sleep habits

The results show that sleep habits were relatively similar between the groups. The majority, 59, answered that they had fairly good sleep during the past month, with only 19 reporting fairly poor sleep. Local Group reported having an average of 6.2 hours of sleep, while Global Group had 6.7 hours daily in the past month. When asked whether they slept alone or with someone else, 41 participants said that they slept by themselves (14 participants from the Local Group and 27 from the Global Group). Two of these people wrote that they share the room with their pets. Listening to sound as a sleep aid was relatively common among our participants, with 45 out of 78 people reporting that they occasionally or regularly use sound to facilitate sleep. The majority declared that they prefer to listen to sounds with words in them, such as podcasts, audiobooks, music

²<https://www.prolific.com>

Figure 1. The *Left* plot illustrates the frequency of sound usage for sleep among participants. Note that the Global Group's counts are divided by 2.7 (N of subject in Global/N of subjects in Local) to make them comparable to the Local Group. The *Right* plot details the types of sounds used among participant.

Figure 2. These figures illustrate the responses from the listening test's ranking questions on sound preferences associated with four different emotions: Stressed, Happy, Sad, and Calm. For each emotion, the bars represent the number of participants who ranked each sound type as their first and second choices according to which group they belong.

with lyrics, TV programs, and Yoga Nadra meditation. In comparison, fewer people declared listening to instrumental music, natural sounds, and ASMR.

5.2 Ranking sounds in relation to emotional state

Figure 2 shows the ranking of all the sounds for all the emotions when we sum the counts for the first and second choice (e.g., for Happy: the Rain sound has been ranked first 9 times and second 0 times, so the sum is 9). Note that the Global counts are made comparable to the Local counts by dividing them by 2.7, i.e. the ratio between the participants in the Local group and the participants in the Global Group.

Overall, the results of the Local Group and the Global Group are fairly similar, confirming the absence of bias due to the different recruitment methods. The sound of Rain was preferred by both groups across emotions, and the sound of Chimes was the least preferred by both groups regardless of the emotion. The main difference between the two groups can be noticed as the Crickets sound is consistently preferred more often by the Local Group rather than the Global Group. Additionally, the Chimes sound is chosen more often by the Global Group, compared to the

Emotion	Top 3 Sound Choices
Stressed	Rain, Underwater, Singing Bowls
Happy	Rain, Birds, Crickets
Sad	Rain, Underwater, Singing Bowls
Calm	Rain, Underwater-Singing Bowls, Birds-Crickets

Table 1. Top 3 sound choices dependent on emotional state.

Emotion	Top 3 Sound Choices
FEMALE (39 people)	
Stressed	Rain, Underwater, Singing Bowls
Happy	Rain, Birds, Crickets
Sad	Rain, Singing Bowls, Crickets-Birds
Calm	Rain, Birds , Singing Bowl-Crickets
MALE (39 people)	
Stressed	Rain, Underwater, Singing Bowls
Happy	Rain, Birds, Crickets
Sad	Rain, Underwater , Singing Bowls
Calm	Rain, Underwater , Singing Bowl-Crickets

Table 2. Top 3 sound choices by gender, the text in **bold** indicates the main differences between the two genders.

Local Group.

Both groups show a change in sound preference depending on the emotional state. When looking at the differences between Positive and Negative emotions, we see that the Underwater sound is ranked relatively high by both groups in relation to negative emotional states (Stressed and Sad). And generally the Local and Global profiles for the Negative emotions are similar. The profiles for the Positive emotions show more differences between groups, but the Birds sound is rated high for the Happy emotion for both groups.

As we mentioned above, the Local Group shows a higher preference for the Crickets sound than Global Group. This preference is relatively stronger in the positive states, in particular the Happy state.

Both Local and Global Groups rated the Underwater and the Singing Bowl sound high in the Stress state. Local Group rates them particularly high in the Sad state too.

To summarize, and combining the results from both tests, in Table 1 are the sounds preferred for each emotion.

5.3 Further Analyses

In Table 2 we report the results by gender.

In this study, male participants seem to prefer the Underwater sound for low arousal emotions (Sad and Calm), while female participants seem to prefer Birds and Crickets sounds.

In Table 3, we can see the results split between participants who use audio as sleep aid in their sleep routine, and participants who never use an audio as sleep aid.

Participants who use audio as sleep aid seem to prefer Singing Bowl and Birds sounds across various emotions, while those who do not use audio as sleep aid seem to

Emotion	Top 3 Sound Choices
AUDIO AID (45 people)	
Stressed	Rain, Underwater, Singing Bowls
Happy	Rain, Birds, Singing Bowls-Crickets
Sad	Rain, Singing Bowls, Crickets-Birds
Calm	Rain, Birds, Singing Bowl
NO AUDIO AID (33 people)	
Stressed	Rain, Underwater, Singing Bowls
Happy	Rain, Crickets-Birds, Underwater
Sad	Rain, Underwater , Singing Bowls
Calm	Rain, Underwater, Crickets

Table 3. Top 3 sound choices for people who use audio as sleep aid vs. people who do not. The text in **bold** indicates the main differences between the two groups.

choose more often the Underwater sound across several emotional states.

5.4 Summary of comments

Twenty three participants from the Global Group and three from the Local Group commented on their choices of sound. Two participants mentioned how some sounds brought back memories. For example, the sound of Crickets reminded some people of a safe place or time on an island, something that helped them calm down when feeling stressed. Three people linked sounds with objects or seasons. For example, a person rated the Crickets' sound high when feeling sad because crickets reminded them of summer, which made them happy. Another person preferred water sounds (Underwater and Rain) when feeling happy because they felt closer to nature. Two people mentioned that birds are associated with early morning, and therefore not the first choice for falling asleep:

Sometimes, hearing birds chirping in the morning reminds me of camping. However, it also brings back memories of how early we had to wake up for activities, which can be a bit of a buzzkill.

Some participants mentioned that the Underwater sound made them feel trapped and anxious. Participants who rated Birds and Crickets high for Sad feelings mentioned that these sounds cheered them up, while the Rain and Singing Bowl sounds made them feel even more sad. Rain and Crickets sounds were mainly described as peaceful sounds. The Chimes were the least favorite of all sounds, although some people did rate them high for positive moods, and were generally described as noisy and too loud. Below are selected comments about each emotion.

In terms of soothing a Sad emotional state, one participant stated: *"Light" sounds (Chimes, Birds) feel good while being in a bad mood, as they are capable of disrupting the bad mood* Another participant stated: *The rain has that calming effect, but when one is sad it also promises better days to come. To me, rain signifies cleaning of the air and growth of vegetables, which is a promise in itself. Birds sounds promise a better day as they mostly chirp when the skies are beautiful with no disturbing weather,*

so they also bring hope.

In addressing a Stressed state one person stated: *Birds are too lively to calm me while stressed, same goes for crickets. The Underwater sound, and especially Rain, seems natural and can make me calm.*

Two comments exemplify the ambivalent feelings towards the Underwater sound: *Water sounds are my thing* versus *Nothing will ever make me enjoy the sound of the ocean or any underwater sound.*

Regarding the Happy emotion, one person stated: *Living creatures seem like a good addition to a happy mood because they seem happy to be alive, so birds and crickets are fine.*

The comments on the Calm state are very varied, reflecting the main results of the study (see Table 1) *Chimes, Birds are relaxing; Crickets with Rain seems natural and easy to blend in calm mood, the underwater sounds are calming, I feel like the singing bowls would help keep me feeling calm.*

Finally, a person stated that: *The quickest I get to fall asleep is when I'm calm, and at this stage I might not need any sound to help me sleep.*

Overall, the survey showed that there is a relationship between emotional state and sound choices for sleep. Based on these findings, we developed an app prototype aiming to suggest to users the perfect sound, tailored to their emotional state, to improve sleep.

6. SOUND ASLEEP - APP DEVELOPMENT

Research shows that many people use smartphone apps to improve their sleep, and most apps aim to reduce sleep latency through auditory stimuli, such as nature sounds and instrumental music [30].

This section describes the initial prototype for an app designed to promote sleep. The prototype presents sounds tailored to the user's emotional state. Research has shown that visual experiences are important to induce relaxation by providing a sense of restoration and a reduction in tension [31]. Therefore, the prototype design paid considerable attention to the visual aspects. Additionally, user-centered design principles [32] are utilized to ensure a calming and pleasant user experience. Moraveji and Soesanto [33] propose 10 design heuristics used to minimize the number of stressors in an interface. These include: (1) reducing feeling overwhelmed by presenting as little data as possible; (2) using appropriate tone and emotions such as being polite and apologetic; (3) providing positive feedback to user input such as "Thank you for filling out the form", and (4) relieving time pressure. Furthermore, a screen dark mode makes it comfortable for users to use their mobiles at night or in the dark [34].

In this prototype, the user is asked to choose their current emotional state from the four emotions used in the survey. Based on the user's responses, the application suggests sounds to be played to enhance sleep. The sound suggestions are based on the results of the survey described in 4. Furthermore, the user can preview the sounds before selecting the final one. The app prioritizes ease of interaction making it as simple as possible for the user to engage

Figure 3. This figure displays three screenshots from the prototype of the sleep enhancement application designed to assist users in selecting sounds based on their emotional state to improve sleep quality.

with the interface and avoid confusion before sleeping. It provides simple visual cues for user guidance and feedback. For instance, when the user clicks on a sound button, the color of the border changes, indicating that the sound is playing. Font type and size are chosen to avoid straining the eyes while reading under low light conditions.

7. DISCUSSION

This study aims to investigate the relationship between emotional state and the sounds people choose to aid their sleep. The results of the survey show that people seem to prefer different sounds for sleep depending on their emotional state.

For negative emotions (Stressed and Sad), Rain, Underwater, and Singing Bowl sounds were preferred. Rain and Underwater are natural sounds with slow tempos, and the Singing Bowl sound is musical with low-pitch characteristics.

For positive emotions (Happy and Calm), Rain, Birds and Crickets sounds were preferred. These sounds are relatively noisy natural sounds, with soft volumes and little loudness variation, but with a relatively high frequency content when compared to the Underwater and Singing Bowl sounds.

The study seems to indicate that the frequency content of a sound plays a role in what sounds people choose depending on their emotional state.

7.1 Sound ranking

Most participants generally rated Underwater sounds high for negative emotions. However, some participants experienced anxiety when exposed to these sounds, which highlights the importance of accounting for individual differences in sound preferences. With this in mind, the app prototype is designed to offer the possibility of choosing among several different sounds that have been shown to be liked when experiencing a specific emotion. This approach ensures that users can further select the sound that best suits their personal comfort and preferences.

In this study, we have also explored differences in relation to gender and the use of audio as a sleep aid. The results seem to indicate that there may be differences along

Figure 4. This figure displays spectrograms of the six sounds used in the survey. On the left side are spectrograms for sounds preferred during negative emotions. On the right side are the sounds preferred during positive emotions.

these categories. These could be due to how the relationship between gender and emotions is portrayed in media and culture, for example. Additionally, a person’s existing experience with audio as a sleep aid might mean that they already know that certain sounds, associations, etc. will not work for soothing or maintaining a particular emotion for them (for example, a person might like the Underwater sound in normal circumstances, but they have used it once to go to sleep and they know that it can bring up bad memories about an experience with water and therefore know that they would not choose it). A larger study specifically designed to examine these differences would need to be carried out to confirm the findings and explore any underlying reasons for this.

The main limitations of the study can be summarized as follows. The sounds were selected on the basis of prior research on sound characteristics that help to reach a relaxed, positive state. However, it is possible that not all participants found that the chosen sounds fit these characteristics. For instance, the pitch and tempo of the Chimes sound were not perceived as pleasant or serene as anticipated. One participant described the sound as *“Too loud and aggressive to be calming,”* adding, *“if I’m already calm, I’d prefer something more chill, like rain”*.

Some differences in choices were observed between the two groups. For example, Local Group preferred the Crickets sound more than the Global Group. We suggest that a cultural difference could be the reason for this. Crickets are not common in cold weather and some can only be heard during summer in Sweden. For some people from the Local Group, Crickets reminded them of summertime on the beach, perhaps in another country, which helped them calm down. This association may be less significant for people from other countries and cultures. Finally, for some participants, the Birds sound was associated with the morning and therefore they felt it not to be suitable as an aid for going to sleep since that usually happens at night. Future studies should explore a more comprehensive collection of sounds for each category and allow participants to select

from multiple instances of each sound category.

Another limitation of this study is the fact that we asked people to “imagine” feeling an emotion before going to sleep, rather than survey them when they go to sleep and feel a specific emotion. This second and more realistic option requires a longitudinal study that is very demanding in terms of time and resources. Our study was designed as a pilot that could reveal whether the research focus would warrant a larger, longitudinal, more in-depth study. In this sense, this study is successful in suggesting that this research direction is worthy of further investigation.

Further limitations include a relatively small participants’ sample, a limited age range, and a limited number of emotions, which again should be addressed in a larger, future study.

7.2 Future work

A further study is underway, where participants are asked to use the “SoundAsleep” app before going to sleep. The study is carried out at home and lasts for a minimum of one week. The app provides participants with several sounds to choose from for each emotion to ensure that individual differences can be observed. The emotional states and sound choices are tracked by the researchers. In addition, each morning, participants are asked to provide feedback on the chosen sound and their sleep through a sleep diary. Finally, participants are asked to answer questions about the app’s effectiveness and user-experience.

8. CONCLUSION

The study investigates the relationship between emotional states and sound preferences as a sleep aid. The study achieved this by conducting an online survey asking participants to rank their sound preferences for sleep according to a particular emotional state they were asked to imagine feeling. The emotional states were Happy, Stressed, Calm, and Sad. Participants were recruited into two groups: one from a close network and another group recruited online. The results from the survey show that there appears to be a relationship between emotional states and sound preferences as a sleep aid. The results indicate distinct preferences for certain types of sounds based on emotional state, with sounds such as Rain, Underwater, and Singing Bowls preferred by individuals experiencing negative emotions. At the same time, Birds and Crickets sounds were more often preferred for positive emotional states. The results also show similarities between the two different groups recruited for data collection. The application prototype presented in this paper is designed to be easy to use and calming, while offering users the choice between three different sounds depending on their emotional state before going to bed.

Acknowledgments

This work is supported by the EU MSCA Lullabyte Doctoral Network <https://lullabyte.eu>.

9. REFERENCES

- [1] Consensus Conference Panel; N. F. Watson, M. S. Badr, G. Belenky, D. L. Bliwise, O. M. Buxton, D. Buysse, D. F. Dinges, J. Gangwisch, M. A. Grandner, C. Kushida, R. K. Malhotra, J. L. Martin, S. R. Patel, S. F. Quan, and E. Tasali, "Joint consensus statement of the american academy of sleep medicine and sleep research society on the recommended amount of sleep for a healthy adult: Methodology and discussion," *Journal of Clinical Sleep Medicine*, vol. 11, no. 8, pp. 931–952. [Online]. Available: <http://jcsm.aasm.org/doi/10.5664/jcsm.4950>
- [2] M. Vandekerckhove, R. Weiss, C. Schotte, V. Exadaktylos, B. Haex, J. Verbraecken, and R. Cluydts, "The role of presleep negative emotion in sleep physiology," *Psychophysiology*, vol. 48, no. 12, pp. 1738–1744.
- [3] T. Trahan, S. Durrant, D. Müllensiefen, and V. Williamson, "The music that helps people sleep and the reasons they believe it works: A mixed methods analysis of online survey reports," *PLoS ONE*, vol. 13, no. 11.
- [4] M. Ohayon, E. M. Wickwire, M. Hirshkowitz, S. M. Albert, A. Avidan, F. J. Daly, Y. Dauvilliers, R. Ferri, C. Fung, D. Gozal, N. Hazen, A. Krystal, K. Lichstein, M. Mallampalli, G. Plazzi, R. Rawding, F. A. Scheer, V. Somers, and M. V. Vitiello, "National sleep foundation's sleep quality recommendations: first report," *Sleep Health*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 6–19.
- [5] H. G. Lund, B. D. Reider, A. B. Whiting, and J. R. Prichard, "Sleep patterns and predictors of disturbed sleep in a large population of college students," *Journal of Adolescent Health*, vol. 46, no. 2, pp. 124–132. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1054139X09002389>
- [6] A. A. Stock, S. Lee, N. G. Nahmod, and A.-M. Chang, "Effects of sleep extension on sleep duration, sleepiness, and blood pressure in college students," *Sleep Health*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 32–39. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352721819302177>
- [7] M. Calem, J. Bisla, A. Begum, M. Dewey, P. E. Bebbington, T. Brugha, C. Cooper, R. Jenkins, J. Lindesay, S. McManus, H. Meltzer, N. Spiers, S. Weich, and R. Stewart, "Increased prevalence of insomnia and changes in hypnotics use in england over 15 years: Analysis of the 1993, 2000, and 2007 national psychiatric morbidity surveys," *Sleep*, vol. 35, no. 3, pp. 377–384. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5665/sleep.1700>
- [8] S. Pallesen, B. Sivertsen, I. H. Nordhus, and B. Bjorvatn, "A 10-year trend of insomnia prevalence in the adult norwegian population," *Sleep Medicine*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 173–179. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1389945713012021>
- [9] M. W. Chee and Y. L. Chuah, "Functional neuroimaging and behavioral correlates of capacity decline in visual short-term memory after sleep deprivation," *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, vol. 104, no. 22, pp. 9487–9492, 2007.
- [10] J. Paterson, J. Dorrian, S. Ferguson, S. Jay, N. Lamond, P. Murphy, S. Campbell, and D. Dawson, "Changes in structural aspects of mood during 39–66 h of sleep loss using matched controls," *Applied Ergonomics*, vol. 42, no. 2, pp. 196–201, 2011.
- [11] C. M. Morin, M. LeBlanc, M. Daley, J. P. Gregoire, and C. Mérette, "Epidemiology of insomnia: Prevalence, self-help treatments, consultations, and determinants of help-seeking behaviors," *Sleep Medicine*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 123–130. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1389945705001954>
- [12] S. Ancoli-Israel and T. Roth, "Characteristics of insomnia in the united states: results of the 1991 national sleep foundation survey. i," *Sleep*, vol. 22 Suppl 2, pp. S347–53.
- [13] T. Akerstedt, G. Kecklund, L. Alfredsson, and J. Selen, "Predicting long-term sickness absence from sleep and fatigue," *Journal of sleep research*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 341–345, 2007.
- [14] A. Qaseem, D. Kansagara, M. A. Forcica, M. Cooke, T. D. Denberg, and C. G. C. of the American College of Physicians*, "Management of chronic insomnia disorder in adults: a clinical practice guideline from the american college of physicians," *Annals of internal medicine*, vol. 165, no. 2, pp. 125–133, 2016.
- [15] D. Riemann, C. Baglioni, C. Bassetti, B. Bjorvatn, L. Dolenc Groseelj, J. G. Ellis, C. A. Espie, D. Garcia-Borreguero, M. Gjerstad, M. Gonçalves *et al.*, "European guideline for the diagnosis and treatment of insomnia," *Journal of sleep research*, vol. 26, no. 6, pp. 675–700, 2017.
- [16] E. Sella, E. Toffalini, L. Canini, and E. Borella, "Non-pharmacological interventions targeting sleep quality in older adults: a systematic review and meta-analysis," *Aging & Mental Health*, vol. 27, no. 5, pp. 847–861, 2023.
- [17] S. MacLeod, S. Musich, S. Kraemer, and E. Wicker, "Practical non-pharmacological intervention approaches for sleep problems among older adults," *Geriatric Nursing*, vol. 39, no. 5, pp. 506–512, 2018.
- [18] R. J. Cole, "Nonpharmacologic techniques for promoting sleep," *Clinics in Sports Medicine*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 343–353. [Online]. Available: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0278591904001462>
- [19] E. Capezuti, K. Pain, E. Alamag, X. Chen, V. Philibert, and A. C. Krieger, "Systematic review: auditory stimulation and sleep," *Journal of Clinical Sleep Medicine*, vol. 18, no. 6, pp. 1697–1709, 2022.

- [20] H. Yoon and H. J. Baek, "External auditory stimulation as a non-pharmacological sleep aid," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 3, p. 1264, 2022.
- [21] A. Choubey, A. Cera, and S. Pauletto, "Sonic blankets: exploring the use of sound-augmented blankets for relaxation and sleep," in *Proceedings of the 19th International Audio Mostly Conference: Explorations in Sonic Cultures*, 2024, pp. 511–524.
- [22] P. N. Juslin and J. Sloboda, *Handbook of music and emotion: Theory, research, applications*. Oxford University Press, 2011.
- [23] J. Zhou, D. Liu, X. Li, J. Ma, J. Zhang, and J. Fang, "Pink noise: Effect on complexity synchronization of brain activity and sleep consolidation," *Journal of Theoretical Biology*, vol. 306, pp. 68–72. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0022519312001798>
- [24] D. Grimaldi, N. A. Papalambros, K. J. Reid, S. M. Abbott, R. G. Malkani, M. Gendy, M. Iwanaszko, R. I. Braun, D. J. Sanchez, K. A. Paller *et al.*, "Strengthening sleep–autonomic interaction via acoustic enhancement of slow oscillations," *Sleep*, vol. 42, no. 5, p. zsz036, 2019.
- [25] L. Besedovsky, H.-V. V. Ngo, S. Dimitrov, C. Gassenmaier, R. Lehmann, and J. Born, "Auditory closed-loop stimulation of eeg slow oscillations strengthens sleep and signs of its immune-supportive function," *Nature communications*, vol. 8, no. 1, p. 1984, 2017.
- [26] M. Lee, C.-B. Song, G.-H. Shin, and S.-W. Lee, "Possible effect of binaural beat combined with autonomous sensory meridian response for inducing sleep," *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, vol. 13, publisher: Frontiers. [Online]. Available: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fnhum.2019.00425>
- [27] S. Delle Monache, D. Jia, D. Kamphuis, and E. Özcan, "Exploring profiling and personalisation in sleep music design: towards conceptualising musical sleep aids for hospital use," in *Proceedings of the 17th International Audio Mostly Conference*, 2022, pp. 129–136.
- [28] J. A. Russell, "A circumplex model of affect." *Journal of personality and social psychology*, vol. 39, no. 6, p. 1161, 1980.
- [29] D. J. Buysse, C. F. Reynolds III, T. H. Monk, S. R. Berman, and D. J. Kupfer, "The pittsburgh sleep quality index: a new instrument for psychiatric practice and research," *Psychiatry research*, vol. 28, no. 2, pp. 193–213, 1989.
- [30] E. Stekl, G. Klosterman, G. Simonelli, J. Collen, and T. J. Doty, "269 sleep enhancement technology: A survey of apps," *Sleep*, vol. 44, p. A108, 2021.
- [31] C. M. Kim, T. J. van Romy, G. L. Louwers, J. Yoon, and G. D. Ludden, "From a morning forest to a sunset beach: Understanding visual experiences and the roles of personal characteristics for designing relaxing digital nature," *International Journal of Human–Computer Interaction*, pp. 1–18, 2023.
- [32] D. A. Norman, *The psychology of everyday things*. Basic books, 1988.
- [33] N. Moraveji and C. Soesanto, "Towards stress-less user interfaces: 10 design heuristics based on the psychophysiology of stress," in *CHI'12 extended abstracts on Human factors in computing systems*, 2012, pp. 1643–1648.
- [34] N. Bonnardel, A. Piolat, and L. Le Bigot, "The impact of colour on website appeal and users' cognitive processes," *Displays*, vol. 32, no. 2, pp. 69–80, 2011.

Probabilistic Generative Music as a Data Sonification Medium

Prithvi Ravi Kantan

Department of Architecture, Design and Media Technology
Aalborg University, Copenhagen
prka@create.aau.dk

ABSTRACT

Auditory displays that incorporate musical structural elements and textures have been used to increase long-term listenability and engagement. Such approaches are often met with skepticism due to the inherent tradeoff between aesthetics and information fidelity. Additionally, their typical reliance on simple deterministic mappings (e.g. MIDI pitch or note duration changes) produce sonic outputs that are either overly predictable or musically incoherent. I propose and demonstrate a framework that expands the parameter mapping space through the manipulation of determinism and nondeterminism in real-time sequenced generative music. The result is dynamic and improvisatory musical patterns that may sustain listener interest while saliently conveying data trends with adequate perceptual independence between musical dimensions. The resulting parameter space may be suited to applications targeting artistic expression or augmented relaxation, sleep, and movement, where informational fidelity and temporal precision may marginally be sacrificed in favor of musicality and its associated affective / motivational benefits. Although pending formal evaluation, this work reflects flashes of the potential that probabilistic generative music has as a data communication medium.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Aesthetics and Fidelity in Sonification Design

Sonification is the systematic and reproducible scientific method for representing data (typically as nonspeech sound) in an auditory display [1]. Sonification has many application domains ranging from scientific to artistic, and the exact data-sound relationship is naturally pivotal to the utility and usability of a sonification. Depending on the application, criteria such as aesthetics, data representational fidelity, and the intuitiveness of data-sound metaphors used may be weighted differently, and research over the years has revealed that these criteria share a complicated push-and-pull relationship with many studies revealing tradeoffs between musicality / aesthetics and data fidelity [2–7].

Focusing primarily on scientific applications, a general consensus among veterans in the field has been that while

conveying the intended ‘message’ is paramount, it is prudent to design sonifications that are aesthetically pleasing to the extent possible [3, 4, 8, 9]. This rings especially relevant when considering applications that entail extended periods of listening to a sonification, where ‘poor acoustic ecology’ may make listening and subsequent data interpretation difficult [10]. These use case contexts include movement rehabilitation [11], peripheral process monitoring [12], and relaxation / mindfulness [13], where it is necessary to appropriately balance communicational efficiency and aesthetic character so the rendered sound does not seem arbitrary in relation to the data underlying it [3]. To promote meaningful mappings, the concept of *conceptual metaphors* has more recently been formalized as a cornerstone of sonification design [14]. Metaphors (e.g. love is a journey), which economically transfer large chunk of information from familiar domains of thought to unfamiliar ones, can connotatively convey information about phenomena that even words cannot, and metaphors are integral to several critical domains of language and thought [14, 15]. Sounds have a natural proclivity to bind to metaphorical associations [16], and a sound-specific domain that most humans have extensive (and usually positive) embodied experience with is music, which has made music an intriguing vehicle for data communication among sonification designers over the years [2].

1.2 Musical Sonification

Notwithstanding ongoing debates regarding the definition of music [2], the term *musical sonification* has historically been used to loosely characterize sonification designs that, for either artistic or aesthetic purposes, integrate traditional elements of musical structure or texture into their design. Musicality may be realized at either the symbolic level (e.g. manipulating MIDI pitches) [17] or signal level (e.g. altering digital processing applied to recorded / synthesized music) [18]. Common reasons for imbuing sonification design with musical traits include enhancing long-term listenability and mediating affect / motivation [2, 11, 18, 19] coupled with the notion that music provides an appealing and universal ‘sonic grammar’ that can be leveraged in the creation of metaphors to reliably convey information about a dataset [3, 20]. Despite these positives, studies have routinely found that ‘data-irrelevant’ musical components may run the risk of ‘cluttering the message’ in the data and reducing user task performance in certain regards [5–7, 18], aside from the reality that even ‘musical’ sonifications may be unengaging and / or fatiguing

Copyright: © 2025 Prithvi Ravi Kantan et al. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15032599>

ing to listen to [2]. Plausible reasons include the prevalence of simplistic data-to-MIDI pitch mappings as well as the information-dense nature of most numerical datasets, which can often lead to musically incoherent sonic outputs [2].

1.3 Proposed Generative Paradigm

As the fundamental medium for data communication, I propose the use of music that is:

1. Generative (algorithmic) and polyphonic with evolutionary components that are both dataset-dependent and independent.
2. Amenable for the manipulation of both its deterministic and nondeterministic characteristics.
3. Probabilistically sequenced in real time.
4. Stylistically inspired by repetitive instrumental popular music genres (e.g. drums and bass).

The vision is, in essence, one where data variable variations convey information through improvisatory musical changes applied in real time to a pre-sequenced basic musical structure. Although sequencer-based sonification approaches have unsystematically been applied before [11], such a paradigm is, for all practical purposes, a novel one with several strong motivations. Generative music, with algorithmically creates a musical output in a rule-based, data-driven, or hybrid manner [21, 22], makes principal sense as a data sonification medium for certain applications. Unlike completely predefined or completely data-controlled music, it allows sonification designers to define which aspects of musical evolution are data-controlled and data-independent, enabling the generation of output sequences that are not only coherent in a musical sense but also informative about the dataset along very specific musical dimensions. Secondly, depending on the generative architecture, it may also expose a variety of musically meaningful control parameters not otherwise accessible when mapping to pre-rendered or predefined MIDI music. Finally, generative music can help avoid copyright issues, flexibly blend musical elements, and tailor the output to environmental and listener-specific aspects [21].

It is common for music performances to comprise a combination of deterministic elements (e.g. composer-specified melodic contours) and nondeterministic elements that are subject to stochastic or creative variation [23]. Although musically informed sonification designs have often mapped data variables to deterministic elements (e.g. melodic pitch, tempo, note duration) [11, 17, 20], nondeterministic elements have received little consideration as ‘mapping material’. Nondeterminism can be computationally modelled using chance processes such as random number generation [24, Sec 1]. Randomness has successfully been harnessed in interactive products to enrich user experience (e.g. iPod Shuffle, *randomURL*), and it has been argued that randomness in music has a distinctive and audible character, which merits its consideration as musical material in and of itself [24, Sec 2]. Nondeterminism

has been shown to be an indispensable entailment of creative processes in music [23], and musical novelty / surprise underpins feelings of musical reward and enjoyment at a neurophysiological level [19].

Generative systems typically exhibit a degree of nondeterminism (e.g. seeded random number generation) in their working [22], which not only adds novelty and surprise to the short- and long-term evolution of their output, but also allow for entirely new musical sequences to be generated each time such systems are run. An example parameter mapping to a nondeterministic attribute would be when a continuous data variable is mapped to the *probability* of a musical event being triggered at a particular point in time, as opposed to simply triggering the event when the variable crosses a threshold (the deterministic counterpart thereof). Despite their intrinsic ties to musical creativity and meaning, mappings to nondeterministic attributes have been exceedingly rare in musical sonification design; Hermann’s taxonomy even explicitly dictates that sonifications must be reproducible at the audio signal level [1]. However, I argue that *deterministic mappings to nondeterministic properties* can convey non-audio information similarly to how the colour / timbre of a noise waveform conveys information about the nondeterministic process that generates it; different bursts of noise sound the same to us even if the exact wave sequences vary. Real-time sequencing and time-continuous manipulation of various dimensions of *musical nondeterminism* can similarly help convey non-audio information through a variety of musical metaphors.

The choice of repetitive instrumental popular music as stylistic inspiration has several motivating factors. Popular music is universal and has ubiquitous appeal, which means that most prospective users will likely have lifelong familiarity with effortlessly decoding its characteristic sonic grammar and symbolic syntax irrespective of musical training [2]. Popular music is commonly used as background music during various non-musical activities such as exercise, learning, studying, driving, etc. to improve concentration, mood, and task performance [19, 25, 26]. Moreover, repetition in music is shown to be an important mediator of anticipatory mechanisms and, in turn, enjoyment during music listening [27]. The simple metrical structure of most popular music also makes it conducive to training (and synchronously providing auditory feedback on) cyclical bodily movements (e.g. walking) [11]. Although musical preferences vary and task performance depends on arousal level [25, 28], popular music seems to readily lend itself to pleasurable long-term listening, a characteristic worthy of leveraging when designing sonifications for process monitoring or real-time biofeedback applications.

1.4 Caveats

Regarding information content, the proposed paradigm is still vulnerable to the possibility of generating a musically incoherent output in certain data mapping configurations, but the in-depth parametric control it offers can allow designers to realize appropriate metaphors for a variety of situations. Regarding fidelity, a nonstationary musical signal with data-independent variation will most likely intro-

duce considerable perceptual ‘noise’ in terms of data value resolution (Y-axis) as well as temporal resolution (X-axis). At the outset, it therefore seems plausible to only make use of this paradigm when conveying data variables that (a) take a relatively small number of discrete values, and (b) do not rapidly change in value. These conditions are broadly satisfied in several instances of process monitoring / biofeedback that convey information about discrete states that evolve relatively slowly.

1.5 Current Scope Delimitation

This work aims to showcase a real-time technical architecture for data sonification through the systematic manipulation of deterministic and nondeterministic elements in probabilistically sequenced generative music. The overall system structure will briefly be explained, and an initial set of mappable parameters are described and demonstrated. Two musical instrumentation styles have been tested thus far - acoustic drums and major scale piano - and a small set of real-time demos with multivariate mappings is also provided. A concise initial appraisal of the potential and implications of the generative paradigm as well as its current implementation will ensue in the discussion.

2. INTERACTIVE SEQUENCER ARCHITECTURE

In order to realize, showcase, and test the concept of conveying information through the manipulation of nondeterministic traits of generative music, a real-time Windows-based generative music sequencing platform was built using the JUCE¹ audio programming environment. It comprises the following key component blocks:

- 6-Channel OSC Input
- Audio Sample Architecture
- Musical Event Chart
- Sequencing and Playback
- Parameter Mapping

2.1 6-Channel OSC Input

The platform takes in six discrete channels of numeric OSC data normalized between 0 – 1. The interface provides a real-time visualization of incoming data on each channel, and it is also possible to simulate real-time input using a slider. Each channel can be linearly mapped to no more than one mapping parameter.

2.2 Audio Sample Architecture

The interface allows for choice between various *instrumentation styles*, which are essentially sample packs that are dynamically loaded from a local folder. For each individual sample file, information about note number and velocity range is obtained from the file name, which follows a strict convention. It is hence possible to have different audio clips for different MIDI velocity ranges of the same

note number (e.g. a soft drum hit for velocities 0–64, a regular hit for 65–96, and a hard rim shot from 97–128). There is no restriction on the number of possible note numbers or the number of velocity-distinct sample files per note number.

2.3 Musical Event Chart

Prior to playback, a grid-based chart of musical events over a short musical duration (e.g. 1-2 bars) must be defined using the visual interface shown in Fig. 1. As in any traditional sequencer, the grid rows indicate note number, and the columns indicate grid position. The grid resolution (e.g. quarter / eighth / sixteenth note) depends on the instrumentation style. The contents of each grid location can be manipulated by the user at any time (also during playback), and these manual changes are registered after pattern playback is complete and is preparing to loop. As shown, there are buttons to instantly clear every row (note number) and column (musical time position). Easy-access buttons (see Fig. 2) enable the user to clear the entire chart or fill each grid position with pseudorandom velocity and probability values that are programmatically weighted to accentuate beat intervals. Events may hence be certain (probability = 1) or uncertain (probability < 1). When an instrumentation style is loaded, the default musical chart is an empty grid, i.e. no musical events at any chart position for any note number. A seemingly effective approach is for the user to define a small set of certain events as the *base pattern* (a simple rhythm or melody) and then randomly populate the remaining grid positions with uncertain events. This ensures a balance between identifiable musical structure and short-term variation to maintain listener interest.

2.4 Sequencing and Playback

When playback is started, the musical event chart is queued based on the user-configured grid event velocities and probabilities for each note number. Hence, each musical event is captured by its note number, probability, velocity, and temporal position in MIDI ticks. During playback, the play position is incremented by a specific number of ticks at a 1-ms interval based on the configured tempo, and the sequencer checks for new events at each interval. If one or more events are found, the sequencer decides whether to trigger them based on their event probability by making use of a JUCE *random number generator (RNG)*. When the sequencer reaches the end of the pattern, it loops back to the start. Musical structure variations are brought about through both probabilistic variations over time and the explicit randomization of specific attributes as described in the next section.

2.5 Parameter Mapping

The music sequencing architecture exposes several parameters for real-time manipulation (see next section), and each of the six OSC inputs may either remain unmapped or be mapped to one of them from a drop-down list. Only linear one-to-one mappings are possible at this stage. Each

¹<https://juce.com/>

Figure 1. The interactive sequencer interface with key components labelled for a 4-beat grid with sixteen note resolution (beats marked in blue). For each grid position, the thicker rectangle shows event velocity and the thinner one shows probability (green for certain events). All velocities and probabilities can be manipulated directly from the UI.

input signal (0 – 1) is linearly scaled to the full range of the parameter it is mapped to. The sequencer is updated with new parameter values every millisecond.

3. MAPPABLE SEQUENCER PARAMETERS

Please refer to the supplementary folder² for A/V demonstrations of each parameter (as well as some bivariate combinations) described in the following subsections. In each video, input data variable changes can be seen in the mapper section to the left of the screen (indicated by downward blue arrows).

3.1 Linear Multiplier Parameters

These parameters work by applying simple multiplicative factors to specific sequencer- or playback-related variables.

1. *Velocity Multiplier*: All triggered event velocities are uniformly multiplied by this factor (default value 1.0, range 0.0 – 1.8). This manifests as changes in volume and event envelope shape that are modulated by changes in the mapped data variable. If different audio clips / samples are used for different velocity ranges (e.g. with acoustic drums), the velocity multiplier alters articulation and timbre as well.

2. *Probability Multiplier*: All uncertain event probabilities are uniformly multiplied by this factor (default value 1.0, range 0.0 – 3.0) prior to RNG check prior to triggering. When it is zero, only the base pattern (certain events) plays. As it is raised, the uncertain events on the chart play with increasing probability, making the output pattern musically busier. As more and more uncertain events become certain, the pattern is at its busiest and most predictable.

3. *Tempo Multiplier*: This applies a multiplier to the tick increment applied to the sequencer every millisecond (default value 1.0, range 0.0 – 2.0). Altering the multiplier value thus alters how quickly the sequencer ‘moves through’ the pattern, changing the output tempo on a moment-to-moment basis without any extraneous alteration to the sound.

4. *Playrate Multiplier*: This applies a uniform multiplier (default value 1.0, range 0.2 – 10) to the read index increment of all loaded audio sample files, which speeds up or slows down all triggered events equally. This manifests as changes in the pitch and envelope shape of individual triggered events, while pattern tempo remains constant.

²<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14568976>

Figure 2. Sequencer playback controls with options relating to tempo, polyphony, instrumentation, and pattern preset choice. Buttons are also provided to instantly clear the entire pattern grid and randomize the probability and velocity of grid positions not currently holding certain events.

3.2 Note Operation Parameters

This class of parameters works at the level of individual musical events by manipulating note numbers or including / excluding events based on note number.

1. *Note Transpose*: This parameter applies a simple additive factor to the note number of all events (default value 0.0, range -10 – 10), which manifests as a simple transposition of the entire pattern assuming that note numbers are arranged in increasing pitch. For non-pitched instrumentation styles (e.g. drums only), a similar principle may be applied but with spectral centroid (bass drum = lowest note, crash cymbal = highest).
2. *Note Randomization Probability*: For uncertain events only, this parameter alters the probability of the event note number being changed to a random other number. Increasing this parameter results in the uncertain component of the pattern becoming increasingly unpredictable in terms of its note progression while keeping articulation and rhythmic content the same. When applied in moderation or in combination with other forms of randomization, this parameter can contribute to adding a degree of short-term musical variation to a pattern, virtually ensuring that the exact same pattern never plays twice even if the higher-order structure of the pattern stays uniform.
3. *Note Filter Cutoff*: This comprises two discrete parameter controls that allow an upper and lower note number cutoff to be applied to a pattern, much like a high- and low-pass filter applied to an audio signal. By default, all available notes have the possibility of being played, but raising (lowering) the lower (upper) cutoff eliminates lower (higher) notes, which responsively changes both the musical complexity and spectral richness of the pattern.

Raising / lowering velocity, probability, tempo, overall pitch, pitch range, and playrate (= pitch) have a relatively clear connotation of an increase / decrease in some quantity related to amount or activity level. As all multipliers are applied with millisecond precision, the temporal resolution of these mappings is limited only by the temporal dis-

tance between successive musical events (grid unit duration). Coupling this with the dynamic nature of the output, it is likely that temporal resolution is most likely poorer, and just-noticeable differences are considerably larger than when mapping to more stationary audio signals, while potentially still being sufficiently small for certain applications.

3.3 Randomization Amount Parameters

This class of mapping parameters aims to affect the output audio signal in musically meaningful ways by manipulating the *amount* of random variation applied to various sequencer-related attributes (e.g. event triggering probability) and signal-specific attributes (e.g. envelope shape). For a given attribute a varying between 0 and a_{max} with default value a_d , mapping parameter p_m controls the amount of randomness (random value r in 0–1 range) added to a_d to yield the final attribute value a_f as:

$$a_f = (1 - p_m) \cdot a_d + p_m \cdot r, \quad \text{where } a_{min} \leq r \leq a_{max} \quad (1)$$

Random value r is generated using the JUCE *Random* class in real time prior to the triggering of all certain and uncertain events, and its ‘contribution’ to the attributes of said event is governed by Eq. 1. The temporal responsiveness of these parameters during real-time application depends on the temporal density of sequenced events, which is a function of the sequencer tempo and the presence of metrical subdivisions in the sequenced pattern. To ensure appropriate attribute-specific perceptual scaling of each mapping parameter, an exponential or logarithmic scaling factor may be applied to p_m :

1. *Velocity Randomization*: This parameter increasingly randomizes the triggering velocity of events, which affects their loudness, envelope shape, and the triggered sound sample. A small amount of velocity randomization can often serve to *humanize* the articulation of most musical patterns, but an excessive amount can cause the rhythmic stability and overall predictability of patterns to break down as rhythmic subdivisions are randomly accentuated or de-accentuated.
2. *Timing Randomization*: This parameter applies a random delay (in sequencer ticks) to every event in

the operational musical event chart. Specifically, increasing the parameter increases the absolute spread of the delay amounts, which adds random timing variability to the musical output. Like with velocity randomization, a small amount of timing variability can humanize most patterns (often desirable), but excessive variability can cause patterns to sound sloppy and ultimately arrhythmic.

3. *Playrate Randomization*: This parameter randomizes the playback rate of all triggered events. The default playback rate is 1x (a sample increment of 1 sample per audio sample interval), and increasing the parameter to its maximum value introduces a spread of 0.99x centered around 1x (resulting in a 0.01x - 1.99x range of possible sample playback rates). This manifests as increasingly random pitch and duration variations that gives percussive patterns an 'other-worldly' quality and detunes melodic patterns.
4. *Envelope Shape Randomization*: This parameter randomizes the shape of an AR (attack-release) envelope applied to each sample when it is triggered. The attack time is 1 ms, and the release time is the remaining length of the sample. By default, the envelope is rectangular (i.e. no envelope). When the parameter value is raised, the envelope shape for triggered events is randomly configured to be anything between the default rectangular envelope and an exponential envelope with increasingly sharp attack and decay. The resulting output is hence made up of sounds that randomly vary in envelope shape. A small amount of envelope shape may serve to humanize a performance, but excessively exponential envelopes can cause musical events to sound overly impulsive and unnatural.
5. *Bandwidth Randomization*: This parameter randomly varies the bandwidth of each triggered sample by manipulating the cutoff frequencies of 2nd order Butterworth low-pass and high-pass filters that operate on the sample (every sample has its own dedicated filters). By default, each sample has a bandwidth of 20 Hz – 20 kHz, but as the parameter value increases, the low-pass cutoff frequency spread increases (maximum range 500 Hz – 5 kHz) as does the high-pass cutoff spread (maximum range 20 Hz – 320 Hz). This results in a very distinct sonic special effect comparable to a traditional auto-filter.
6. *Probability Randomization*: This parameter applies an increasing degree of random variability to the probability of all uncertain chart events, which randomly alters their likelihood of triggering. As such, the audible result is a marginally less predictable musical pattern, although the effect of the parameter on the resulting output is indirect in nature as it works by manipulating triggering probability and not sound attributes directly.

7. *Sample Startpoint Randomization*: This parameter increasingly randomizes the exact audio sample index from which triggered audio events play (anywhere between the sound clip start and 40% of its length). The resulting output is a stream of auditory events that sound randomly chopped at the start, which manifests as an unusual and unnatural special effect.

The musical changes elicited by the randomization amount parameters can have various connotations that influence listener interpretations of the phenomenon under observation, and should therefore be factored into design choices. In some cases, the connotation is very clearly negative (e.g. delay / startpoint / envelope / playrate of melodic samples) that causes the music to sound out-of-tune, out-of-time or 'chopped'. In others (playrate of percussive samples, bandwidth), it is ambiguous as due to the *special effect*-like nature of the resulting musical changes that are neither clearly positive / negative nor have any clear embodied connection with the constructs of size or amount. They can potentially be used to signal specific anomalies during process monitoring tasks, but listener training will likely be necessary. Regarding perceptual resolution, although all of the above parameters are technically continuous from 0–1, the non-stationary nature of the musical output most likely makes it impossible for continuous-valued data trajectories to reliably be deduced from listening to the output even if the changes themselves are salient. A conservative estimate is that one may deduce binary or ternary states, and it therefore appears appropriate to quantize the input data variable to 2-3 discrete levels prior to mapping.

Regarding orthogonality in the perceptual domain, as the mapping parameters pertain to sequencer playback and not directly auditory perceptual attributes, the question of their perceptual independence is an interesting one. In particular, the linear multiplier parameters are conceptually distinct and may afford considerable perceptual independence from each other (e.g. *playrate multiplier* – *probability multiplier*) as well as several randomization amount parameters (e.g. *probability multiplier* – *delay randomization*), which may be suited to representing independent variables independently. At the same time, there are several combinations that may interfere with each other (e.g. *note filter cutoff* – *probability multiplier*, *sample startpoint randomization* – *velocity multiplier*). As with traditional mapping parameters, it is important to consider the implications perceptual interactions as part of the design process.

3.4 Interactive Demos

In the attached supplementary folder, several examples of real-time interactive sonification are provided. In all cases, angular velocity / orientation data from forearm-mounted inertial sensors are used to control various combinations of the aforementioned parameters. Although lacking clear use case scenarios at present, these demos serve to demonstrate the level of real-time responsive musical control afforded by the platform and parameters.

4. DISCUSSION

In this work, I have demonstrated how a probabilistic generative musical platform can serve as a medium for sonifying multivariate data. In this paradigm, data variables may be mapped to deterministic and nondeterministic properties of the generative process, ultimately conveying information about the data through variations in musical articulation, dynamics, timbre, and rhythmic patterning.

Although the platform is yet to be formally evaluated, there are several aspects of the overall approach worth discussing. Relative to the variety of generative music paradigms devised of the years [21, 22], the notion of a probabilistic step sequencer operating based on limited user input and random number generation is not altogether novel or complex. But based on initial experimentation, my current appraisal is that when configured suitably with a well-designed set of audio sample clips and initial rhythmic pattern, the platform is capable of producing musical outputs that expressively convey information in multivariate datasets. Future user studies will investigate combinations of parameters (base randomization amount values for timing, velocity, probability, note) for ensuring a balance between a predictable repetitive base structure and musically interesting short-term variations. In addition, it will also be necessary to experimentally ascertain optimal base values for the velocity and probability multipliers so as to balance task performance and musical arousal for various use cases [28]. A larger palette of instrumentation styles must be designed and rendered to suit user variability in musical taste as well as the stylistic requirements of different application domains. Finally, it will be necessary to design and evaluate discrete combinations of instrumentation styles, mapping parameters, and sequenced musical arrangements in well-defined sonification use cases.

Concerning the set of available mappable parameters, key aspects such as perceptual salience, meaningfulness, and orthogonality have briefly been remarked upon previously. Overall, it appears that depending on the mapping choices made, the generative paradigm has considerable potential for representing data changes in a salient and musically interesting manner, although the perceptual resolution of many affected musical attributes may be limited both in time and in terms of exact value. In order to quantify the informative potential of each parameter in terms of task accuracy and response time, experimental comparisons such as [12, 18] with univariate and multivariate mappings will be necessary to conduct. The current palette mappable parameters allows deterministic control of deterministic and nondeterministic musical attributes alike, opening up an interesting parameter space for musical metaphors for communication. Ultimately, application-specific user-centered studies will need to be carried out so as to ascertain meaningful combination of metaphors for different target groups. In addition, clear distinctions will need to be made empirically between parameters that should contribute to adding musical interest independently of the data, and parameters that data variables should be mapped to. To facilitate meaningful exploration, future versions of the platform will include an expanded mappable parameter set

to allow further real-time manipulation of symbolic and signal-related properties alike.

5. CONCLUSION

The core concept of mapping data variables to nondeterministic aspects of generative music synthesis seems worthy of investigation in sonification applications that (a) involve long-term listening, (b) may rely on musical appeal to support the goals of the user, (c) convey a relatively small number of data variables that evolve slowly over time and can tolerate discretization to 2-3 values. Although the current work made use of a relatively basic sequencer architecture and generative paradigm, it appears so far that the biggest potential advantage of such mappings over traditional ones is that they elicit sonic changes that are both perceptually salient and musically compelling. I attribute this to the ‘predictable unpredictability’ brought about by deterministic mappings to nondeterministic components of the music generation process. Using a probabilistic multitrack sequencing paradigm affords symbol-level manipulation possibilities simply not achievable when mapping to pre-recorded stereo mixes / stems. This facilitates the creation of multiple perceptually orthogonal mappings that are clearly separable not only from each other but also from the short-term evolution and variability of the music itself. In conclusion, I believe that skilful data-driven manipulation of determinism and nondeterminism can effectively unleash the latent potential of generative music as a data communication medium.

Acknowledgments

I would like to thank my supervisors Sofia Dahl and Erika G. Spaich for continuing to support risky creative exploration in times of significant uncertainty.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] T. Hermann, “Taxonomy and definitions for sonification and auditory display,” in *Proceedings of the 14th International Conference on Auditory Display (ICAD)*, Paris, France, June 24 - 27, 2008, pp. 1–8.
- [2] P. Vickers, “Sonification and music, music and sonification,” in *The Routledge Companion to Sounding Art*. Routledge, 2016, pp. 135–144.
- [3] P. Vickers, B. Hogg, and D. Worrall, “Aesthetics of sonification: Taking the subject-position,” in *Body, sound and space in music and beyond: multimodal explorations*. Routledge, 2017, pp. 89–109.
- [4] J. G. Neuhoff, “Is sonification doomed to fail,” in *Proceedings of the 25th International Conference on Auditory Display (ICAD)*, 2019, pp. 327–330.
- [5] J. Middleton, J. Hakulinen, K. Tiitinen, J. Hella, T. Keskinen, P. Huuskonen, J. Culver, J. Linna, M. Turunen, M. Ziat *et al.*, “Data-to-music sonification and user engagement,” *Frontiers in big Data*, vol. 6, p. 1206081, 2023.

- [6] N. Rönnerberg, “Sonification for conveying data and emotion,” in *Proceedings of the 16th International Audio Mostly Conference*, 2021, pp. 56–63.
- [7] G. Weinberg and T. Thatcher, “Interactive sonification: Aesthetics, functionality and performance,” *Leonardo Music Journal*, vol. 16, pp. 9–12, 2006.
- [8] B. N. Walker and M. A. Nees, “Theory of sonification,” *The sonification handbook*, vol. 1, pp. 9–39, 2011.
- [9] F. Grond and T. Hermann, “Interactive sonification for data exploration: How listening modes and display purposes define design guidelines,” *Organised Sound*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 41–51, 2014.
- [10] P. Vickers, “Ars informatica – ars electronica: Improving sonification aesthetics,” in *Understanding and Designing for Aesthetic Experience (Workshop at HCI 2005: The 19th British HCI Group Annual Conference)*, Edinburgh, UK, September 2005.
- [11] P. Kantan, E. G. Spaich, and S. Dahl, “A technical framework for musical biofeedback in stroke rehabilitation,” *IEEE Transactions on Human-Machine Systems*, vol. 52, no. 2, pp. 220–231, 2022.
- [12] T. Hildebrandt, T. Hermann, and S. Rinderle-Ma, “Continuous sonification enhances adequacy of interactions in peripheral process monitoring,” *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, vol. 95, pp. 54–65, 2016.
- [13] B. Van Kerrebroeck and P.-J. Maes, “A breathing sonification system to reduce stress during the covid-19 pandemic,” *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 12, p. 623110, 2021.
- [14] S. Roddy and B. Bridges, “Addressing the Mapping Problem in Sonic Information Design through Embodied Image Schemata, Conceptual Metaphors, and Conceptual Blending,” *Journal of Sonic Studies*, no. 17, 2018.
- [15] H. Feinstein, “Meaning and visual metaphor,” *Studies in art education*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 45–55, 1982.
- [16] D. Worrall, “Sonification: A prehistory,” in *Proc. of the 24th Int. Conf. on Auditory Display (ICAD)*, 2018, pp. 177–182.
- [17] L. Stockmann, A. Berndt, and N. Röber, “A musical instrument based on 3d data and volume sonification techniques,” in *Proc. of the Audio Mostly Conference*, 2008, pp. 72–79.
- [18] P. R. Kantan, “Comparing sonification strategies applied to musical and non-musical signals for auditory guidance purposes,” in *19th Sound and Music Computing Conference, SMC 2022*. Sound and Music Computing Network, 2022, pp. 279–286.
- [19] P.-J. Maes, J. Buhmann, and M. Leman, “3MO: A Model for Music-Based Biofeedback,” *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, vol. 1, 12 2016.
- [20] P. R. Kantan, E. G. Spaich, and S. Dahl, “A metaphor-based technical framework for musical sonification in movement rehabilitation,” in *The 26th International Conference on Auditory Display (ICAD)*, 2021.
- [21] A. Dash and K. Agres, “Ai-based affective music generation systems: A review of methods and challenges,” *ACM Computing Surveys*, vol. 56, no. 11, pp. 1–34, 2024.
- [22] S. Hunt, C. Nash, and T. Mitchell, “Thoughts on interactive generative music composition,” in *2nd Conference on Computer Simulation of Musical Creativity*, 2017.
- [23] P. N. Johnson-Laird, “Freedom and constraint in creativity,” *The nature of creativity: Contemporary psychological perspectives*, vol. 202, 1988.
- [24] P. Sloan, “Listening to possibility: Randomness as musical material,” Master’s thesis, Mills College, 2014.
- [25] L. Kiss and K. J. Linnell, “Making sense of background music listening habits: An arousal and task-complexity account,” *Psychology of Music*, vol. 51, no. 1, pp. 89–106, 2023.
- [26] A. T. Rödel, “Listening to background music while studying-emotional drive or cognitive overload?” Master’s thesis, University of Twente, 2021.
- [27] E. H. Margulis, *On repeat: How music plays the mind*. Oxford University Press, 2013.
- [28] A. B. Ünal, D. de Waard, K. Epstude, and L. Steg, “Driving with music: Effects on arousal and performance,” *Transportation research part F: traffic psychology and behaviour*, vol. 21, pp. 52–65, 2013.